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// Acapella Assay Language / Image Analysis
// 2024-04-05 13:36:39 +0200
// AcapellaVersion: 3.1.2.110719
```

```
AAL::GetData()
AAL::FindNuclei()
AAL::CalculateMorphologyProperties()
AAL::CalculateIntensityProperties()
AAL::SelectPopulation()
AAL::FindCytoplasm()
AAL::SelectCellRegion()
AAL::SelectCellRegion()
AAL::SelectCellRegion()
AAL::CalculateIntensityProperties()
AAL::CalculateIntensityProperties()
AAL::CalculateIntensityProperties()
AAL::CalculateProperties()
AAL::CalculateProperties()
AAL::SelectCellRegion()
AAL::FindSpots()
AAL::CalculateMorphologyProperties()
AAL::SelectPopulation()
AAL::SelectPopulation()
AAL::CalculateIntensityProperties()
AAL::CalculateIntensityProperties()
AAL::CalculateIntensityProperties()
AAL::FindSpots()
AAL::SelectPopulation()
AAL::SelectPopulation()
AAL::ReturnResults()
```

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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="ymid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
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```

```
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<a n="image_title" t="s">Channels</a>
<a n="stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</
s></vdata>
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s></vdata>
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s></vdata>
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<a n="stencil_title" t="s">Overlays</a>
<a n="tracker" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
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</a>
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</m>
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t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.FindNuclei.Outputs.AttrTable.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
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<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
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</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</
s></vdata>
</m>
```

```
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="s">0</a>
<a n="cRenderSettings" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Render" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="Colormode_ColorTranslator" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Colormode"
t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Colormode</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="colormode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Images</a>
<a n="palette" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">ScaleBar</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="f">NaN</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">Stencils</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="rainbowsize" t="f">10</a>
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</a>
</m>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Nuclei" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString" t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.FindNuclei.Outputs.Nuclei.dataitem</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</
a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="InitialMaskFindNuclei" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Initial Mask</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">InitialMaskFindNuclei</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Initial Mask should be slightly larger than the actual nuclei and all nuclei
under interest must be present on it. If required adjust the parameter Common Threshold.</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Initial Mask</s></vdata>
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</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
```

```
</a>
<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.InitialMaskFindNuclei</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTable0n" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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</a>
<a n="SummaryTableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Summary</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</a>
<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s"></a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="Controls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Images" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</
s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
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</a>
<a n="stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Initial
Mask</s></vdata>
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>red</s></
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</m>
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<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</
s></vdata>
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</a>
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</a>
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```

```
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<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
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</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</
s></vdata>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">red</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Initial@20Mask" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
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</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="i">0</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Nuclei" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString" t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.FindNuclei.Outputs.InitialMask.dataitem</a>
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</a>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</
a>
</m>
</a>
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<a n="LowContrastFindNuclei" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Low Contrast Objects</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">LowContrastFindNuclei</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">1 objects are discarded as low contrast artifacts. If required adjust the
parameter Contrast.</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
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<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Low Contrast Objects</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.LowContrastFindNuclei</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
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<a n="SummaryTable0n" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
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</a>
<a n="SummaryTableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Summary</s></vdata>
```

```
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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</a>
<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s"></a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="Controls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Images" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGQEAJAAQ=
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</
s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
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</m>
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<a n="stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Low
Contrast Objects</s></vdata>
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Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjBAAAAGAC
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</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>white</s></
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</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>white</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">white</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Low@20Contrast@200objects" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
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</a>
<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
```

```

</m>
</a>
</m>
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<a n="current_frame" t="i">0</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Nuclei" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString" t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.FindNuclei.Outputs.LowContrastObjects.dataitem</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Callbacks" t="i">0</a>
<a n="current_tab" t="s">NucleiFindNuclei</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Inputs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="NucleiDetectionChannel_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Exp1Cam1</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select channel for nuclei detection</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">NucleiDetectionChannel_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Channel</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Compare the detection results by the different channels and select the most appropriate one.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Channel selection</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
<a n="WizardTabNames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindNuclei</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindNuclei.NucleiDetectionChannel_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Exp1Cam1</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NucleiDetectionAlgorithm" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">B</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select method for nuclei detection</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">NucleiDetectionAlgorithm</a>

```

```

<a n="Label" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Compare the detection results by the different methods and select the
most appropriate one.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Method selection</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindNuclei</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindNuclei.AdditionalParameters.title</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">B</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="4"><vdata k="4" t="string"><s>A</
s><s>B</s><s>C</s><s>M</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>B</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ThresholdAdjustment" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0.4</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Controls common threshold calculation. Adjust by the tuning illustration
Initial Mask.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Simple</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">ThresholdAdjustment</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Common Threshold</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1.0</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="GoodnessCalcON" t="i">1</a>
<a n="GoodnessProc" t="s">AAL::GoodnessProc_CommonThreshold()</a>
<a n="Iview_Wizard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2"
t="string"><s>InitialMaskFindNuclei</s><s>NucleiFindNuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select the parameter value so that the Initial Mask is slightly larger
than the actual nuclei and all nuclei under interest are present on it.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Common Adaptive Threshold</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindNuclei</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">0.05</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindNuclei.AdditionalParameters.ThresholdAdjustment</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0.4</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="10" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="10"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJybNRMEdtrPATMn7Y3B4DKUf90eAQweQMUf26eBwT0o/Ev7s2dA4A1U3Qd7AK9V
IwA=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">0.1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="MinimumNuclearArea" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">30</a>

```

```

<a n="Description" t="s">Controls Common Adaptive Threshold calculation. Adjust by the illustration Initial Mask.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Simple</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">i</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">MinimumNuclearArea</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Area</a>
<a n="max" t="s">5000</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select the parameter value so that from one side small artifacts are not recognized as nuclei and from the other the actual nuclei are not discarded as objects with too small area.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Minimum Nuclear Area</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindNuclei</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">2</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindNuclei.AdditionalParameters.MinimumNuclearArea</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"> $\mu\text{m}^2$ </a>
<a n="value" t="s">30</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="10" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="10" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZWBg4AJiEScWA2IjIA4A4gogPgHEExgZGBSYGRgAKQACuA==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">6</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NuclearSplittingAdjustment" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">7.0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">The Split Factor influence on splitting of clump nuclei to the individual objects. Range 1..100. Smaller values result with higher number of objects.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Simple</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">NuclearSplittingAdjustment</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Split Factor</a>
<a n="max" t="s">100.0</a>
<a n="min" t="s">1.0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select the parameter value so that from one side small artifacts are not recognized as nuclei and from the other the actual nuclei are not discarded as objects with too small area.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Split Factor</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindNuclei</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">0.5</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindNuclei.AdditionalParameters.More.NuclearSplittingAdjustment</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">14</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="7" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="7" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">

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```
eJxjYmBgYAZiViBmB2IuIOYHYkkgBgACxABE
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1.0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="IndividualThresholdAdjustment" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue"
t="s">0.4</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">The parameter adjusts the object borders, i.e. the detected nuclei could
appear larger or smaller.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Simple</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">IndividualThresholdAdjustment</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Individual Threshold</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1.0</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="AutoTune" t="i">1</a>
<a n="AutoTuneProc" t="s">OptimizeITA()</a>
<a n="AutotuneStencilname" t="s">NucleiDetectionData.NucleiIllustrations.Nuclei</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select the parameter value, which corresponds to the most appropriate
border positions.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Individual Threshold</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindNuclei</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">0.05</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindNuclei.AdditionalParameters.More.IndividualThresholdAdjustment</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0.7</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="10" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="10"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJybNRMEdtrPAtn7Y3B4DKUf90eAQweQMUf26eBwT0o/Ev7s2dA4A1U3Qd7AK9V
IwA=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">0.1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="MinimumNuclearContrast" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0.1</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Defines the minimum allowed contrast of nucleus. All objects with contrast
less than the limit are discarded as artifacts. Adjust by the tuning illustration Low Contrast
Nuclei.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Simple</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">MinimumNuclearContrast</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Contrast</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1.0</a>
<a n="min" t="s">-1.0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Iview_Wizard" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>LowContrastFindNuclei</s><s>NucleiFindNuclei</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select the parameter value so that from one side low contrast
artifacts are not recognized as nuclei and from the other the actual nuclei are not discarded as low
contrast objects.</a>
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<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Minimum Nuclear Contrast</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindNuclei</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s">&amp;gt;</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">0.05</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindNuclei.AdditionalParameters.More.MinimumNuclearContrast</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0.1</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="8" t="double" rank="1" dimsiz0="8"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBB/sZoGDWTBBYaQ+hd9obg8FhKP8kLL4JFX9sDwCunRiE
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">0.1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NucDiam" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">13.0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Expected diameter of nuclei. Smaller values yield more fragmented and
smaller objects. Range: 2..40.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">NucDiam</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Diameter</a>
<a n="max" t="s">40.0</a>
<a n="min" t="s">2.0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="AutoTune" t="i">1</a>
<a n="AutoTuneProc" t="s">Set(NucDiam=NucleiDetectionData.EstimatedDiam)</a>
<a n="AutotuneStencilname" t="s">NucleiDetectionData.Nuclei</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Expected diameter of nuclei. Smaller values yield more fragmented and
smaller objects. Range: 2..40.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Diameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindNuclei</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">2.0</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindNuclei.AdditionalParameters.NucDiam</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s">µm</a>
<a n="value" t="s">13.0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">4.0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SplitTuner" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0.4</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Controls splitting of stuck nuclei. Range: 0..1.0. At the value 0, splitting
is switched off. Higher values return increasingly more splitting events.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">SplitTuner</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Splitting Coefficient</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1.0</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Controls splitting of stuck nuclei. Range: 0..1.0. At the value 0,

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splitting is switched off. Higher values return increasingly more splitting events.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Splitting Coefficient</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindNuclei</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">0.05</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindNuclei.AdditionalParameters.SplitTuner</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0.4</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">0.1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="DynRanThr" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0.4</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">This is a relative threshold determining how dark objects can be detected.
Range: 0..1.0. With smaller values, darker objects are detected.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">DynRanThr</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Common Threshold</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1.0</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">This is a relative threshold determining how dark objects can be
detected. Range: 0..1.0. With smaller values, darker objects are detected.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Common Threshold</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindNuclei</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">0.05</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindNuclei.AdditionalParameters.DynRanThr</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0.4</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">0.1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OutputName" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Name of the output population. Default name is Nuclei.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">OutputName</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Output Population</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultNamingIsUsed" t="i">1</a>
<a n="DefaultString" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="OriginalDefault" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="UsedListCounter" t="i">1</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindNuclei</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>

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<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindNuclei.OutputName</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__initialBuildMinor" t="i">110719</a>
<a n="__initialversion" t="s">3</a>
<a n="__ProcOpenStatus" t="i">1</a>
<a n="__UsedPopulationNamesInCurrentBBRun" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata
k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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</a>
</m>
</a>
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<a n="OutputName" t="s">Nuclei</a>
</m>
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<a n="CalculateMorphologyProperties" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="BBHasBeenSaved"
t="i">1</a>
<a n="bbType" t="s">builtin</a>
<a n="IDName" t="s">CalculateMorphologyProperties</a>
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<a n="Label" t="s">Replace me</a>
<a n="Tabs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="TabItemName" t="s">PopulationCalculateMorphologyProperties</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Population Nuclei with region Nucleus by which the new properties are
calculated.</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
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t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
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</a>
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t="string"><s>Properties Nuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.PopulationCalculateMorphologyProperties</a>
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</a>
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```

```
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t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
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t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
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c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
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label="TranslateColormode" title="ColorMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0"
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<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</
s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
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```

```
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<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
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</m>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
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</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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<a n="Render_Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
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c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
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></CallbackList></m>
</a>
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<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</
```

```
s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
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<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
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t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
</m>
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<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="palette" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
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c="container"></m>
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</m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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label="ReloadFrames" title="Palette" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /></
CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
</m>
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eJxjYIAAAAAIAAE=
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```

```
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<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</
s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
</m>
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<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="f">NaN</a>
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```

```
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<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
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<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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</a>
<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
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eJxjZGQEAJAAQ=
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s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
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<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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</m>
</a>
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s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
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Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
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</m>
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```

```
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="xmax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJzjYWs++GB1swMrZ/ppRasyBwYwiHQAAGUgBo8=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xmin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
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</a>
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="image_title" t="s">Channels</a>
<a n="stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
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<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjBAAAAGAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
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Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
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```

```
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</s></vdata>
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</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="stencil_title" t="s">Overlays</a>
<a n="tracker" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
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</a>
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</m>
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</m>
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</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.CalculateMorphologyProperties.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
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<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="s">0</a>
<a n="cRenderSettings" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Render" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="Colormode_ColorTranslator" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Colormode"
t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Colormode</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="colormode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Images</a>
<a n="palette" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">ScaleBar</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="f">NaN</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">Stencils</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="rainbowsize" t="f">10</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Nuclei" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
```

```
<a n="ListRefString"
t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.CalculateMorphologyProperties.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</a>
a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Callbacks" t="i">0</a>
<a n="current_tab" t="s">PopulationCalculateMorphologyProperties</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Inputs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="WholeCells_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select population</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Population</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SelectedPopulation" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RefString" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.FindNuclei.Outputs.Nuclei.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ValidFlag" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OriginRef" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>FindNuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>FindNuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYmBgAAAADAAD
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="Hidden" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
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<m n="InternalIDNumber" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
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<m n="InvalidatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<m n="NewPopulation" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
```

```
</m>
<m n="OverTakenFrom" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>FindNuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="MyPopulationTypes" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Objects</s></vdata>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateMorphologyProperties</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateMorphologyProperties.WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select region which should be characterized.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Region</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Region</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateMorphologyProperties</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedPropertyOrRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>FindNuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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```

```
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
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<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
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</m>
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</m>
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</a>
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</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateMorphologyProperties.Region</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Method" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a method</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Area_ONOFF" t="s">1</a>
<a n="Area_Unit" t="s"> $\mu\text{m}^2$ </a>
<a n="Length_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Length_Unit" t="s"> $\mu\text{m}$ </a>
<a n="RatioWidthToLength_ONOFF" t="s">1</a>
<a n="Roundness_ONOFF" t="s">1</a>
<a n="Width_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Width_Unit" t="s"> $\mu\text{m}$ </a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateMorphologyProperties</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateMorphologyProperties.Method.title</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Standard</
s><s>STAR</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Standard</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Area_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">1</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Turn the area calculation ON/OFF</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Area_ONOFF</a>
```

```

<a n="Label" t="s">Area</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateMorphologyProperties</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateMorphologyProperties.Method.Area_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"> $\mu\text{m}\leq$ </a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Area_Unit" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s"> $\mu\text{m}\leq$ </a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Unit for area property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Area_Unit</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Area Unit</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateMorphologyProperties</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateMorphologyProperties.Method.Area_ONOFF.Unit</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s"> $\mu\text{m}\leq$ </a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s> $\mu\text{m}\leq$ </
s><s>px</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s> $\mu\text{m}\leq$ </
s></vdata>
</m>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="Roundness_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">1</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Turn the roundness calculation ON/OFF</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Roundness_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Roundness</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateMorphologyProperties</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>

```

```

<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateMorphologyProperties.Method.Roundness_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Width_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Turn the width calculation ON/OFF</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Width_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Width</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateMorphologyProperties</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateMorphologyProperties.Method.Width_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"> $\mu\text{m}$ </a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Width_Unit" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s"> $\mu\text{m}$ </a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Unit for width property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Width_Unit</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Width Unit</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateMorphologyProperties</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateMorphologyProperties.Method.Width_ONOFF.Unit</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s"> $\mu\text{m}$ </a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s> $\mu\text{m}$ </
s><s>px</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s> $\mu\text{m}$ </s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Length_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Turn the length calculation ON/OFF</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>

```

```
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Length_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Length</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateMorphologyProperties</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateMorphologyProperties.Method.Length_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"> $\mu\text{m}$ </a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Length_Unit" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s"> $\mu\text{m}$ </a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Unit for length property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Length_Unit</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Width Unit</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateMorphologyProperties</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateMorphologyProperties.Method.Length_ONOFF.Unit</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s"> $\mu\text{m}$ </a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s> $\mu\text{m}$ /
s</s><px</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s> $\mu\text{m}$ </s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="RatioWidthToLength_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Turn the ratio width to length calculation ON/OFF</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">RatioWidthToLength_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Ratio Width to Length</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateMorphologyProperties</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateMorphologyProperties.Method.RatioWidthToLength_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SuffixForPropertyNames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nucleus</
a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Common prefix for the property names</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">SuffixForPropertyNames</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Output Properties</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultNamingIsUsed" t="i">1</a>
<a n="DefaultString" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="OriginalDefault" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="UsedListCounter" t="i">0</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateMorphologyProperties</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateMorphologyProperties.SuffixForPropertyNames</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="FromInputs2Main" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="RegionTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>FindNuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
```

```
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="__initialBuildMinor" t="i">110719</a>
<a n="__initialversion" t="s">6</a>
<a n="__ProcOpenStatus" t="i">1</a>
<a n="__version" t="s">6</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OutputClass" t="s">Output Properties</a>
<a n="OutputName" t="s">Nucleus</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CalculateIntensityProperties" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="BBHasBeenSaved"
t="i">1</a>
<a n="bbType" t="s">builtin</a>
<a n="IDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties</a>
<a n="ImageView" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Replace me</a>
<a n="Tabs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PopulationCalculateIntensityProperties" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered"
t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">PopulationCalculateIntensityProperties</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Population Nuclei with region Nucleus by which the new properties are
calculated.</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Properties Nuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.PopulationCalculateIntensityProperties</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTableOn" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Summary</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttrTypeTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
</a>
<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s">SingleDefaultOverLay</a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20class@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__cnt_defaults" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Controls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="general" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Render_Colormode_Standard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TranslateColormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="TranslateColormode" title="ColorMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0"
disabled="0" /></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</
```

```
s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize=0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAMAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Labels_Labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ColoringMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
```

```
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAMAAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
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<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="palette" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
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</a>
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</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
</m>
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<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
</m>
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</vdata>
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</m>
</a>
```

```
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<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
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<a n="ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
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label="ReloadFrames" title="ReloadFrames" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList></m>
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<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</
s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="f">NaN</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="5"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
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</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="5" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
```

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<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
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<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</
s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGAAAGAAI=
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</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="3"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAMAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
```

```
</m>
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<a n="xfmid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
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<a n="xmax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJzjYWs++GB1swMrZ/ppRasyBwYwiHQAAGUgBo8=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
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<a n="xmin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJz7VWM3/zy7osP17ceXfNTzdmCAAgCKIQgu
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<a n="ymax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="ymid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="image_title" t="s">Channels</a>
<a n="stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
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```

```
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<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</s></vdata>
</m>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="stencil_title" t="s">Overlays</a>
<a n="tracker" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
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<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.CalculateIntensityProperties.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="s">0</a>
<a n="cRenderSettings" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Render" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="Colormode_ColorTranslator" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Colormode"
t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Colormode</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="colormode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Images</a>
<a n="palette" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">ScaleBar</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="f">NaN</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">Stencils</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="rainbowsize" t="f">10</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Nuclei" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
```

```

<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString"
t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.CalculateIntensityProperties.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Callbacks" t="i">0</a>
<a n="current_tab" t="s">PopulationCalculateIntensityProperties</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Inputs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="channel_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Exp1Cam1</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select channel by which the intensity statistics should be calculated</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="EvalString" t="s">AAL::GetCurrentFrameImages(EvaluationData=EvaluationData)
set(Signal=FrameImages.Exp1Cam1)</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">channel_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Channel</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties.channel_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Exp1Cam1</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1/</s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="WholeCells_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select population</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Population</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SelectedPopulation" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>WholeCells</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RefString" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.CalculateMorphologyProperties.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>

```

```
<m n="ValidFlag" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OriginRef" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>FindNuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>CalculateMorphologyProperties</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZmBgAAAAEAAE
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="Hidden" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<m n="InternalIDNumber" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="InvalidatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="NewPopulation" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OverTakenFrom" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>FindNuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="MyPopulationTypes" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0objects</s></vdata>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties.WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a region which should be characterized</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Region</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Region</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
```

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c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedPropertyOrRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector"
t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>FindNuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
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<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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<m n="_order" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjyGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties.Region</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Method" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a method. Please note that you can enter method sub-section and
switch the individual properties ON/OFF.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Method</a>

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<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Contrast_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="CV_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Max_ONOFF" t="s">1</a>
<a n="Mean_ONOFF" t="s">1</a>
<a n="Median_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Min_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="QuantileFraction" t="s">50</a>
<a n="Quantile_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Stddev_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Sum_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties.Method.title</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Standard</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Standard</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Mean_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">1</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the mean intensity</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Mean_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties.Method.Mean_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Stddev_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the standard deviation</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Stddev_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Standard Deviation</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties.Method.Stddev_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CV_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the coefficient of variance</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">CV_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Coefficient of Variance</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties.Method.CV_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Median_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the median intensity</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Median_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Median</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties.Method.More.Median_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
```

```
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Sum_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the sum/integral intensity</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Sum_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Sum</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties.Method.More.Sum_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Max_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the maximum intensity</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Max_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Maximum</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties.Method.More.Max_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Min_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the minimum intensity</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Min_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Minimum</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
```

```
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties.Method.More.Min_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="QuantileFraction" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">50</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Quantile fraction</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">QuantileFraction</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Quantile Fraction</a>
<a n="max" t="s">100</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">5</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties.Method.More.QuantileFraction</
a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s">%</a>
<a n="value" t="s">50</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">10</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Quantile_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the quantile intensity</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Quantile_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Quantile</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties.Method.More.QuantileFraction.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
```

```
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Contrast_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the contrast</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Contrast_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Contrast</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties.Method.More.Contrast_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
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Nucleus Exp1Cam1</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Common prefix for the property names</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">SuffixForPropertyNames</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Output Properties</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultNamingIsUsed" t="i">1</a>
<a n="DefaultString" t="s">Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1</a>
<a n="OriginalDefault" t="s">Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="UsedListCounter" t="i">0</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties.SuffixForPropertyNames</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
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<a n="__initialversion" t="s">3</a>
<a n="__ProcOpenStatus" t="i">1</a>
<a n="__version" t="s">3</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OutputClass" t="s">Output Properties</a>
<a n="OutputName" t="s">Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean, Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</a>
```

```
</m>
</a>
<a n="SelectPopulation" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="BBHasBeenSaved" t="i">1</a>
<a n="bbType" t="s">builtin</a>
<a n="IDName" t="s">SelectPopulation</a>
<a n="ImageView" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Replace me</a>
<a n="Tabs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PopulationSelectPopulation" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">PopulationSelectPopulation</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Number of selected objects: 64; Number of discarded objects: 12; Total number
of objects: 76</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIClass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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t="string"><s>Selected Objects</s><s>Discarded Objects</s></vdata>
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<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
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t="string"><s>Properties Nuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s">SingleDefaultOverLayMixed</a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20class@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">yellow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">yellow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">red</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">red</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
```

```
c="container"><a n="default_color" t="s">green</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Discarded Objects</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">body</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
</m>
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<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Selected Objects</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@205@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
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ority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
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ority@2c@20style@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">body</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Discarded@20Objects" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">violet</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">2</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">2</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Selected@20Objects" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">blue</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__cnt_defaults" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@Discarded@20Objects" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="color" t="s">violet</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">2</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">2</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
</a>
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n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">blue</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
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</m>
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</m>
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</a>
<a n="Controls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="general" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Render_Colormode_Standard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TranslateColormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="TranslateColormode" title="ColorMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="">
disabled="0" /></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</
s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
</m>
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eJxjYEAAAAAAAE=
</vdata>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
```

```
</m>
</a>
</m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
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<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Labels_Labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
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</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
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</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ColoringMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</
s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
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</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
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dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAMAAE=
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
```

```
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="palette" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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</m>
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label="ReloadFrames" title="Palette" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /></
CallbackList></m>
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<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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eJxjyIAAAAAIAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
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</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
```

```
</a>
<a n="Render_ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ReloadFrames" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</
s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="f">NaN</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="5"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBH/UMK0CDPZThAKE4HABJFgMv
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="5" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
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</a>
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<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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</a>
```

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<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
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s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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```
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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</m>
</a>
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t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s></s></s></s></s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>yellow</
s><s>green</s><s>red</s></vdata>
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t="string"><s>yellow</s><s>green</s><s>red</s></vdata>
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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s><s>Selected Objects</s><s>Discarded Objects</s></vdata>
</m>
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s><s>body</s><s>body</s></vdata>
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t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
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t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation.Outputs.Wholecells_ForIllustration.dataitem<
/s></vdata>
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<a n="cIViewRelatedPopulationData" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Illustration@20SelectPopulation" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="TabName"
```

```
t="s">FilteredSelectPopulation</a>
</m>
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<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>yellow</s><s>green</s><s>red</s></vdata>
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<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">body</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
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<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
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c="container"><a n="Colormode_ColorTranslator" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Colormode"
t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Colormode</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
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<a n="Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="colormode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Images</a>
<a n="palette" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">ScaleBar</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="f">NaN</a>
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<a n="Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">Stencils</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="rainbowsize" t="f">10</a>
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<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Nuclei" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString"
t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation.Outputs.Wholecells_ForIllustration.dataitem</a>
</m>
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a>
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<a n="TabItemName" t="s">FilteredSelectPopulation</a>
```

```
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Qualified objects (64).</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
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t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
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<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
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t="string"><s>Properties Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
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<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.FilteredSelectPopulation</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
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<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
</m>
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t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
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<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
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t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
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n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
```

```
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
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<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
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<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TranslateColormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
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<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</
s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
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</a>
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<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
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eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
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<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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</a>
```

```
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<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
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<a n="Render_Labels_Labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="Render_Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
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</m>
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label="ReloadFrames" title="ColoringMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</
s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
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<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
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<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
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<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
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<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
</m>
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<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
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c="container"></m>
</a>
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Label="ReloadFrames" title="Palette" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /></m>
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<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
</m>
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<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="2" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="2" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYIAAAAAIAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
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</a>
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<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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<a n="ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
```

```
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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label="ReloadFrames" title="ReloadFrames" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList></m>
</a>
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<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</
s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="f">NaN</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="5"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBH/UMK0CDPZThAKE4HABJFGMv
</vdata>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="5" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
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</m>
</a>
```

```
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<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</
s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="3"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
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<a n="xfmid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJwze13NpXHjjP2SH0170hxn7RnA4IE9AHdgCBk=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
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<a n="xmax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJyzs70z2yfW4KCRu0F+YXinAwMYRDoAAFuJBks=
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xmin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJwrLACCAD2Ht1Gf009wmzswQAEAbrIGkA==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<a n="ymax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBD/YMaDQAIt0Djg==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<a n="ymid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="ymin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
```

```
Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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</a>
<a n="image_title" t="s">Channels</a>
<a n="stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="priority" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="stencil_title" t="s">Overlays</a>
<a n="tracker" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
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</m>
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</a>
<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation.Outputs.WholeCells_filtered.DataItem</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="cIViewRelatedPopulationData" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Nuclei" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="TabName" t="s">PopulationSelectPopulation</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</
s></vdata>
```

```
</m>
</a>
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<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString"
t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation.Outputs.WholeCells_filtered.DataItem</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Callbacks" t="i">0</a>
<a n="current_tab" t="s">PopulationSelectPopulation</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Inputs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="WholeCells_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select an input population based on which a new population should be
created.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Population</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SelectedPopulation" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>WholeCells</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RefString" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.CalculateIntensityProperties.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ValidFlag" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OriginRef" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>FindNuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>CalculateIntensityProperties</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
```

```
eJxjYWBgAAAAFAAF
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<m n="Hidden" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<m n="InternalIDNumber" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="InvalidatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<m n="NewPopulation" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OverTakenFrom" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>CalculateMorphologyProperties</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="MyPopulationTypes" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Objects</s></vdata>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation.WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Method" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Filter by Property</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a method by which a new population should be created</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation.Method.title</a>
```

```
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Filter by Property</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Filter by
Property</s><s>Common Filters</s><s>Linear Classifier</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Filter
by Property</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</a>
<a n="Attribute1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper value for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Attribute1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="f">3.00000000000000018e+34</a>
<a n="min" t="f">-3.00000000000000018e+34</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation.Method.Attribute1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">50</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="13" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="13"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJwrt0W6vrhA50C1yDr3h1U0Dpox/Ye+coQ4GIPA5XgHBhC4k0qQBgLbsiH0uQKI
+IFiilrNZRDxZZU0s2aCQI3D2TNA0FMPUefQ6AAA7h8m6g==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="f">47.1799999999999997</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttributeName1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Property by which the filtering criterion is defined</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="EvalString" t="s">AAL::GetSelectedRegion(SelectedLabel=AttributeName1, RegionTable=ScalarTable|
ScalarTable_1=TableForSelectedRegion, SelectedScalarRowIndex_1=SelectedRegionRowIndex)</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeName1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="FinalFilterText" t="s"> _Scalar1&gt;50 and
_Scalar1&lt;500 and _Scalar5&lt;500 and _Scalar2&gt;0.8</a>
<a n="MaxUsedNumberOfFilters" t="i">5</a>
<a n="NumberOfFilters" t="i">5</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus Area [μm<sup>2</sup>]</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Scalar</s></vdata>
</m>
```

```
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>_Scalar1</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>CalculateMorphologyProperties</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>3</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus Area [μm<sup>2</sup>]</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Area of Nucleus [μm<sup>2</sup>]</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Area</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>μm<sup>2</sup></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Area [μm<sup>2</sup>]</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Area [μm<sup>2</sup>]</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="_order" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation.Method.Attribute1.Label</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nucleus Area [μm<sup>2</sup>]</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
<s><s>Nucleus Area [μm<sup>2</sup>]</s><s>Nucleus Roundness</s><s>Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Intensity
Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</s><s>Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus
Area [μm<sup>2</sup>]</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttributeQualifier1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper qualifier for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="display" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</s></vdata>
<s><s>?</s><s>&lt;</s><s>?</s><s>=</s><s>?</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeQualifier1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
```

```
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation.Method.Attribute1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</s></vdata>
<s></s></m>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>&gt;</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Attribute2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper value for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Attribute2</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="f">3.00000000000000018e+34</a>
<a n="min" t="f">-3.00000000000000018e+34</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation.Method.Attribute2</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">500</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="13" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="13"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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+IFiiLrNZRDxZZU0s2aCQI3D2TNA0FMPUefQ6AAA7h8m6g==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="f">47.179999999999997</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttributeName2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Property by which the filtering criterion is defined</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="EvalString" t="s">AAL::GetSelectedRegion(SelectedLabel=AttributeName2, RegionTable=ScalarTable|
ScalarTable_2=TableForSelectedRegion, SelectedScalarRowIndex_2=SelectedRegionRowIndex)</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeName2</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s></vdata>
</m>
```

```

<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Scalar</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>_Scalar1</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>CalculateMorphologyProperties</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>3</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus Area [ $\mu\text{m}$ ]</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Area of Nucleus [ $\mu\text{m}$ ]</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Area</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s> $\mu\text{m}$ </s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Area [ $\mu\text{m}$ ]</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Area [ $\mu\text{m}$ ]</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="_order" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation.Method.Attribute2.label</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nucleus Area [ $\mu\text{m}$ ]</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s></s></s><s>Nucleus Area [ $\mu\text{m}$ ]</s><s>Nucleus Roundness</s><s>Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Intensity
Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</s><s>Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus
Area [ $\mu\text{m}$ ]</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttributeQualifier2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper qualifier for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="display" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</s></s><?</s><s>&lt;</s><s><?</s><s>=</s><s><?</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeQualifier2</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>

```

```
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation.Method.Attribute2.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">&lt;</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>&lt;</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Attribute3" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper value for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Attribute3</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="f">3.00000000000000018e+34</a>
<a n="min" t="f">-3.00000000000000018e+34</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation.Method.Attribute3</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">500</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="13" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="13"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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PtEAod80OgAAFgUQCw==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="f">36.5</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttributeName3" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Property by which the filtering criterion is defined</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="EvalString" t="s">AAL:GetSelectedRegion(SelectedLabel=AttributeName3, RegionTable=ScalarTable|
ScalarTable_3=TableForSelectedRegion, SelectedScalarRowIndex_3=SelectedRegionRowIndex)</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeName3</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
```

```
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Scalar</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>_Scalar5</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>CalculateIntensityProperties</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>4</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Intensity Nucleus
Exp1Cam1 Maximum</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Maximum intensity of Nucleus
by channel Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Maximum Intensity</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Counts/Pixel</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Maximum Intensity</
s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Maximum intensity of Nucleus by
channel Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="_order" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYWBgAAAAFAAF
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation.Method.Attribute3.Label</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s></
s><s>Nucleus Area [μm]</s><s>Nucleus Roundness</s><s>Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Intensity
Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</s><s>Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttributeQualifier3" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper qualifier for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="display" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</
s><s>?</s><s>&lt;</s><s>?</s><s>=</s><s>?</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeQualifier3</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation.Method.Attribute3.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">&lt;</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>&lt;</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Attribute4" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper value for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Attribute4</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="f">3.00000000000000018e+34</a>
<a n="min" t="f">-3.00000000000000018e+34</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation.Method.Attribute4</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0.8</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="13" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="13"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxb5/6wSmTdY/uzZ0Dgif2bwBlyra+f2r/R3630z/3cnnvrssrjmi/stawmna73
eGmvlTH1CmfGK3vPuQ1qh9pe22co5VRULX1j3748/JTRkbf2Ha1RL/c8fmfPAAyf
7PsPfdWI6f9gDwAjczPV
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="f">0.0350299999999999986</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttributeName4" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Property by which the filtering criterion is defined</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="EvalString" t="s">AAL::GetSelectedRegion(SelectedLabel=AttributeName4, RegionTable=ScalarTable|
ScalarTable_4=TableForSelectedRegion, SelectedScalarRowIndex_4=SelectedRegionRowIndex)</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeName4</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus Roundness</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Scalar</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>_Scalar2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>CalculateMorphologyProperties</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>3</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus Roundness</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Roundness of Nucleus</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Roundness</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Roundness</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Roundness</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="__order" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation.Method.Attribute4.label</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nucleus Roundness</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s></
s><s>Nucleus Area [ $\mu\text{m}$ ]</s><s>Nucleus Roundness</s><s>Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Intensity
Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</s><s>Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus
Roundness</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttributeQualifier4" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper qualifier for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="display" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</
s><s>?</s><s>&lt;</s><s>?</s><s>=</s><s>?</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeQualifier4</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
```

```
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation.Method.Attribute4.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>&gt;</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Attribute5" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper value for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Attribute5</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation.Method.Attribute5</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttributeName5" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Property by which the filtering criterion is defined</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="EvalString" t="s">AAL::GetSelectedRegion(SelectedLabel=AttributeName5, RegionTable=ScalarTable|
ScalarTable_5=TableForSelectedRegion, SelectedScalarRowIndex_5=SelectedRegionRowIndex)</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeName5</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>None</s></vdata>
</m>
```

```

<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>None</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</m>
</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation.Method.Attribute5.Label</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s"></a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
<s><s>Nucleus Area [μm<sup>2</sup>]</s><s>Nucleus Roundness</s><s>Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Intensity
Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</s><s>Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttributeQualifier5" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper qualifier for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="display" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</s></vdata>
<s><s>?</s><s><s>&lt;</s><s>?</s><s>=</s><s>?</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeQualifier5</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation.Method.Attribute5.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</s></vdata>
<s><s>&gt;=</s><s>&lt;</s><s>&lt;=</s><s>!=</s></vdata>
</m>

```

```

</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>&gt;</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="BooleanOperations" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s"> F1 and F2 and F3 and F4</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define boolean operations between filters, e.g. (F1 OR F2) AND F3. As default AND operations are used.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">BooleanOperations</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Boolean Operations</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultNamingIsUsed" t="i">1</a>
<a n="DefaultString" t="s"> F1 and F2 and F3 and F4</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation.Method.More.BooleanOperations</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s"> F1 and F2 and F3 and F4</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OutputName" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Name of the output population.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">OutputName</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Output Population</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultNamingIsUsed" t="i">1</a>
<a n="DefaultString" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="OriginalDefault" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="UsedListCounter" t="i">1</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation.OutputName</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
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```

```
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<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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<a n="IDName" t="s">FindCytoplasm</a>
<a n="ImageView" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Replace me</a>
<a n="Tabs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="CellsFindCytoplasm" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">CellsFindCytoplasm</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Detected cell borders. Inspect results and if required adjust parameters.</a>
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</a>
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t="s">rainbow</a>
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<a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Cell</a>
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<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
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n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Nucleus</a>
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<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
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```
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t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="PositionOld" t="i">3</a>
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<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
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n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
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<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
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```

```
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<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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</m>
```

```
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<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="description" t="s"></a>
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<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
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s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
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<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
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</vdata>
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<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
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</m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
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<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
</m>
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</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
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eJxjYIAAAAAIAAE=
</vdata>
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<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
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<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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<a n="Render_ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ReloadFrames" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList></m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="f">NaN</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="5"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBH/UMKOCDPZThAKE4HABJFgMv
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="5" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMAEAAAUAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="rainbowsize" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="value" t="f">10</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
```

```
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGQEAJAAQ=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</
s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYQAAAAFAAI=
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="3"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xfmid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJz7GHbJz5zhgv3ntRc0F2mespf88PvQp7XX7AGg8w2V
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xmax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxbaZAJz1xQ6uAaL+FYa7bBoePq1DKN3BIHAGfTCN4=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xmin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJzTWv3cs+AfU80U3Que72uydShbvmhaha6lAwCbeAvB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
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<a n="ymax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBD/YMaDQAIt0Djg==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ymid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBB/YMaDQAIP0DXg==
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
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<a n="ymin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMA0AAAYAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="image_title" t="s">Channels</a>
<a n="stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="4"><vdata k="4" t="string"><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="4"><vdata k="4" t="string"><s>rainbow</
s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="4"><vdata k="4"
t="string"><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="4" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="4" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGRgAAAABwAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="4"><vdata k="4" t="string"><s>Nucleus</
s><s>Cell</s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="4" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="4"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAFAAAQAAE=
</vdata>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="priority" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="4" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="4"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAFAAAQAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
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<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="4"><vdata k="4" t="string"><s>Border</
s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="stencil_title" t="s">0verlays</a>
<a n="tracker" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.FindCytoplasm.Outputs.WhoLeCells_illustrative.dataitem</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="4"><vdata k="4" t="string"><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</
s><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="4"><vdata k="4" t="string"><s>Border</
s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Cell" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
```

```
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="s">0</a>
<a n="cRenderSettings" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Render" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="Colormode_ColorTranslator" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Colormode"
t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Colormode</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="colormode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Images</a>
<a n="palette" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">ScaleBar</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="f">NaN</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">Stencils</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="rainbowsize" t="f">10</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Cells" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Cells</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">Cells</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString"
t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.FindCytoplasm.Outputs.WholeCells_illustrative.dataitem</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</
a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Callbacks" t="i">0</a>
<a n="current_tab" t="s">CellsFindCytoplasm</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Inputs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="CytoplasmDetectionChannel_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue"
t="s">Exp1Cam1</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select channel for cytoplasm detection</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Simple</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">CytoplasmDetectionChannel_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Channel</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Compare the cytoplasm detection results by the different channels and
select the most appropriate one.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Channel selection</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindCytoplasm</a>
```

```
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindCytoplasm.CytoplasmDetectionChannel_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Exp2Cam2</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Exp2Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Nuclei_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select population of nuclei. Cytoplasm regions are detected around the pre-detected nuclei.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Nuclei_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SelectedPopulation" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>WholeCells_filtered</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RefString" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation.Outputs.WholeCells_filtered.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ValidFlag" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OriginRef" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectPopulation</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectPopulation</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZWBgAAAAGAAG
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="Hidden" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="InternalIDNumber" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYmBgAAAADAAD
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="InvalidatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<m n="NewPopulation" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OverTakenFrom" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectPopulation</s></vdata>
</m>
```

```

vdata>
</m>
<m n="MyPopulationTypes" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Objects</s></vdata>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select the appropriate list of nuclei. Please note, tht the parameter
is visible only if thare exist more than one list of nuclei.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindCytoplasm</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindCytoplasm.Nuclei_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Nuclei/
s><s>Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei
Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Method" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">A</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select method for cytoplasm detection</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Compare the detection results by the different methods and select the
most appropriate one.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Method selection</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindCytoplasm</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindCytoplasm.Method.title</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">B</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>A</
s><s>B</s><s>C</s><s>D</s><s>E</s><s>F</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>B</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="MembraneChannel_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue"
t="s">Exp1Cam1</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select the membrane channel for the cytoplasm detection method F. The
membrane stained image is used as additional informtion (in addition to the cytoplasm stained image
given by input Channel).</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">MembraneChannel_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Membrane Channel</a>

```

```

<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select the membrane stained image. Please note, that the parameter is
visible only if the method F has been selected.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Membrane Channel selection</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindCytoplasm</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindCytoplasm.Method.MembraneChannel_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Exp1Cam1</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CytoplasmThresholdAdjustment" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue"
t="s">0.45</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Controls Common Adaptive Threshold calculation for cytoplasm detection. The
input is used by the Methods B, C and E.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Simple</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">CytoplasmThresholdAdjustment</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Common Threshold</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1.0</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select the parameter value, which provides the most appropriate
detection results. Adjust together with the parameter Individual Threshold.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Common Adaptive Threshold</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindCytoplasm</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">0.05</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindCytoplasm.Method.CytoplasmThresholdAdjustment</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0.25</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">0.1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CytoplasmIndividualThresholdAdjustment" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue"
t="s">0.15</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">The parameter adjusts the object borders, i.e. the detected cytoplasm
regions can appear larger or smaller.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Simple</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">CytoplasmIndividualThresholdAdjustment</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Individual Threshold</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1.0</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="GoodnessCalcON" t="i">1</a>
<a n="GoodnessProc" t="s">AAL::GoodnessProc_CytoplasmIndividualThreshold()</a>

```

```

<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select the parameter value, which corresponds to the most appropriate
border positions.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Individual Threshold</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindCytoplasm</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">0.05</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindCytoplasm.Method.CytoplasmIndividualThresholdAdjustment</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0.2</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="12" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="12"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJybNRMVEvtrPAtm77Y3B4DCUfxLKvwzL37RnAIMHUPHH9mLg8Awq/9L+7BkQeANV
98EeABv8KbM=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">0.05</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OutputName" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">MultiNucleated
Cells</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Name of the created/detected population.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">OutputName</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Output Population</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultNamingIsUsed" t="i">1</a>
<a n="DefaultString" t="s">MultiNucleated Cells</a>
<a n="OriginalDefault" t="s">MultiNucleated Cells</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="UsedListCounter" t="i">1</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindCytoplasm</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindCytoplasm.OutputName</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">MultiNucleated Cells</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__initialBuildMinor" t="i">110719</a>
<a n="__initialversion" t="s">3</a>
<a n="__ProcOpenStatus" t="i">1</a>
<a n="__UsedPopulationNamesInCurrentBBRun" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata
k="1" t="string"><s>MultiNucleated Cells</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="__version" t="s">3</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>

```

```

<a n="OutputClass" t="s">Output Regions</a>
<a n="OutputName" t="s">Cell, Cytoplasm, Membrane</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SelectCellRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="BBHasBeenSaved" t="i">1</a>
<a n="bbType" t="s">builtin</a>
<a n="IDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion</a>
<a n="ImageView" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Replace me</a>
<a n="Tabs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="CellRegionSelectCellRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">CellRegionSelectCellRegion</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">The created region Nucleus Region. </a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Nucleus Region</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Properties Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.CellRegionSelectCellRegion</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTable0n" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Summary</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttrTypeTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s">SingleDefaultOverLay</a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
<a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20class@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Cell</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Body</a>
</m>
</a>

```

```
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Body</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Cytoplasm</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Body</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Nucleus Region</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Membrane</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@205@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@205@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20priority@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@206@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20pri
ority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@206@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20priority@2c@20
style@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Body</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@207@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20pri
ority@2c@20style@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Body</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nucleus@20Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Body</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">4</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Cell" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
```

```
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Cytoplasm" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">3</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">3</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Membrane" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">2</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">2</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__cnt_defaults" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@Nucleus@20Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Body</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">4</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Controls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="general" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Render_Colormode_Standard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TranslateColormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="TranslateColormode" title="ColorMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0"
disabled="0" /></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
```

```
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize=0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Labels_Labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ColoringMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
```

```
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAAAE=
</vdata>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
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<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="palette" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="Palette" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
</m>
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</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="2" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="2" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYIAAAAAIAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
```

```
</m>
</a>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
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<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
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</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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</a>
</m>
</a>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
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c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
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</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
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label="ReloadFrames" title="ReloadFrames" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</
s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="f">NaN</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="5"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBH/UMKOCDPZThAKE4HABJFgMv
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="5" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMAEAAAUAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="rainbowsize" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="value" t="f">10</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGQEAJAAQ=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</
s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGAAAGAAI=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
```

```
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="3"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</m>
</a>
<a n="xfmid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJz7GHbJz5zhgv3ntRc0F2mespf88PvQp7XX7AGg8w2V
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xmax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxbaZAJz1xQ6uAaL+FYa7bBoePq1DKN3BIHAGfTCN4=
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xmin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJzTWv3cs+AfU80U3Que72uydShbvmhaha6lAwCbeAvB
</vdata>
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</m>
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<a n="ymax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBD/YMaDQAIt0Djg==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
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<a n="ymid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="ymin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMAOAAAYAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="image_title" t="s">Channels</a>
<a n="stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>rainbow</
s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5"
t="string"><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="5" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgYAQAAAYAAg==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>Nucleus</
s><s>Cell</s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="5"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMAEAAAUAEE=
</vdata>
```

```
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</a>
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Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMAEAAAUAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>Body</
s><s>Body</s><s>Body</s><s>Body</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="stencil_title" t="s">Overlays</a>
<a n="tracker" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectCellRegion.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Body</
s><s>Body</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">Body</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Nucleus@20Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Body</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Body</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="s">0</a>
<a n="cRenderSettings" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Render" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="Colormode_ColorTranslator" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Colormode"
t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Colormode</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="colormode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Images</a>
<a n="palette" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">ScaleBar</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="f">NaN</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">Stencils</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="rainbowsize" t="f">10</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
```

```
</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="CellRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">CellRegion</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">CellRegion</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString" t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectCellRegion.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Callbacks" t="i">0</a>
<a n="current_tab" t="s">CellRegionSelectCellRegion</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Inputs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="WholeCells_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select population</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Population</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SelectedPopulation" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>WholeCells</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RefString" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.FindCytoplasm.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ValidFlag" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OriginRef" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectPopulation</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>FindCytoplasm</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjY2BgAAAAHAHAH
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="Hidden" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<m n="InternalIDNumber" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="InvalidatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
```

```

<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<m n="NewPopulation" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OverTakenFrom" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectPopulation</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="MyPopulationTypes" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Objects</s></vdata>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select population of cells or nuclei by which the cell region should
be created.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Select population</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion.WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Nuclei</s><s>Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei
Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CenterRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select nucleus region, i.e. center region</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">CenterRegion</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Center Region</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedPropertyOrRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector"
t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>FindNuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>

```

```
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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<m n="order" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion.CenterRegion</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="4"><vdata k="4" t="string"><s>Nucleus</
s><s>Cell</s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="RestrictiveRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Cell</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select cell region</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">RestrictiveRegion</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Restrictive Region</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion.RestrictiveRegion</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Cell</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>Nucleus</
s><s>Cell</s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>None</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Cell</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Method" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Resize Region [%]</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a method</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
```

```
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@Resize@20@Region@20@5b@25@5d" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="UnitType"
t="s">%</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion.Method.title</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Resize Region [%]</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Resize
Region [%]</s><s>Resize Region [ $\mu\text{m}/\text{px}$ ]</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Resize
Region [%]</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="RegionType" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Cytoplasm Region</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select region type</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="display" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>Cell
Region</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Cytoplasm Region</s><s>Membrane Region</s><s>Ring Region</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">RegionType</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Region Type</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select the proper region type. If required adjust the parameters which
control the region borders.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Select Region Type</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion.Method.RegionType</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nucleus Region</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>Cell
Region</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Cytoplasm Region</s><s>Membrane Region</s><s>Ring Region</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus
Region</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="UnitType" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">%</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Unit</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
```

```
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">UnitType</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">UnitType</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="RelativeOrAbsolute" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion.Method.UnitType</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">%</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OuterBorderShift" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">55</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Outer border shift</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">OuterBorderShift</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Outer Border</a>
<a n="max" t="s">100</a>
<a n="min" t="s">-200</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@Nucleus@20Region_@25" t="s">55</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion.Method.OuterBorderShift</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s">%</a>
<a n="value" t="s">55</a>
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dimsize0="16" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJw79////xtA/AiI3wDxNyBmAAIuIBYBYjkg1gBiIyC2AWI3IA4A4iggTgFiAD9S
FYI=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">5</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="UnitType2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">%</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Unit for the inputs outer border shift and inner border shift</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">UnitType2</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Shift Unit</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
```

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</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion.Method.UnitType2</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">%</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>%</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>%</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="InnerBorderShift" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">100</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Inner border shift</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">InnerBorderShift</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Inner Border</a>
<a n="max" t="s">100</a>
<a n="min" t="s">-200</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@Nucleus@20Region_@25" t="s">100</a>
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<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
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<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion.Method.InnerBorderShift</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s">%</a>
<a n="value" t="s">100</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="11" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="11">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">5</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="RegionName" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nucleus Region</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Name of the created region</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">RegionName</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Output Region</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultNamingIsUsed" t="i">1</a>
<a n="DefaultString" t="s">Nucleus Region</a>
<a n="OriginalDefault" t="s">Nucleus Region</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>

```

```
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="UsedListCounter" t="i">1</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion.RegionName</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nucleus Region</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__initialBuildMinor" t="i">110719</a>
<a n="__initialversion" t="s">3</a>
<a n="__ProcOpenStatus" t="i">1</a>
<a n="__version" t="s">3</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OutputClass" t="s">Output Region</a>
<a n="OutputName" t="s">Nucleus Region</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SelectCellRegion_2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="BBHasBeenSaved" t="i">1</a>
<a n="bbType" t="s">builtin</a>
<a n="IDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion_2</a>
<a n="ImageView" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Replace me</a>
<a n="Tabs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="CellRegionSelectCellRegion_2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">CellRegionSelectCellRegion_2</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">The created region Ring Region. </a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Ring Region</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Properties Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.CellRegionSelectCellRegion_2</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTable0n" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Summary</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
```

```
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s">SingleDefaultOverLay</a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
<a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20class@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Cell</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Body</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Ring Region</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Body</a>
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</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Body</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Cytoplasm</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Nucleus Region</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Membrane</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@205@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@205@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20priority@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Body</a>
</m>
```

```
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@206@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20pri
riority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@206@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20priority@2c@20
style@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Body</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@207@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20pri
ority@2c@20style@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Body</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nucleus@20Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">4</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Ring@20Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">5</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">5</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Cell" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Cytoplasm" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">3</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">3</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Membrane" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">2</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">2</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__cnt_defaults" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@Ring@20Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">5</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">5</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
```

```
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Controls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="general" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Render_Colormode_Standard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TranslateColormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
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</a>
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label="TranslateColormode" title="ColorMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0"
disabled="0" /></CallbackList></m>
</a>
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<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s"></a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</
s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
```

```
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Labels_Labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ColoringMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s"></a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</
s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="palette" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
</m>
</a>
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label="ReloadFrames" title="Palette" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /></
CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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dimsize0="2" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjyIAAAAAIAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ReloadFrames" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
```

```
</CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="f">NaN</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="5" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBH/UMKOCDPZThAKE4HABJFgMv
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="5" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMAEAAAUAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="rainbowsize" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="value" t="f">10</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
```

```
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGQEAAAJAAQ=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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```
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<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Cytoplasm@20Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Body</a>
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</a>
```

```
<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Body</a>
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c="container"><a n="Colormode_ColorTranslator" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Colormode"
t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Colormode</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="colormode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Images</a>
<a n="palette" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
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<a n="ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">ScaleBar</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="f">NaN</a>
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<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">CellRegion</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">CellRegion</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString" t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectCellRegion_2.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</
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<a n="WholeCells_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select population</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Population</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SelectedPopulation" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
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<m n="ItemType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei</s></vdata>
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```

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</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select population of cells or nuclei by which the cell region should
be created.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Select population</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion_2</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion_2.WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Nuclei/<
s><s>Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
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</a>
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Selected</s></vdata>
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<a n="CenterRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select nucleus region, i.e. center region</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s"></a>
<a n="Item" t="s">CenterRegion</a>
```

```

<a n="Label" t="s">Center Region</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
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c="container"></m>
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<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedPropertyOrRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector"
t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
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<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion_2.CenterRegion</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>Nucleus</
s><s>Cell</s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region</s></vdata>
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<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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</a>
<a n="RestrictiveRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Cell</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select cell region</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>

```

```
<a n="Item" t="s">RestrictiveRegion</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Restrictive Region</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
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</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion_2</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion_2.RestrictiveRegion</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Cell</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>Nucleus</
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s></vdata>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="Method" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Resize Region [%]</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a method</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
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t="s">%</a>
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<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion_2</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion_2.Method.title</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Resize Region [%]</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Resize
Region [%]</s><s>Resize Region [ $\mu$ m/px]</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Resize
Region [%]</s></vdata>
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</a>
<a n="RegionType" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Cytoplasm Region</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select region type</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="display" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>Cell
Region</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Cytoplasm Region</s><s>Membrane Region</s><s>Ring Region</s></
vdata>
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</a>
</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">RegionType</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Region Type</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
```

```

c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select the proper region type. If required adjust the parameters which
control the region borders.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Select Region Type</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion_2</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion_2.Method.RegionType</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Ring Region</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>Cell
Region</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Cytoplasm Region</s><s>Membrane Region</s><s>Ring Region</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Ring
Region</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="UnitType" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">%</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Unit</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">UnitType</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">UnitType</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="RelativeOrAbsolute" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion_2</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion_2.Method.UnitType</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">%</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OuterBorderShift" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">25</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Outer border shift</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">OuterBorderShift</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Outer Border</a>
<a n="max" t="s">100</a>
<a n="min" t="s">-200</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@Cytoplasm@20Region_@25" t="s">5</a>
<a n="@Nucleus@20Region_@25" t="s">5</a>
<a n="@Ring@20Region_@25" t="s">35</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>

```

```
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion_2</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion_2.Method.OuterBorderShift</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s">%</a>
<a n="value" t="s">35</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="12" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="12"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjyAABzWNgisEFSttBaRMorQKLYUDFASoPpe2gtAuEbnCD0t40AKrTCM8=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">5</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="UnitType2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">%</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Unit for the inputs outer border shift and inner border shift</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">UnitType2</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Shift Unit</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion_2</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion_2.Method.UnitType2</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">%</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>%</s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>%</s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="InnerBorderShift" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">40</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Inner border shift</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">InnerBorderShift</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Inner Border</a>
<a n="max" t="s">100</a>
<a n="min" t="s">-200</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@Cytoplasm@20Region_@25" t="s">45</a>
<a n="@Nucleus@20Region_@25" t="s">45</a>
<a n="@Ring@20Region_@25" t="s">45</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion_2</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
```

```
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion_2.Method.InnerBorderShift</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s">%</a>
<a n="value" t="s">45</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="9" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="9"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYAABSwcw1eAIPd2gtDeEdgiA0AeCoPxQKD8cQjNE0gAAFYMIcw==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">5</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="RegionName" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Ring Region</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Name of the created region</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">RegionName</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Output Region</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultNamingIsUsed" t="i">1</a>
<a n="DefaultString" t="s">Ring Region</a>
<a n="OriginalDefault" t="s">Ring Region</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="UsedListCounter" t="i">1</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion_2</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion_2.RegionName</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Ring Region</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__initialBuildMinor" t="i">110719</a>
<a n="__initialVersion" t="s">3</a>
<a n="__ProcOpenStatus" t="i">1</a>
<a n="__version" t="s">3</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OutputClass" t="s">Output Region</a>
<a n="OutputName" t="s">Ring Region</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SelectCellRegion_4" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="BBHasBeenSaved" t="i">1</a>
<a n="bbType" t="s">builtin</a>
<a n="IDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion_4</a>
<a n="ImageView" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Replace me</a>
<a n="Tabs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="CellRegionSelectCellRegion_4" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">CellRegionSelectCellRegion_4</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">The created region Ring Region (2). </a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Ring Region (2)</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Properties Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.CellRegionSelectCellRegion_4</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTable0n" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Summary</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttrTypeTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s">SingleDefaultOverLay</a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
<a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20class@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Cell</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Body</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Ring Region (2)</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Body</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="flag"
t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Nucleus Region</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
```

```
c="container"><a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Cytoplasm</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Body</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2c@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Body</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Membrane</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@205@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@205@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20priority@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Body</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@206@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20pri
ority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@207@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20pri
ority@2c@20style@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Body</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nucleus@20Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">4</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Ring@20Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">5</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">5</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Ring@20Region@20@282@29" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">6</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">6</a>
</m>
</a>
```

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</m>
</a>
<a n="Cell" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Cytoplasm" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">3</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">3</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Membrane" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">2</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">2</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__cnt_defaults" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@Ring@20Region@20@282@29" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">6</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">6</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Controls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="general" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Render_Colormode_Standard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TranslateColormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
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label="TranslateColormode" title="ColorMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0"
disabled="0" /></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</
s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
```

```
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Labels_Labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ColoringMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
```

```
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="palette" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="Palette" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /></
CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="2" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="2" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYIAAAAAIAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ReloadFrames" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</
s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="f">NaN</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="5"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBH/UMK0CDPZThAKE4HABJFgMv
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="5" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMAEAAUAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
```

```
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="rainbowsize" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="value" t="f">10</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGQEAJAAQ=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</
s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGAAAGAAI=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="3"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAAAE=
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xfmid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJz7GHbJz5zhgv3ntRc0F2mespf88PvQp7XX7AGg8w2V
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xmax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxbaZAJz1xQ6uAaL+FYa7bBoePq1DKN3BIHAGfTCN4=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xmin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJzTWv3cs+AfU80U3Que72uydShbvmhaha6lAwCbeAvB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ymax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBD/YMaDQAIt0Djg==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ymid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBB/YMaDQAIP0DXg==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ymin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMA0AAAYAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="image_title" t="s">Channels</a>
<a n="stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="7"><vdata k="7" t="string"><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="7"><vdata k="7" t="string"><s>rainbow</
s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="7"><vdata k="7"
t="string"><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</
s><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="7" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="7" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYAABRgAACAAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="7"><vdata k="7" t="string"><s>Nucleus</
s><s>Cell</s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Ring Region</s><s>Ring Region
(2)</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="7" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="7"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMANAAAcAAE=
</vdata>
```

```
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="priority" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="7" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="7"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMANAAACAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="7"><vdata k="7" t="string"><s>Body</
s><s>Body</s><s>Body</s><s>Body</s><s>Body</s><s>Body</s><s>Body</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="stencil_title" t="s">Overlays</a>
<a n="tracker" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectCellRegion_4.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Body</
s><s>Body</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">Body</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Nucleus@20Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Body</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Body</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="s">0</a>
<a n="cRenderSettings" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Render" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="Colormode_ColorTranslator" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Colormode"
t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Colormode</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="colormode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Images</a>
<a n="palette" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">ScaleBar</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="f">NaN</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">Stencils</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="rainbowsize" t="f">10</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
```

```
</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="CellRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">CellRegion</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">CellRegion</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString" t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectCellRegion_4.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Callbacks" t="i">0</a>
<a n="current_tab" t="s">CellRegionSelectCellRegion_4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Inputs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="WholeCells_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select population</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Population</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SelectedPopulation" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>WholeCells</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RefString" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectCellRegion_2.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ValidFlag" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OriginRef" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectPopulation</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectCellRegion_2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJzjYGBgAAAAJAAJ
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="Hidden" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="InternalIDNumber" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="InvalidatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
```

```
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="NewPopulation" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OverTakenFrom" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectCellRegion</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="MyPopulationTypes" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Objects</s></vdata>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select population of cells or nuclei by which the cell region should
be created.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Select population</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion_4</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion_4.WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Nuclei</
s><s>Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei
Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CenterRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select nucleus region, i.e. center region</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">CenterRegion</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Center Region</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion_4</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedPropertyOrRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector"
t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>FindNuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
```

```
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="_order" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion_4.CenterRegion</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>Nucleus</
s><s>Cell</s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Ring Region</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="RestrictiveRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Cell</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select cell region</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">RestrictiveRegion</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Restrictive Region</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion_4</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion_4.RestrictiveRegion</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Cell</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="7"><vdata k="7" t="string"><s>Nucleus</
s><s>Cell</s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Ring Region</s><s>None</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Cell</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```

<a n="Method" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Resize Region [%]</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a method</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@Resize@20Region@20@5b@25@5d" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="UnitType"
t="s">%</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion_4</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion_4.Method.title</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Resize Region [%]</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Resize
Region [%]</s><s>Resize Region [ $\mu$ m/px]</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Resize
Region [%]</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="RegionType" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Cytoplasm Region</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select region type</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="display" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>Cell
Region</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Cytoplasm Region</s><s>Membrane Region</s><s>Ring Region</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">RegionType</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Region Type</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select the proper region type. If required adjust the parameters which
control the region borders.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Select Region Type</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion_4</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion_4.Method.RegionType</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Ring Region</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>Cell
Region</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Cytoplasm Region</s><s>Membrane Region</s><s>Ring Region</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Ring
Region</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>

```

```

<a n="UnitType" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">%</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Unit</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">UnitType</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">UnitType</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="RelativeOrAbsolute" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion_4</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion_4.Method.UnitType</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">%</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OuterBorderShift" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">25</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Outer border shift</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">OuterBorderShift</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Outer Border</a>
<a n="max" t="s">100</a>
<a n="min" t="s">-200</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@Nucleus@20Region_@25" t="s">55</a>
<a n="@Ring@20Region_@25" t="s">50</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion_4</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion_4.Method.OuterBorderShift</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s">%</a>
<a n="value" t="s">50</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="13" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="13"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYAABzwNgisEFSttBaRmorQKLYUDFASoPpe2gtAuU9oTQDTDazwEA6kkJXg==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">5</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="UnitType2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">%</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Unit for the inputs outer border shift and inner border shift</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">UnitType2</a>

```

```
<a n="Label" t="s">Shift Unit</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion_4</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion_4.Method.UnitType2</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">%</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>%</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>%</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="InnerBorderShift" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">40</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Inner border shift</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">InnerBorderShift</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Inner Border</a>
<a n="max" t="s">100</a>
<a n="min" t="s">-200</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@Nucleus@20Region_@25" t="s">100</a>
<a n="@Ring@20Region_@25" t="s">51</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion_4</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion_4.Method.InnerBorderShift</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s">%</a>
<a n="value" t="s">51</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="12" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="12"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACCBjchBjdwhNAN3lC+H4R2CICKB0LoA0FQ+RCofChUPgwqHw6Vj3QAAOKL
Css=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">5</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="RegionName" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Ring Region (2)</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Name of the created region</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">RegionName</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Output Region</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultNamingIsUsed" t="i">1</a>
```

```
<a n="DefaultString" t="s">Ring Region (2)</a>
<a n="OriginalDefault" t="s">Ring Region</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="UsedListCounter" t="i">2</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion_4</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion_4.RegionName</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Ring Region (2)</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__initialBuildMinor" t="i">110719</a>
<a n="__initialversion" t="s">3</a>
<a n="__ProcOpenStatus" t="i">1</a>
<a n="__version" t="s">3</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OutputClass" t="s">Output Region</a>
<a n="OutputName" t="s">Ring Region (2)</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CalculateIntensityProperties_2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="BBHasBeenSaved"
t="i">1</a>
<a n="bbType" t="s">builtin</a>
<a n="IDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_2</a>
<a n="ImageView" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Replace me</a>
<a n="Tabs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PopulationCalculateIntensityProperties_2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered"
t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">PopulationCalculateIntensityProperties_2</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Population Nuclei Selected with region Nucleus Region by which the new
properties are calculated.</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp2Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Nucleus Region</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Properties Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.PopulationCalculateIntensityProperties_2</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAAAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTable0n" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="SummaryTableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Summary</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttrTypeTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s">SingleDefaultOverLay</a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
<a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20class@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Cell</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Ring Region (2)</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="flag"
t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Nucleus Region</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Cytoplasm</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2c@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
```

c="container">0
</m>

<m n="memblock" c="container">Membrane
</m>

<m n="memblock" c="container">0
</m>

<m n="memblock" c="container">0
</m>

<m n="memblock" c="container">Border
</m>

<m n="memblock" c="container">0
</m>

<m n="memblock" c="container">Border
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<m n="memblock" c="container"><m n="memblock" c="container"><m n="memblock" c="container"><m n="memblock" c="container"><m n="memblock" c="container"><m n="memblock" c="container">NonDefault
NonDefault
4
4
</m>

</m>

Default
NonDefault
4
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</m>

</m>

Default
Default
4
4
</m>

</m>

<m n="memblock" c="container"><m n="memblock" c="container">NonDefault
NonDefault
5
5
</m>

</m>

<m n="memblock" c="container"><m n="memblock" c="container">NonDefault
NonDefault
6
6
</m>

</m>

<m n="memblock" c="container"><m n="memblock" c="container">NonDefault
NonDefault
1
1

```
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Cytoplasm" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">3</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">3</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Membrane" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">2</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">2</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__cnt_defaults" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@Nucleus@20Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverlayClass"
t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">4</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">4</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">4</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Controls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="general" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Render_Colormode_Standard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TranslateColormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="TranslateColormode" title="ColorMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0"
disabled="0" /></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</
s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
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</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAMAAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Labels_Labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
</m>
</a>
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label="ReloadFrames" title="ColoringMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList></m>
</a>
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<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</
s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="palette" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="Palette" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /></
CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
```

```
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="2" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="2" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYIAAAAAIAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
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<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ReloadFrames" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="f">NaN</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="5"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBH/UMKOCDPZThAKE4HABJFgMv
```

```
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="5" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMAEAAAUAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
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<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="rainbowsize" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="value" t="f">10</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGQEAAAJAAQ=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</
s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
```

```
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYQAAAAFAAI=
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="3"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAMAAE=
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<a n="xfmid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJy7PVGrcYHuaftFRSorrl0+b1/3IGFpG9d1ewCehAyP
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xmax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJwL/rXz0kKeJgeLeX4JMf0rHS7N4WP8zFPtAACT2grX
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xmin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJybv/XAiqPZJg7/CyPePNfwdcix7P6ePsPXAQCmawxH
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ymax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBD/YMaDQAIt0Djg==
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<a n="ymid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBB/YMaDQAIP0DXg==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ymin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMAOAAAYAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="image_title" t="s">Channels</a>
<a n="stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s>rainbow</
s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>#FF930A</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8"
t="string"><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>#FF930A</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="8" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="8" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
```

```
eJxjYGBgYAQiAAANAAM=
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s>Nucleus/
s><s>Cell</s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Ring Region</s><s>Ring Region
(2)</s><s>Highlighted Objects</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="8" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="8"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMAPAAAgAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="priority" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="8" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="8"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMANGIEYAAAkAAI=
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s>Border</
s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>solid</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="stencil_title" t="s">0overlays</a>
<a n="tracker" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.CalculateIntensityProperties_2.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="s">0</a>
<a n="cRenderSettings" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Render" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="Colormode_ColorTranslator" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Colormode"
t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Colormode</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="colormode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Images</a>
<a n="palette" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
```

```

</m>
</a>
<a n="ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">ScaleBar</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="f">NaN</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">Stencils</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="rainbowsize" t="f">10</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString"
t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.CalculateIntensityProperties_2.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SkipTab" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ButtonDef" t="s">
    set(UI_in=UI)
    set(UI=ocnt())
    UI::C_Layout(&quot;(1)&quot;;, vec(&quot;Controls&quot;)),
cellalign=&quot;center&quot;;, class=&quot;packer&quot;);
    //UI::C_Input(&quot;Keep View&quot;;,0,0,&quot;b&quot;;,description=&quot;Include the
current tab to the return result view.&quot;;,insert=&quot;controls.export&quot;);
    set(Buttons=UI)
    set(UI=UI_in)
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Callbacks" t="i">0</a>
<a n="current_tab" t="s">PopulationCalculateIntensityProperties_2</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Inputs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="channel_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Exp1Cam1</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select channel by which the intensity statistics should be calculated</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="EvalString" t="s">AAL::GetCurrentFrameImages(EvaluationData=EvaluationData)
set(Signal=FrameImages.Exp2Cam2)</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">channel_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Channel</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_2</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_2.channel_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Exp2Cam2</a>

```

```
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp2Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="WholeCells_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select population</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s"></a>
<a n="Item" t="s">WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Population</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SelectedPopulation" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>WholeCells</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RefString" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectCellRegion_4.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ValidFlag" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OriginRef" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectPopulation</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectCellRegion_4</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJzjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="Hidden" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<m n="InternalIDNumber" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="InvalidatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="NewPopulation" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OverTakenFrom" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectCellRegion_2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="MyPopulationTypes" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Objects</s></vdata>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```

<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_2</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_2.WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Nuclei/
s</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei
Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Cell</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a region which should be characterized</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Region</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Region</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_2</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedPropertyOrRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector"
t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Region</s></vdata>
</m>
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</m>
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s</vdata>
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<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nucleus Region</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="7"><vdata k="7" t="string"><s>Nucleus</
s><s>Cell</s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Ring Region</s><s>Ring Region
(2)</s></vdata>
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Region</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
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switch the individual properties ON/OFF.</a>
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<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
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<a n="Label" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
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<a n="CV_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Max_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
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<a n="Median_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Min_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
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<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_2.Method.title</a>
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<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
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s></vdata>
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<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the mean intensity</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Mean_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
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```

```

<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
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<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_2.Method.Mean_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
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<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Stddev_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Standard Deviation</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
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c="container"></m>
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<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_2</a>
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<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
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</a>
<a n="CV_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
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<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">CV_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Coefficient of Variance</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
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c="container"></m>
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<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_2.Method.CV_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>

```

```
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<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
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<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Median_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Median</a>
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<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_2.Method.More.Median_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
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<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Sum_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Sum</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_2.Method.More.Sum_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
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<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Max_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Maximum</a>
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```
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_2.Method.More.Max_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Min_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Minimum</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
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<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_2</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_2.Method.More.Min_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
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<a n="Description" t="s">Quantile fraction</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">QuantileFraction</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Quantile Fraction</a>
<a n="max" t="s">100</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
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c="container"></m>
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<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">5</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_2.Method.More.QuantileFraction</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
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<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Quantile_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Quantile</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_2.Method.More.QuantileFraction.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
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<a n="Contrast_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the contrast</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Contrast_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Contrast</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_2</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_2.Method.More.Contrast_ONOFF</
a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
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<a n="SuffixForPropertyNames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Intensity
Nucleus Region Exp2Cam2</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Common prefix for the property names</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">SuffixForPropertyNames</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Output Properties</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
```

```
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultNamingIsUsed" t="i">1</a>
<a n="DefaultString" t="s">Intensity Nucleus Region Exp2Cam2</a>
<a n="OriginalDefault" t="s">Intensity Nucleus Region Exp2Cam2</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="UsedListCounter" t="i">0</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_2.SuffixForPropertyNames</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Intensity Nucleus Region Exp2Cam2</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
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<a n="__initialversion" t="s">3</a>
<a n="__ProcOpenStatus" t="i">1</a>
<a n="__version" t="s">3</a>
</m>
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<a n="OutputName" t="s">Intensity Nucleus Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</a>
</m>
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t="i">1</a>
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<a n="PopulationCalculateIntensityProperties_3" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered"
t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">PopulationCalculateIntensityProperties_3</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Population Nuclei Selected with region Ring Region by which the new properties
are calculated.</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
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t="string"><s>Properties Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
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<a n="UIInsert" t="s">FeedBack.PopulationCalculateIntensityProperties_3</a>
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<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
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t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
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<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
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n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Ring Region (2)</a>
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<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
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</m>
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</a>
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<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
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<a n="label" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
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```

```
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t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
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ority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
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ority@2c@20style@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
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n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">4</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">4</a>
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n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Missing</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">5</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">-1</a>
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</a>
<a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">5</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">5</a>
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<a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">5</a>
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n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
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<a n="PositionOld" t="i">6</a>
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<a n="Position" t="i">1</a>
```

```
<a n="Position0ld" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="Position" t="i">3</a>
<a n="Position0ld" t="i">3</a>
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<a n="Position0ld" t="i">2</a>
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t="s">NonDefault</a>
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<a n="Position0ld" t="i">-1</a>
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<a n="OverLay0ldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">5</a>
<a n="Position0ld" t="i">5</a>
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<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLay0ldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">5</a>
<a n="Position0ld" t="i">5</a>
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c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</
s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
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<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
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<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
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```
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<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
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s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
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<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
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t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
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<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
```

```
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
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eJxjYIAAAAAIAAE=
</vdata>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
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</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
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<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
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</m>
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<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ReloadFrames" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="f">NaN</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="5"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
```

```
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</vdata>
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<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="5" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMAEAAAUAAE=
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</m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
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<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
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<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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</a>
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</a>
<a n="Render_Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="rainbowsize" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="value" t="f">10</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
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<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</
s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
```

```
</m>
</a>
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Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYQGAAAAFAAI=
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="3"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</m>
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<a n="xfmid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<a n="xmax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="xmin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJybv/XAiqPZJg7/CyPePNfwdciX7P6ePsPXAQCmawxH
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="image_title" t="s">Channels</a>
<a n="stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s>rainbow</
s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</
s></vdata>
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</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8"
t="string"><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</
s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="8" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="8" Transfer-
```

```
Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s><s>Cell</s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Ring Region</s><s>Ring Region (2)</s><s>Highlighted Objects</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="8" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="8"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="priority" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="8" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="8"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMANGIEYAAkAAI=
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>solid</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="stencil_title" t="s">Overlays</a>
<a n="tracker" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
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</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.CalculateIntensityProperties_3.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</s></vdata>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="s">0</a>
<a n="cRenderSettings" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Render" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="Colormode_ColorTranslator" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Colormode"
t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Colormode</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="colormode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Images</a>
<a n="palette" t="s">Extended</a>
```

```

<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">ScaleBar</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="f">NaN</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">Stencils</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="rainbowsize" t="f">10</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString"
t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.CalculateIntensityProperties_3.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SkipTab" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ButtonDef" t="s">
    set(UI_in=UI)
    set(UI=ocnt())
    UI::C_Layout(&quot;(1)&quot;;, vec(&quot;Controls&quot;)),
cellalign=&quot;center&quot;;, class=&quot;packer&quot;;)
    //UI::C_Input(&quot;Keep View&quot;;,0,0,&quot;b&quot;;,description=&quot;Include the
current tab to the return result view.&quot;;,insert=&quot;controls.export&quot;;)
    set(Buttons=UI)
    set(UI=UI_in)
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Callbacks" t="i">0</a>
<a n="current_tab" t="s">PopulationCalculateIntensityProperties_3</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Inputs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="channel_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Exp1Cam1</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select channel by which the intensity statistics should be calculated</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="EvalString" t="s">AAL::GetCurrentFrameImages(EvaluationData=EvaluationData)
set(Signal=FrameImages.Exp2Cam2)</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">channel_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Channel</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_3</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_3.channel_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>

```

```
<a n="value" t="s">Exp2Cam2</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp2Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</m>
</a>
<a n="WholeCells_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select population</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Population</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SelectedPopulation" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>WholeCells</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RefString" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.CalculateIntensityProperties_2.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ValidFlag" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OriginRef" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectPopulation</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>CalculateIntensityProperties_2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="Hidden" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
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</vdata>
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<m n="InternalIDNumber" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<m n="InvalidatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="NewPopulation" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OverTakenFrom" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectCellRegion_4</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="MyPopulationTypes" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Objects</s></vdata>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
```

```
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_3</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_3.WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Nuclei/
s</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei
Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Cell</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a region which should be characterized</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Region</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Region</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_3</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedPropertyOrRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector"
t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Ring Region</s></vdata>
</m>
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<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectCellRegion_2</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>8</s></vdata>
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</m>
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<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Ring Region;%</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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</m>
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```

```
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base64">
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</vdata>
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</m>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_3.Region</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Ring Region</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="7"><vdata k="7" t="string"><s>Nucleus</
s><s>Cell</s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Ring Region</s><s>Ring Region
(2)</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Ring
Region</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Method" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a method. Please note that you can enter method sub-section and
switch the individual properties ON/OFF.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Contrast_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="CV_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Max_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Mean_ONOFF" t="s">1</a>
<a n="Median_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Min_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="QuantileFraction" t="s">50</a>
<a n="Quantile_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Stddev_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Sum_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_3</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_3.Method.title</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Standard</
s></vdata>
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<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Standard</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Mean_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">1</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the mean intensity</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Mean_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Mean</a>
```

```
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_3</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_3.Method.Mean_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Stddev_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the standard deviation</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Stddev_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Standard Deviation</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_3</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_3.Method.Stddev_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CV_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the coefficient of variance</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">CV_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Coefficient of Variance</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_3</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
```

```
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_3.Method.CV_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Median_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the median intensity</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Median_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Median</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_3</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_3.Method.More.Median_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Sum_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the sum/integral intensity</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Sum_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Sum</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_3</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_3.Method.More.Sum_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Max_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the maximum intensity</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Max_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Maximum</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
```

```
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<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
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<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
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</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_3</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_3.Method.More.Max_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Min_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the minimum intensity</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Min_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Minimum</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_3</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_3.Method.More.Min_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="QuantileFraction" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">50</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Quantile fraction</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">QuantileFraction</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Quantile Fraction</a>
<a n="max" t="s">100</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_3</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">5</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_3.Method.More.QuantileFraction</a>
```

```

<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s">%</a>
<a n="value" t="s">50</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">10</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Quantile_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the quantile intensity</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Quantile_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Quantile</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_3</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_3.Method.More.QuantileFraction.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Contrast_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the contrast</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Contrast_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Contrast</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_3</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_3.Method.More.Contrast_ONOFF</
a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SuffixForPropertyNames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Intensity
Ring Region Exp2Cam2</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Common prefix for the property names</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">SuffixForPropertyNames</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Output Properties</a>

```

```
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultNamingIsUsed" t="i">1</a>
<a n="DefaultString" t="s">Intensity Ring Region Exp2Cam2</a>
<a n="OriginalDefault" t="s">Intensity Ring Region Exp2Cam2</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="UsedListCounter" t="i">0</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_3</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_3.SuffixForPropertyNames</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Intensity Ring Region Exp2Cam2</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
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<a n="__version" t="s">3</a>
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t="i">1</a>
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t="i">1</a>
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<a n="TabItemName" t="s">PopulationCalculateIntensityProperties_7</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Population Nuclei Selected with region Ring Region (2) by which the new
properties are calculated.</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
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t="string"><s>Properties Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
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```

```
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<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
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t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
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<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
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<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
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<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Ring Region (2)</a>
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<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
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```

```
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<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">4</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">4</a>
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<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">5</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">5</a>
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t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">6</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">6</a>
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</a>
<a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">6</a>
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<a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
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<a n="Position" t="i">6</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">6</a>
</m>
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```

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<a n="Position" t="i">6</a>
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<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">6</a>
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<a n="PositionOld" t="i">6</a>
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<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</
s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
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<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
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<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
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```
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></CallbackList></m>
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<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
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t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
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eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
</vdata>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
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<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
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s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
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```

```
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
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</vdata>
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<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
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<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
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<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ReloadFrames" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
```

```
<a n="value" t="f">NaN</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="5"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBH/UMKOCDPZThAKE4HABJFgMv
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="5" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMAEAAAUAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="rainbowsize" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="value" t="f">10</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGQEAJAAQ=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</
s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
```


<m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>

<m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYQAAAAFAAI=
</vdata>
1
</m>

<m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>

<m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="3"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
</vdata>
1
</m>

<m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJy7PVGrcYHuaftFRSorr10+b1/3IGFpG9d1ewCehAyP
</vdata>
1
</m>

<m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJwL/rXz0kKeJgeLeX4JMf0rHS7N4WP8zFPtAACT2grX
</vdata>
1
</m>

<m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJybv/XAiqPZJg7/CyPePNfwdciX7P6ePsPXAQCmawXH
</vdata>
1
</m>

<m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBD/YMaDQAI0Djg==
</vdata>
1
</m>

<m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBB/YMaDQAIP0DXg==
</vdata>
1
</m>

<m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMA0AAAYAAE=
</vdata>
1
</m>

</m>

Channels
<m n="memblock" c="container"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s></vdata>
</m>

<m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s>rainbow</
s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</
s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>

<m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8"
t="string"><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</
s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s></vdata>

```
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="8" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="8" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYAABRkYAAAsAAw==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s>Nucleus</
s><s>Cell</s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Ring Region</s><s>Ring Region
(2)</s><s>Highlighted Objects</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="8" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="8"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMAPAAAgAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="priority" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="8" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="8"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMANGIEYAAAKAAI=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s>Border</
s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>solid</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="stencil_title" t="s">Overlays</a>
<a n="tracker" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.CalculateIntensityProperties_7.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="s">0</a>
<a n="cRenderSettings" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Render" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="Colormode_ColorTranslator" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Colormode"
t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Colormode</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```

<a n="Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="colormode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Images</a>
<a n="palette" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">ScaleBar</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="f">NaN</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">Stencils</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="rainbowsize" t="f">10</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString"
t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.CalculateIntensityProperties_7.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SkipTab" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ButtonDef" t="s">
    set(UI_in=UI)
    set(UI=ocnt())
    UI::C_Layout(&quot;(1)&quot;;, vec(&quot;Controls&quot;)),
cellalign=&quot;center&quot;;, class=&quot;packer&quot;;)
    //UI::C_Input(&quot;Keep View&quot;;,0,0,&quot;b&quot;;,description=&quot;Include the
current tab to the return result view.&quot;;,insert=&quot;controls.export&quot;;)
    set(Buttons=UI)
    set(UI=UI_in)
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Callbacks" t="i">0</a>
<a n="current_tab" t="s">PopulationCalculateIntensityProperties_7</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Inputs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="channel_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Exp1Cam1</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select channel by which the intensity statistics should be calculated</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="EvalString" t="s">AAL::GetCurrentFrameImages(EvaluationData=EvaluationData)
set(Signal=FrameImages.Exp2Cam2)</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">channel_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Channel</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_7</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>

```

```
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_7.channel_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Exp2Cam2</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
<s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp2Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="WholeCells_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select population</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Population</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SelectedPopulation" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>WholeCells</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RefString" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.CalculateIntensityProperties_3.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ValidFlag" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OriginRef" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectPopulation</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>CalculateIntensityProperties_3</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJzjZmBgAAAAMAAM
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="Hidden" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="InternalIDNumber" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="InvalidatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="NewPopulation" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OverTakenFrom" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>CalculateIntensityProperties_2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="MyPopulationTypes" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Objects</s></vdata>
```

```
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_7</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_7.WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Nuclei</s><s>Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Cell</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a region which should be characterized</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Region</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Region</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_7</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedPropertyOrRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Ring Region (2)</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>_Region7</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Ring Region (2)</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectCellRegion_4</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>9</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Ring Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Ring Region (2)</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Ring Region;%</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
```

```
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="_order" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjY2BgAAAAHAAH
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_7.Region</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Ring Region (2)</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="7"><vdata k="7" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s><s>Cell</s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Ring Region</s><s>Ring Region (2)</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Ring Region (2)</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Method" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a method. Please note that you can enter method sub-section and switch the individual properties ON/OFF.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s"></a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Contrast_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="CV_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Max_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Mean_ONOFF" t="s">1</a>
<a n="Median_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Min_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="QuantileFraction" t="s">50</a>
<a n="Quantile_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Stddev_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Sum_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_7</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_7.Method.title</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Standard</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Mean_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">1</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the mean intensity</a>
```

```

<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Mean_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_7</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_7.Method.Mean_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Stddev_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the standard deviation</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Stddev_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Standard Deviation</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_7</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_7.Method.Stddev_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CV_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the coefficient of variance</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">CV_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Coefficient of Variance</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>

```

```

<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_7</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_7.Method.CV_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Median_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the median intensity</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Median_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Median</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_7</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_7.Method.More.Median_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Sum_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the sum/integral intensity</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Sum_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Sum</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_7</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_7.Method.More.Sum_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Max_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the maximum intensity</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>

```

```
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Max_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Maximum</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_7</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_7.Method.More.Max_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Min_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the minimum intensity</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Min_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Minimum</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_7</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_7.Method.More.Min_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="QuantileFraction" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">50</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Quantile fraction</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">QuantileFraction</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Quantile Fraction</a>
<a n="max" t="s">100</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_7</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
```

```

<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">5</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_7.Method.More.QuantileFraction</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s">%</a>
<a n="value" t="s">50</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">10</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Quantile_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the quantile intensity</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Quantile_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Quantile</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_7</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_7.Method.More.QuantileFraction.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Contrast_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the contrast</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Contrast_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Contrast</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_7</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_7.Method.More.Contrast_ONOFF</
a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SuffixForPropertyNames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Intensity
Ring Region (2) Exp2Cam2</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Common prefix for the property names</a>

```

```
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">SuffixForPropertyNames</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Output Properties</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultNamingIsUsed" t="i">1</a>
<a n="DefaultString" t="s">Intensity Ring Region (2) Exp2Cam2</a>
<a n="OriginalDefault" t="s">Intensity Ring Region (2) Exp2Cam2</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="UsedListCounter" t="i">0</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_7</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_7.SuffixForPropertyNames</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Intensity Nucleoplasm</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__initialBuildMinor" t="i">110719</a>
<a n="__initialversion" t="s">3</a>
<a n="__ProcOpenStatus" t="i">1</a>
<a n="__version" t="s">3</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OutputClass" t="s">Output Property</a>
<a n="OutputName" t="s">Intensity Nucleoplasm Mean</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CalculateProperties" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="BBHasBeenSaved" t="i">1</a>
<a n="bbType" t="s">builtin</a>
<a n="IDName" t="s">CalculateProperties</a>
<a n="ImageView" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Replace me</a>
<a n="Tabs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PopulationCalculateProperties" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</
a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">PopulationCalculateProperties</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Population: Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Cell</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Properties Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.PopulationCalculateProperties</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="SummaryTable0n" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Summary</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttrTypeTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s">SingleDefault0verLay</a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
<a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20class@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Cell</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Ring Region (2)</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="flag"
t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Nucleus Region</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Cytoplasm</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2c@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
```

```
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Membrane</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@205@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@205@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20priority@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@206@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20pri
ority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@207@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20pri
ority@2c@20style@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nucleus@20Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">4</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Ring@20Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">5</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">5</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Ring@20Region@20@282@29" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">6</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">6</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Cell" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Cytoplasm" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">3</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">3</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
```

```
</a>
<a n="Membrane" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">2</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">2</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__cnt_defaults" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="Cell" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Controls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="general" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Render_Colormode_Standard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TranslateColormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="TranslateColormode" title="ColorMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0"
disabled="0" /></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s"></a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</
s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
```

```
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Labels_Labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ColoringMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</
s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize=3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAMAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
```

```
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="palette" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="Palette" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /></
CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="2" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsz0="2" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYIAAAAIAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ReloadFrames" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</
s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="f">NaN</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="5"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBH/UMK0CDPZThAKE4HABJFgMv
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="5" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMAEAAAUAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
```

```
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="rainbowsize" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="value" t="f">10</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGQEAJAAQ=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</
s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGAAAGAAI=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="3"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xfmid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJy7PVGrcYHuaftFRSorr10+b1/3IGFpG9d1ewCehAyP
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xmax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJwL/rXz0kKeJgeLeX4JMf0rHS7N4WP8zFPtAACT2grX
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
```



```

<a n="tracker" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.CalculateProperties.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="s">0</a>
<a n="cRenderSettings" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Render" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="Colormode_ColorTranslator" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Colormode"
t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Colormode</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="colormode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Images</a>
<a n="palette" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">ScaleBar</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="f">NaN</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">Stencils</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="rainbowsize" t="f">10</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Population" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Population</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">Population</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString"
t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.CalculateProperties.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SkipTab" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ButtonDef" t="s">
    set(UI_in=UI)

```

```

        set(UI=ocnt())
        UI::C_Layout(&quot;(1)&quot;;, vec(&quot;Controls&quot;),
cellalign=&quot;center&quot;;, class=&quot;packer&quot;);
//UI::C_Input(&quot;Keep View&quot;;,0,0,&quot;b&quot;;,description=&quot;Include the
current tab to the return result view.&quot;;,insert=&quot;controls.export&quot;);
        set(Buttons=UI)
        set(UI=UI_in)
    </a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Callbacks" t="i">0</a>
<a n="current_tab" t="s">PopulationCalculateProperties</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Inputs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="WholeCells_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select population, for which a custom defined property should be
calculated.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Population</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SelectedPopulation" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>WholeCells</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RefString" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.CalculateIntensityProperties_7.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ValidFlag" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OriginRef" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectPopulation</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>CalculateIntensityProperties_7</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJzjYWBgAAAANAAN
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="Hidden" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="InternalIDNumber" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="InvalidatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>

```

```
<m n="NewPopulation" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OverTakenFrom" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>CalculateIntensityProperties_3</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="MyPopulationTypes" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Objects</s></vdata>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateProperties</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateProperties.WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Nuclei</
s><s>Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei
Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Method" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">By Formula</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a method</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s"></a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@By@20Formula" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PropertyName"
t="s">Formula</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateProperties</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateProperties.Method.title</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">By Formula</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>By
Formula</s><s>By Related Population</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>By
Formula</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Formula" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">a/b</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate a new property with formula in style 100*(A-B)/C and thereupon
specify below the corresponding variables A, B etc. Please use only single characters (A, B, ..,Y).</
a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
```

```

<a n="EvalString"
t="s">set(FoundLetters=EvaluationData.Procedures[ProcedureIDName].Inputs.Formula.private.FoundLetters
)</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Formula</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Formula</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="FoundLetters" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>A</s><s>B</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateProperties</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateProperties.Method.Formula</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">a/b</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="VariableA" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nucleus Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a property to which the variable A should correspond to</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="EvalString" t="s">AAL::GetSelectedRegion(SelectedLabel=VariableA, RegionTable=ScalarTable|
ScalarTable_A=TableForSelectedRegion, SelectedScalarRowIndex_A=SelectedRegionRowIndex)</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">VariableA</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Variable A</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateProperties</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Intensity Nucleus Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Scalar</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>_Scalar7</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>CalculateIntensityProperties_2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>10</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Intensity Nucleus Region
Exp2Cam2 Mean</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean intensity of Nucleus
Region by channel Exp2Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus Region;%</
s></vdata>
</m>

```

```
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean Intensity</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Exp2Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Counts/Pixel</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean Intensity</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean intensity of Nucleus Region by
channel Exp2Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="order" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjZWBgAAAAGAAG
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateProperties.Method.VariableA</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Intensity Nucleus Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s>Nucleus
Area [µm²]</s><s>Nucleus Roundness</s><s>Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Intensity Nucleus
Exp1Cam1 Mean</s><s>Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</s><s>Intensity Nucleus Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</
s><s>Intensity Ring Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>Intensity Nucleoplasm Mean</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Intensity Nucleus Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="VariableB" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nucleus Roundness</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a property to which the variable B should correspond to</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="EvalString" t="s">AAL::GetSelectedRegion(SelectedLabel=VariableB, RegionTable=ScalarTable|
ScalarTable_B=TableForSelectedRegion, SelectedScalarRowIndex_B=SelectedRegionRowIndex)</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">VariableB</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Variable B</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateProperties</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Intensity Ring Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s></vdata>
</m>
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</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>_Scalar8</s></vdata>
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<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Ring Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>CalculateIntensityProperties_3</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>11</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
```

```
</m>
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Exp2Cam2 Mean</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean intensity of Ring
Region by channel Exp2Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Ring Region;%</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean Intensity</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Exp2Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
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<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Counts/Pixel</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean Intensity</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean intensity of Ring Region by
channel Exp2Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="_order" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
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</vdata>
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</m>
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</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateProperties.Method.VariableB</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Intensity Ring Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s>Nucleus
Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]/</s><s>Nucleus Roundness</s><s>Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Intensity Nucleus
Exp1Cam1 Mean</s><s>Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</s><s>Intensity Nucleus Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</
s><s>Intensity Ring Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>Intensity Nucleoplasm Mean</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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t="string"><s>Intensity Ring Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s></vdata>
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</m>
</a>
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<a n="Description" t="s">Name of the calculated property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">PropertyName</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Output Property</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateProperties</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateProperties.PropertyName</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
```

```
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Formula</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
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<a n="__initialversion" t="s">3</a>
<a n="__ProcOpenStatus" t="i">1</a>
<a n="__version" t="s">3</a>
</m>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="OutputClass" t="s">Output Property</a>
<a n="OutputName" t="s">Formula</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CalculateProperties_2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="BBHasBeenSaved" t="i">1</a>
<a n="bbType" t="s">builtin</a>
<a n="IDName" t="s">CalculateProperties_2</a>
<a n="ImageView" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Replace me</a>
<a n="Tabs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PopulationCalculateProperties_2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered"
t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">PopulationCalculateProperties_2</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Population: Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Cell</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Properties Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.PopulationCalculateProperties_2</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
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</vdata>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTable0n" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Summary</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttrTypeTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s">SingleDefaultOverLay</a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
<a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
```

```
</m>
</a>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Cell</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
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</a>
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n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Ring Region (2)</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
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t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Nucleus Region</a>
</m>
</a>
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n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Cytoplasm</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2c@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
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n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Membrane</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@205@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="open" t="i">0</a>
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n="@Container@3a@205@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20priority@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
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ority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
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ority@2c@20style@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
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<a n="@Nucleus@20Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">4</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">4</a>
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c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">5</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">5</a>
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n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">6</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">6</a>
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<a n="Cell" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">1</a>
</m>
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<a n="Cytoplasm" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">3</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">3</a>
</m>
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</m>
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<a n="Membrane" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">2</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">2</a>
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</m>
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<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__cnt_defaults" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="Cell" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">1</a>
</m>
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```

```
</m>
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</m>
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<a n="Controls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="general" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Render_Colormode_Standard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TranslateColormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
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</m>
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label="TranslateColormode" title="ColorMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0"
disabled="0" /></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</
s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
</m>
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<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
</vdata>
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</m>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
```

```
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
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<a n="Render_Labels_Labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
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<a n="Render_Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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label="ReloadFrames" title="ColoringMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</
s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
</m>
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t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
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<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
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<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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c="container"></m>
</a>
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```

```
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<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
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s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
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s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
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<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
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</m>
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<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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</m>
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<a n="Render_Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="rainbowsize" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="value" t="f">10</a>
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<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
```

```
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</m>
</a>
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s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
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</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
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<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
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<a n="xmax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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```
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t="string" k="7"><vdata k="7" t="string"><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="7"><vdata k="7" t="string"><s>rainbow</
s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
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s><s>Cell</s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Ring Region</s><s>Ring Region
(2)</s></vdata>
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<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="7"><vdata k="7" t="string"><s>Border</
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<a n="stencil_title" t="s">Overlays</a>
<a n="tracker" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
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<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
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c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
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</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</
s></vdata>
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<a n="@sticky:1003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
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<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
```

```
</a>
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<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
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c="container"><a n="Colormode_ColorTranslator" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Colormode"
t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Colormode</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
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<a n="methodclass" t="s">Images</a>
<a n="palette" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">ScaleBar</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="f">NaN</a>
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<a n="Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">Stencils</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="rainbowsize" t="f">10</a>
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<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Population" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Population</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">Population</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString"
t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.CalculateProperties_2.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</a>
</m>
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a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
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<a n="current_tab" t="s">PopulationCalculateProperties_2</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Inputs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="WholeCells_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select population, for which a custom defined property should be
calculated.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Population</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SelectedPopulation" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>WholeCells</s></vdata>
</m>
```

```
<m n="ItemType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RefString" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.CalculateProperties.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ValidFlag" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
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</vdata>
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</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>CalculateProperties</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
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base64">
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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<m n="NewPopulation" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<m n="OverTakenFrom" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>CalculateIntensityProperties_7</s></vdata>
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<m n="MyPopulationTypes" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Objects</s></vdata>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
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<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateProperties_2</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateProperties_2.WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Nuclei</
s><s>Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei
Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Method" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">By Formula</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a method</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
```

```

<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@By@20Formula" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PropertyName"
t="s">Formula (2)</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateProperties_2</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateProperties_2.Method.title</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">By Formula</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>By
Formula</s><s>By Related Population</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>By
Formula</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Formula" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">a/b</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate a new property with formula in style  $100*(A-B)/C$  and thereupon
specify below the corresponding variables A, B etc. Please use only single characters (A, B, ..,Y).</
a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="EvalString"
t="s">set(FoundLetters=EvaluationData.Procedures[ProcedureIDName].Inputs.Formula.private.FoundLetters
)</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Formula</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Formula</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="FoundLetters" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>A</s><s>B</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateProperties_2</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateProperties_2.Method.Formula</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">a/b</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="VariableA" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nucleus Area [ $\mu\text{m}\leq$ ]</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a property to which the variable A should correspond to</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="EvalString" t="s">AAL::GetSelectedRegion(SelectedLabel=VariableA, RegionTable=ScalarTable|
ScalarTable_A=TableForSelectedRegion, SelectedScalarRowIndex_A=SelectedRegionRowIndex)</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>

```

```
<a n="InputType" t="s"></a>
<a n="Item" t="s">VariableA</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Variable A</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateProperties_2</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Intensity Ring Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Scalar</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>_Scalar8</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Ring Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>CalculateIntensityProperties_3</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>11</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Intensity Ring Region
Exp2Cam2 Mean</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean intensity of Ring
Region by channel Exp2Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Ring Region;%</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean Intensity</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Exp2Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Counts/Pixel</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean Intensity</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean intensity of Ring Region by
channel Exp2Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="__order" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjY2BgAAAHAHAH
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateProperties_2.Method.VariableA</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Intensity Ring Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="9"><vdata k="9" t="string"><s>Nucleus
Area [µm<sup>2</sup>]</s><s>Nucleus Roundness</s><s>Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Intensity Nucleus
Exp1Cam1 Mean</s><s>Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</s><s>Intensity Nucleus Exp2Cam2 Mean</
s><s>Intensity Ring Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>Intensity Nucleoplasm Mean</s><s>Formula</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Intensity Ring Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s></vdata>
```

```

</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="VariableB" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nucleus Roundness</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a property to which the variable B should correspond to</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="EvalString" t="s">AAL::GetSelectedRegion(SelectedLabel=VariableB, RegionTable=ScalarTable|
ScalarTable_B=TableForSelectedRegion, SelectedScalarRowIndex_B=SelectedRegionRowIndex)</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">VariableB</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Variable B</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateProperties_2</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Scalar</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>_Scalar4</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>CalculateIntensityProperties</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>4</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Intensity Nucleus
Exp1Cam1 Mean</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean intensity of Nucleus by
channel Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean Intensity</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Counts/Pixel</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean Intensity</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean intensity of Nucleus by channel
Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="__order" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjZmBgAAAAEAAE
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateProperties_2.Method.VariableB</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>

```

```
<a n="value" t="s">Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="9"><vdata k="9" t="string"><s>Nucleus
Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]/</s><s>Nucleus Roundness</s><s>Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Intensity Nucleus
Exp1Cam1 Mean</s><s>Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</s><s>Intensity Nucleus Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</
s><s>Intensity Ring Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>Intensity Nucleoplasm Mean</s><s>Formula</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="PropertyName" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Formula</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Name of the calculated property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">PropertyName</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Output Property</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateProperties_2</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateProperties_2.PropertyName</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Formula (2)</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__initialBuildMinor" t="i">110719</a>
<a n="__initialversion" t="s">3</a>
<a n="__ProcOpenStatus" t="i">1</a>
<a n="__version" t="s">3</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OutputClass" t="s">Output Property</a>
<a n="OutputName" t="s">Formula (2)</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SelectCellRegion_3" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="BBHasBeenSaved" t="i">1</a>
<a n="bbType" t="s">builtin</a>
<a n="IDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion_3</a>
<a n="ImageView" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Replace me</a>
<a n="Tabs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="CellRegionSelectCellRegion_3" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">CellRegionSelectCellRegion_3</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">The created region Nucleus Region2. </a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Nucleus Region2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Properties Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
```

```
</m>
</a>
<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.CellRegionSelectCellRegion_3</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTable0n" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Summary</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttrTypeTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s">SingleDefaultOverLay</a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
<a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20class@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Cell</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Body</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Ring Region (2)</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Body</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="flag"
t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Nucleus Region</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label"
t="s">Nucleus Region2</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Cytoplasm</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Body</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20label@2c@20open@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Body</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2c@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Body</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Membrane</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@205@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@205@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20priority@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Body</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@206@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20pri
ority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@207@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20pri
ority@2c@20style@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Body</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nucleus@20Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">4</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nucleus@20Region2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">7</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">7</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Ring@20Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">5</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">5</a>
```

```
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Ring@20Region@20@282@29" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">6</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">6</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Cell" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Cytoplasm" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">3</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">3</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Membrane" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">2</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">2</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__cnt_defaults" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@Nucleus@20Region2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">7</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">7</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Controls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="general" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Render_Colormode_Standard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TranslateColormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
```

```
label="TranslateColormode" title="ColorMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0"
disabled="0" /></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Labels_Labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
```

```
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ColoringMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</
s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="palette" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="Palette" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /></
CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
```

```
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="2" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="2" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYIAAAAAIAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ReloadFrames" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="f">NaN</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="5"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBH/UMK0CDPZThAKE4HABJFgMv
</vdata>
```

```
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="5" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMAEAAAUAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="rainbowsize" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="value" t="f">10</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGQEAJAAQ=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</
s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGAAAAAGAAI=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="3"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xfmid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJzTUhApqQo6ac+3uUNccNlFewYweGAPAFxZBu0=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xmax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJwzEXZaZ09a5TCBUXICY2SbAwMYRDoAAE6MBV0=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xmin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJyrnLl303eEts0/Z/lA50LAAAUai+EIfw==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ymax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBD/YMaDQAIt0Djg==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
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</vdata>
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</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="image_title" t="s">Channels</a>
<a n="stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s></vdata>
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</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s>rainbow</
s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</
s></vdata>
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</a>
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</a>
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Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYAADRgAACQAC
```

```
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s><s>Cell</s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Ring Region
(2)</s><s>Nucleus Region2</s></vdata>
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Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</m>
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t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
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<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectCellRegion_3.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
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c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Body</
s><s>Body</s></vdata>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">Body</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Nucleus@20Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Body</a>
</m>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Body</a>
</m>
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</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="s">0</a>
<a n="cRenderSettings" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Render" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="Colormode_ColorTranslator" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Colormode"
t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Colormode</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
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<a n="Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="colormode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Images</a>
<a n="palette" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">ScaleBar</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="f">NaN</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">Stencils</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="rainbowsize" t="f">10</a>
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</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="CellRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">CellRegion</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">CellRegion</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString" t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectCellRegion_3.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</a>
</m>
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</m>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Callbacks" t="i">0</a>
<a n="current_tab" t="s">CellRegionSelectCellRegion_3</a>
</m>
</a>
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<a n="Inputs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="WholeCells_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select population</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Population</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SelectedPopulation" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>WholeCells</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RefString" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.CalculateProperties_2.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ValidFlag" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OriginRef" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectPopulation</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>CalculateProperties_2</s></vdata>
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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<m n="Hidden" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
```

```
base64">
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<m n="InternalIDNumber" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
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<m n="OverTakenFrom" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>CalculateProperties</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="MyPopulationTypes" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Objects</s></vdata>
</m>
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</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select population of cells or nuclei by which the cell region should
be created.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Select population</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion_3</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion_3.WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Nuclei/
s</s><s>Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei
Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CenterRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select nucleus region, i.e. center region</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">CenterRegion</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Center Region</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion_3</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedPropertyOrRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector"
t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
```

```
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<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>FindNuclei</s></vdata>
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<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>2</s></vdata>
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<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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<m n="_order" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
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</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">4</a>
</m>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion_3.CenterRegion</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="7"><vdata k="7" t="string"><s>Nucleus</
s><s>Cell</s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Ring Region</s><s>Ring Region
(2)</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="RestrictiveRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Cell</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select cell region</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">RestrictiveRegion</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Restrictive Region</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion_3</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion_3.RestrictiveRegion</a>
```

```

<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Cell</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s><s>Cell</s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Ring Region</s><s>Ring Region (2)</s><s>None</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Cell</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Method" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Resize Region [%]</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a method</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Resize@20Region@20@5b@25@5d" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="UnitType" t="s">%</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion_3</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion_3.Method.title</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Resize Region [%]</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Resize Region [%]</s><s>Resize Region [ $\mu$ m/px]</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Resize Region [%]</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="RegionType" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Cytoplasm Region</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select region type</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="display" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>Cell Region</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Cytoplasm Region</s><s>Membrane Region</s><s>Ring Region</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">RegionType</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Region Type</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select the proper region type. If required adjust the parameters which control the region borders.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Select Region Type</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion_3</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion_3.Method.RegionType</a>

```

```

<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nucleus Region</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>Cell
Region</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Cytoplasm Region</s><s>Membrane Region</s><s>Ring Region</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus
Region</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="UnitType" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">%</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Unit</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">UnitType</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">UnitType</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="RelativeOrAbsolute" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion_3</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion_3.Method.UnitType</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">%</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OuterBorderShift" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">55</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Outer border shift</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">OuterBorderShift</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Outer Border</a>
<a n="max" t="s">100</a>
<a n="min" t="s">-200</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@Nucleus@20Region_@25" t="s">52</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion_3</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion_3.Method.OuterBorderShift</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s">%</a>
<a n="value" t="s">52</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="16" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="16" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJw799///xtA/AiI3wDxNyBmAiIuIBYBYjkg1gBiIyC2AWI3IA4A4iggTgFiAD9S
FYI=

```

```
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">5</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="UnitType2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">%</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Unit for the inputs outer border shift and inner border shift</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">UnitType2</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Shift Unit</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion_3</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion_3.Method.UnitType2</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">%</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>%</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>%</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="InnerBorderShift" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">100</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Inner border shift</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">InnerBorderShift</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Inner Border</a>
<a n="max" t="s">100</a>
<a n="min" t="s">-200</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@Nucleus@20Region_@25" t="s">100</a>
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</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion_3</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion_3.Method.InnerBorderShift</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s">%</a>
<a n="value" t="s">100</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="12" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="12"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACcBncHBjDwgtANPlC+P4Q+EADlB0Foh2CohCofChUPhwqHwHlRzoAAOK7
CLM=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">5</a>
</m>
```

```
</a>
<a n="RegionName" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nucleus Region (2)</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Name of the created region</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">RegionName</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Output Region</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultNamingIsUsed" t="i">1</a>
<a n="DefaultString" t="s">Nucleus Region (2)</a>
<a n="OriginalDefault" t="s">Nucleus Region</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="UsedListCounter" t="i">2</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectCellRegion_3</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectCellRegion_3.RegionName</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nucleus Region2</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__initialBuildMinor" t="i">110719</a>
<a n="__initialversion" t="s">3</a>
<a n="__ProcOpenStatus" t="i">1</a>
<a n="__version" t="s">3</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OutputClass" t="s">Output Region</a>
<a n="OutputName" t="s">Nucleus Region2</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="FindSpots" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="BBHasBeenSaved" t="i">1</a>
<a n="bbType" t="s">builtin</a>
<a n="IDName" t="s">FindSpots</a>
<a n="ImageView" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Replace me</a>
<a n="Tabs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SpotsFindSpots" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Spots</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">SpotsFindSpots</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Detected Spots</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp2Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Properties Spots</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.SpotsFindSpots</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
```

```
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTable0n" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Summary</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttrTypeTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s">SingleDefaultOverLay</a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20class@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Spot</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Spot" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__cnt_defaults" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="Spot" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Controls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="general" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Render_Colormode_Standard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TranslateColormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
```

```
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="TranslateColormode" title="ColorMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0"
disabled="0" /></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</
s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Labels_Labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
```

```
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ColoringMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s"></a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</
s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="palette" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="Palette" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /></
CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s"></a>
```

```
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="2" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="2" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYIAAAAAIAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
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<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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</a>
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</a>
<a n="Render_ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
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</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ReloadFrames" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
</m>
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```

```
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<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="f">NaN</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="5"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBH/UMKOCDPZThAKE4HABJFgMv
</vdata>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="5" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
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</m>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
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<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
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</a>
<a n="Render_Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="rainbowsize" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="value" t="f">10</a>
</m>
</a>
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<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGQEAAAJAAQ=
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
```

```
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</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGQAAAAFAAI=
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</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
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<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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</a>
<a n="xfmid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxz5Ny4ZM7vU/Yau9T45bads2cAgwf2AH7mCIk=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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</a>
<a n="xmax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxLjg7ZKB7U4DC1bqvD0q09DgxgE0kAAHicCAM=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<a n="xmin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJyzV3/5Sjhn3yFBN+BluleLAWMUAAB19AYD
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<a n="ymax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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</a>
<a n="ymid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBB/YMaDQAI0DXg==
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="image_title" t="s">Channels</a>
<a n="stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
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```

```
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
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<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="priority" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>border</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="stencil_title" t="s">0overlays</a>
<a n="tracker" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.FindSpots.Outputs.Spots.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="cIViewRelatedPopulationData" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="TabName"
t="s">PopulationFindSpots</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>border</
s><s>Border</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">border</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Spot" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
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<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
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</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="s">0</a>
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```
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c="container"><a n="Colormode_ColorTranslator" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Colormode"
t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Colormode</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
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<a n="Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="colormode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Images</a>
<a n="palette" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
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<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="f">NaN</a>
</m>
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<a n="Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">Stencils</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="rainbowsize" t="f">10</a>
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</a>
</m>
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</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Spots" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Spots</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">Spots</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString" t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.FindSpots.Outputs.Spots.dataitem</a>
</m>
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</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</
a>
</m>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="spotmethodwizardFindSpots" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Spots</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">spotmethodwizardFindSpots</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Detected Spots</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp2Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Properties Spots</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.spotmethodwizardFindSpots</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="SummaryTable0n" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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```
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t="string"><s>Summary</s></vdata>
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</a>
<a n="AttrTypeTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s">SingleDefaultOverLay</a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Spot</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Spot" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</a>
<a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
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</a>
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c="container"><a n="Spot" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
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</a>
</a>
<a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
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</a>
</m>
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<a n="Controls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Images" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGQEAAAJAAQ=
</vdata>
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</m>
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<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</
s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
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</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGQAAAAFAAI=
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</
```

```
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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</a>
<a n="stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjBAAAAGAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
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<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.FindSpots.Outputs.spotmethodwizard.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Spot" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
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<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="i">0</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="spotmethodwizard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">spotmethodwizard</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">spotmethodwizard</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString" t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.FindSpots.Outputs.spotmethodwizard.dataitem</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="PopulationFindSpots" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">PopulationFindSpots</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Region where spots are searched and detected spots.</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
```

```
t="string"><s>Exp2Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2"
t="string"><s>Nucleus Region2</s><s>Spot Borders</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Properties Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.PopulationFindSpots</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTable0n" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Summary</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttrTypeTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s">SingleDefault0verLay</a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
<a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20class@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Cell</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Ring Region (2)</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="flag"
t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Spot Borders</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label"
```

```
t="s">Spots</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
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t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Cytoplasm</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20label@2c@20open@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20open@2c@20priority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2c@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20label@2c@20open@2c@20priority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Membrane</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@205@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@205@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20priority@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@206@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20pri
ority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
```

```
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@207@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20pri
riority@2c@20style@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nucleus@20Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">4</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nucleus@20Region2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass"
t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Missing</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">6</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">-1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">6</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">6</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">7</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">7</a>
</m>
</a>
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</a>
<a n="@Ring@20Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">5</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">5</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Ring@20Region@20@282@29" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">6</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">6</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spot@20Borders" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">7</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">7</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">7</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">7</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
```

```
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">9</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">9</a>
</m>
</a>
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</a>
<a n="Cell" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Cytoplasm" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">3</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">3</a>
</m>
</a>
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</a>
<a n="Membrane" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">2</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">2</a>
</m>
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<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
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</a>
<a n="Spots" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">8</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">8</a>
</m>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__cnt_defaults" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@Nucleus@20Region2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass"
t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Missing</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">6</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">-1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">6</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">6</a>
</m>
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</m>
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<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">7</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">7</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
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```

```
<a n="@Spot@2@Borders" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">7</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">7</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">7</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">7</a>
</m>
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</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">9</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">9</a>
</m>
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</a>
<a n="Controls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="general" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Render_Colormode_Standard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TranslateColormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="TranslateColormode" title="ColorMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0"
disabled="0" /></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</
s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
```

```
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Labels_Labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ColoringMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</
s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
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t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
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```

```
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<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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</a>
</m>
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c="container"></m>
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label="ReloadFrames" title="Palette" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /></
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<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
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s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
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<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
```

```
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<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</
s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
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<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="5"
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<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="signed int" rank="1"
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<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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</m>
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<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
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<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</
s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
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<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
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<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
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</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="3"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="xfmid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxz5Ny4ZM7vU/Yau9T45bads2cAgwf2AH7mCIk=
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Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxLjg7Zk87U4DC1bqvD0q09DgXgE0kAAHicCAM=
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</m>
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<a n="xmin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJyzV3/5SjhN3yFBN+BluleLAWMUAAAB19AYD
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```



```
</m>
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<a n="Spots" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="TabName" t="s">SpotsFindSpots</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
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s><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
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</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="4"><vdata k="4" t="string"><s>border</
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<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">border</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
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<a n="@Spot@20Borders" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
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<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
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</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString" t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.FindSpots.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</
a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="imCorrectedImageFindSpots" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Background Correction</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">imCorrectedImageFindSpots</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Background corrected image</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Background Corrected Image</s></vdata>
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<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="0" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="0" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="0" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="0"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
```

```
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<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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t="string"><s>Summary</s></vdata>
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<a n="AttrTypeTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
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</m>
</a>
<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s"></a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="Controls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Images" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjBAAAAGAC
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<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Gray</s></
vdata>
</m>
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<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Background
Corrected Image</s></vdata>
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<a n="stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
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Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">

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<a n="style" t="s">border</a>
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```

```
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dimsize0="0" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">

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<a n="Image_title" t="s">Background corrected image</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="i">0</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="imCorrectedImage" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">imCorrectedImage</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">imCorrectedImage</a>
<a n="Images_RefString"
t="s">set(Images=EvaluationData.Procedures.FindSpots.Outputs.imCorrectedImage.dataitem)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">set(Stencils=Vec())</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
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a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Callbacks" t="i">0</a>
<a n="current_tab" t="s">SpotsFindSpots</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Inputs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="channel_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Exp1Cam1</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select channel for spot detection</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="EvalString" t="s">set(signal=FrameImages[q(channel_string)])</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">channel_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Channel</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select channel by which the spot-like features should be detected.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Channel selection</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots.channel_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Exp2Cam2</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp2Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="WholeCells_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a population with the region where the spot-like features should be
searched and detected</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
```

```
<a n="Item" t="s">WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Population</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SelectedPopulation" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>WholeCells</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RefString" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectCellRegion_3.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ValidFlag" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OriginRef" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectPopulation</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectCellRegion_3</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="Hidden" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<m n="InternalIDNumber" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<m n="NewPopulation" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
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</m>
<m n="OverTakenFrom" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>CalculateProperties_2</
s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="MyPopulationTypes" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Objects</s></vdata>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select a population with the region where the spot-like features
should be searched and detected.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Select population</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots.WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
```

```
<a n="value" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Nuclei/
s</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei
Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Cell</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select region where the spot-like features should be searched and detected</
a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Region</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Region</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select region where the spot-like features should be searched and
detected.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Select Region</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedPropertyOrRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector"
t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus Region2</s></vdata>
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<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>_Region8</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus Region2</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectCellRegion_3</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>15</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus Region2</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus Region;%</
s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
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<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="_order" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjZ2BgAAAAIAAI
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
```

```
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots.Region</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nucleus Region2</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s><s>Cell</s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Ring Region</s><s>Ring Region (2)</s><s>Nucleus Region2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus Region2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Method" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">A</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a method for detecting or characterizing spot-like features</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Iview_Wizard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>spotmethodwizardFindSpots</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="A" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="dBackGroundCorrection" t="s">0.5</a>
<a n="DetectionSensitivity" t="s">0.5</a>
<a n="MinRelativeSignal" t="s">0.035</a>
<a n="SplittingCoefficient" t="s">1</a>
<a n="SplittingSensitivity" t="s">0.5</a>
<a n="SpotMaximumRadius" t="s">50</a>
<a n="SpotMaximumRadius__MyUnit" t="s">px</a>
<a n="SpotMinimumContrast" t="s">0</a>
<a n="SpotMinimumDistance" t="s">2</a>
<a n="SpotMinimumDistance__MyUnit" t="s">px</a>
<a n="SpotMinimumToCellIntensity" t="s">0.1</a>
<a n="SpotPeakRadius" t="s">0</a>
<a n="SpotPeakRadius__MyUnit" t="s">px</a>
<a n="UnitType" t="s">px</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="B" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="dBackGroundCorrection" t="s">0.5</a>
<a n="DetectionSensitivity" t="s">0.6</a>
<a n="MinRelativeSignal" t="s">0.03</a>
<a n="SplittingCoefficient" t="s">1</a>
<a n="SplittingSensitivity" t="s">0.855</a>
<a n="SpotMaximumRadius" t="s">50</a>
<a n="SpotMaximumRadius__MyUnit" t="s">px</a>
<a n="SpotMinimumContrast" t="s">0</a>
<a n="SpotMinimumDistance" t="s">2</a>
<a n="SpotMinimumDistance__MyUnit" t="s">px</a>
<a n="SpotMinimumToCellIntensity" t="s">0.1</a>
<a n="SpotPeakRadius" t="s">0</a>
<a n="SpotPeakRadius__MyUnit" t="s">px</a>
<a n="UnitType" t="s">px</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="C" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="SpotMaximumRadius" t="s">5</a>
<a n="SpotMaximumRadius__MyUnit" t="s">px</a>
<a n="SpotMinimumContrast" t="s">0.1</a>
<a n="SpotMinimumDistance" t="s">3</a>
<a n="SpotMinimumDistance__MyUnit" t="s">px</a>
<a n="SpotMinimumToCellIntensity" t="s">1</a>
<a n="SpotPeakRadius" t="s">0</a>
<a n="SpotPeakRadius__MyUnit" t="s">px</a>
<a n="UnitType" t="s">px</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="D" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="dBackGroundCorrection" t="s">0.1</a>
<a n="DetectionSensitivity" t="s">0.95</a>
<a n="MinRelativeSignal" t="s">0.03</a>
<a n="SplittingCoefficient" t="s">1</a>
```

```
<a n="SplittingSensitivity" t="s">0.71</a>
<a n="SpotMaximumRadius" t="s">50</a>
<a n="SpotMaximumRadius_MyUnit" t="s">px</a>
<a n="SpotMinimumContrast" t="s">0</a>
<a n="SpotMinimumDistance" t="s">2</a>
<a n="SpotMinimumDistance_MyUnit" t="s">px</a>
<a n="SpotMinimumToCellIntensity" t="s">0.1</a>
<a n="SpotPeakRadius" t="s">0</a>
<a n="SpotPeakRadius_MyUnit" t="s">px</a>
<a n="UnitType" t="s">px</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select a method for detecting or characterizing spot-like features.</a>
<a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots.Method.title</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">D</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="4"><vdata k="4" t="string"><s>A</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>D</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="MinRelativeSignal" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0.03</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Lower limit for relative spot intensity, spot candidates with property value less than the limit are discarded. Range: 0..1</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">MinRelativeSignal</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Relative Spot Intensity</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1.0</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select the appropriate value for the lower limit of the parameter, spot candidates with property value less than the limit are discarded.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Relative Spot Intensity</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">0.005</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots.Method.MinRelativeSignal</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0.03</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="6" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="6" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJyrFlnn/rBqiv0OudbXgTvm2VeD+Uug9BZ7YzA4bD9rJgictAcAJKIWRg==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">0.05</a>
```

```

</m>
</a>
<a n="DetectionSensitivity" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0.5</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Determines how intense a spot must be. Higher values return generally more
spots and the detected spot appear also larger. Range: 0..1.0.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">DetectionSensitivity</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Detection Sensitivity</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1.0</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select the appropriate value for the parameter. Range: 0..1.0.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Detection Sensitivity</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">0.05</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots.Method.DetectionSensitivity</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0.95</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="6" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="6"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJybNRMETtobg8Fl+1lg/k17BjB4ABV/DBV/aQ8A6rQTxQ==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">0.05</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SplittingCoefficient" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">1</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Controls splitting of stuck spot candidates. Higher values return
increasingly more splitting events. Range: 0..1.0.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">SplittingCoefficient</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Splitting Coefficient</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1.0</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select the appropriate value for the parameter. Higher values return
increasingly more splitting events. Range: 0..1.0.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Splitting Coefficient</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">0.005</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots.Method.SplittingCoefficient</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="6" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="6"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBB/ZpYPDMftZMEHpf/YMCLyBir+zBytj+GAPAOc0FBw=
</vdata>

```

```

<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">0.05</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SplittingSensitivity" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0.5</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Controls splitting of stuck spot candidates. Higher values return
increasingly more splitting events. Range: 0..1.0.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">SplittingSensitivity</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Splitting Coefficient</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1.0</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select the appropriate value for the parameter. Higher values return
increasingly more splitting events. Range: 0..1.0.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Splitting Coefficient</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">0.005</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots.Method.SplittingSensitivity</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0.71</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="6" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="6"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJybNRMETtobg8FL+1lg/k17BjB4ABV/DBV/aQ8A6rQTxQ==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">0.05</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="dBackgroundCorrection" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0.5</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Tuning parameter for selecting background correction. Value 0 yields nearly
constant background.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">dBackgroundCorrection</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Background Correction</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1.0</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Iview_Wizard" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>imCorrectedImageFindSpots</
s><s>SpotsFindSpots</s><s>PopulationFindSpots</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">0.005</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots.Method.More.dBackgroundCorrection</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>

```

```
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0.1</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="7" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="7"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYICAWTNB4KQ9hL5pDxF9YG8MBo+h4i+h4h/sAQL6ErA=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">0.05</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AddPropertiesAndRegions" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">1</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate properties and add them to output populations</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AddPropertiesAndRegions</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Calculate Spot Properties</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots.Method.More.AddPropertiesAndRegions</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SpotMaximumRadius" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">50</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Upper limit for radius of spot-like features. Determines the maximum radius
of regions created around the local intensity maxima.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">SpotMaximumRadius</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Radius</a>
<a n="max" t="s">100.1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0.99</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDefaultTab" t="s">SpotClassificationFindSpots</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Define the approximate upper limit for radius of spot-like features.
The parameter determines the maximum radius of regions created around the local intensity maxima.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Radius</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s">&le;</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">0.1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots.Method.More.SpotMaximumRadius</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s">px</a>
<a n="value" t="s">50</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="4" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="4"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYAABEQcwxACpU2gtKcDABRkAbY=
```

```

</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="UnitType" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">px</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Unit for the inputs Radius, Distance and Spot Peak Radius.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">UnitType</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Unit</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots.Method.More.SpotMaximumRadius.Unit</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">px</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>µm</
s><s>px</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>px</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SpotMinimumContrast" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Minimum allowed contrast for spot-like features, objects with contrast less
than the limit are discarded.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">SpotMinimumContrast</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Contrast</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1.0</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDefaultTab" t="s">SpotClassificationFindSpots</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select a proper value for the main classification parameter. Objects
with contrast less than the limit are discarded.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Contrast</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">0.01</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots.Method.More.SpotMinimumContrast</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="15" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="15"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYICApF17g+rptjPmgkCK6H0TntjMDgM5Z+0h6i+ABW/DBW/CRV/ABV/bJ8G
Bs+g8i/tz54BgTdQdR/sAXFdLnQ=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>

```

```

</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">0.05</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SpotMinimumToCellIntensity" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0.1</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Minimum allowed spot to region intensity ratio, objects with the parameter
value less than the limit are discarded.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">SpotMinimumToCellIntensity</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Uncorrected Spot to Region Intensity</a>
<a n="max" t="s">10.0</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDefaultTab" t="s">SpotClassificationFindSpots</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select a proper value for the classification parameter, objects with
the parameter value less than the limit are discarded.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Spot to Region Intensity</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">0.1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots.Method.More.SpotMinimumToCellIntensity</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0.1</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="12" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="12"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAGF+wh9AMo/QJKf4DSX6D0DyJN4AChWKA0B5QWgNIiDgC/aQhf
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">0.1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SpotMinimumDistance" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">2</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Minimum allowed distance between two local intensity maxima (spot centers).
If distance is less than the limit two maxima are regarded as a single object.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">SpotMinimumDistance</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Distance</a>
<a n="max" t="s">20.1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0.99</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDefaultTab" t="s">SpotClassificationFindSpots</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select a proper value for the parameter, which defines a minimum
allowed distance between two local intensity maxima (spot centers).</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Distance</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s">&g></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">0.1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots.Method.More.SpotMinimumDistance</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>

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```

<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s">px</a>
<a n="value" t="s">2</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="7" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="7"
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SpotPeakRadius" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Radius of the disk, where the spot peak intensity is calculated. In the most
cases there is no need to change the default value 0, which means that the peak intensity is equal to
the intensity of the maximum point.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">SpotPeakRadius</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spot Peak Radius</a>
<a n="max" t="s">10.1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select a proper value for the parameter. In the most cases the default
value could be used.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Spot Peak Radius</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">0.1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots.Method.More.SpotPeakRadius</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s">px</a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="7" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="7"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
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</a>
<a n="OutputName" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Spots</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Name of the output population of spot-like features.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">OutputName</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Output Population</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultNamingIsUsed" t="i">1</a>
<a n="DefaultString" t="s">Spots</a>
<a n="OriginalDefault" t="s">Spots</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="UsedListCounter" t="i">1</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>

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```
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots.OutputName</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Spots</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
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</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="FromInputs2Main" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="RegionTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s><s>Cell</s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus
Region</s><s>Ring Region</s><s>Ring Region (2)</s><s>Nucleus Region2</s></vdata>
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<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s>Region</s><s>Region</
s><s>Region</s><s>Region</s><s>Region</s><s>Region</s><s>Region</s><s>Region</s><s>Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s><s>_Region2</
s><s>_Region3</s><s>_Region4</s><s>_Region5</s><s>_Region6</s><s>_Region7</s><s>_Region8</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s><s>Cell</
s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Ring Region</s><s>Ring Region (2)</
s><s>Nucleus Region2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s>FindNuclei</
s><s>FindCytoplasm</s><s>FindCytoplasm</s><s>FindCytoplasm</s><s>SelectCellRegion</
s><s>SelectCellRegion_2</s><s>SelectCellRegion_4</s><s>SelectCellRegion_3</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s>2</s><s>6</s><s>6</s><s>6</
s><s>7</s><s>8</s><s>9</s><s>15</s></vdata>
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<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s><s>Cell</
s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Ring Region</s><s>Ring Region</s><s>Nucleus
Region</s></vdata>
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s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Ring Region</s><s>Ring Region (2)</
s><s>Nucleus Region2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s></s><s>Cell by channel
Exp2Cam2, method B</s><s>Cell border by channel Exp2Cam2, method B</s><s>Cytoplasm by channel
Exp2Cam2, method B</s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s></vdata>
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<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s><s>Cell</
s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region;%</s><s>Ring Region;%</s><s>Ring Region;%</
s><s>Nucleus Region;%</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s><s>Exp2Cam2</
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s>0</s><s>0</s><s>0</
s><s>0</s><s>0</s><s>0</s><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s></s><s></s><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s>d</s><s>d</s><s>d</s><s>d</
s><s>d</s><s>d</s><s>d</s><s>d</s></vdata>
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<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="8"><vdata k="8" t="string"><s></s><s></s><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="__initialBuildMinor" t="i">110719</a>
```

```
<a n="__initialversion" t="s">7</a>
<a n="__ProcOpenStatus" t="i">1</a>
<a n="__UsedPopulationNamesInCurrentBBRun" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spots</s></vdata>
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<a n="__version" t="s">7</a>
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</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OutputClass" t="s">Output Population</a>
<a n="OutputName" t="s">Spots</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CalculateMorphologyProperties_2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="BBHasBeenSaved" t="i">1</a>
<a n="bbType" t="s">builtin</a>
<a n="IDName" t="s">CalculateMorphologyProperties_2</a>
<a n="ImageView" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Replace me</a>
<a n="Tabs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PopulationCalculateMorphologyProperties_2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Spots</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">PopulationCalculateMorphologyProperties_2</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Population Spots with region Spot by which the new properties are calculated.</a>
a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.PopulationCalculateMorphologyProperties_2</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
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</m>
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</m>
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<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s">SingleDefaultOverLay</a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20class@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
```

```
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Spot</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Spot" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
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</a>
</m>
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n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="Render_Colormode_Standard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TranslateColormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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</a>
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<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</
s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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dimsize=0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
```

```
</m>
</a>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
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<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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</a>
</m>
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<a n="Render_Labels_Labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="Render_Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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></CallbackList></m>
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<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</
s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
</m>
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dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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```

```
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<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="palette" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
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c="container"></m>
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label="ReloadFrames" title="Palette" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /></
CallbackList></m>
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<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
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dimsize0="2" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
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<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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```

```
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
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<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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<a n="Render_ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
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</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</
s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="f">NaN</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="5"
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="5" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
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```

```
</m>
</a>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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</a>
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</a>
<a n="Render_Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="rainbowsize" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="value" t="f">10</a>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
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<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGQEAJAAQ=
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</
s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
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<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGAAAAAGAAI=
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</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
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</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="3"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
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<a n="xfmid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxz5Ny4ZM7vU/Yau9T45bads2cAgwf2AH7mCIk=
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<a n="xmax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxLjg7Zk87U4DC1bqvD0q09DgxgE0kAAHicCAM=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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```
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
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<a n="ymax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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</m>
</a>
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<a n="stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
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s></vdata>
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<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
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</m>
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c="container"><a n="Colormode_ColorTranslator" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Colormode"
t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Colormode</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
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<a n="palette" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
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<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
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<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="rainbowsize" t="f">10</a>
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<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Spots</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">Spots</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
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t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.CalculateMorphologyProperties_2.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</a>
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<a n="Description" t="s">Select population</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Population</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SelectedPopulation" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spots</s></vdata>
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<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
```

```
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateMorphologyProperties_2.WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Spots</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Nuclei/</s><s>Nuclei Selected</s><s>Spots</s></vdata>
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</m>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Spot</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select region which should be characterized.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Region</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Region</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
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</a>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
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</m>
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<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Spot</a>
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</m>
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</m>
</m>
</a>
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<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Area_ONOFF" t="s">1</a>
<a n="Area_Unit" t="s"> $\mu\text{m}^2$ </a>
<a n="Length_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Length_Unit" t="s"> $\mu\text{m}$ </a>
<a n="RatioWidthToLength_ONOFF" t="s">1</a>
<a n="Roundness_ONOFF" t="s">1</a>
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<a n="Width_Unit" t="s"> $\mu\text{m}$ </a>
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<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateMorphologyProperties_2</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateMorphologyProperties_2.Method.title</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Standard</s><s>STAR</s></vdata>
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t="string"><s>Standard</s></vdata>
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<a n="Description" t="s">Turn the area calculation ON/OFF</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Area_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Area</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
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c="container"></m>
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<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>

```

```
</m>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateMorphologyProperties_2.Method.Area_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"> $\mu\text{m}$ </a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
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<a n="Description" t="s">Unit for area property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Area_Unit</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Area Unit</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateMorphologyProperties_2.Method.Area_ONOFF.Unit</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s"> $\mu\text{m}$ </a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s> $\mu\text{m}$ </
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<a n="Description" t="s">Turn the roundness calculation ON/OFF</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Roundness_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Roundness</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
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<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateMorphologyProperties_2.Method.Roundness_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
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```

```

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<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Width_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Width</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
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c="container"></m>
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<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
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<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateMorphologyProperties_2</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateMorphologyProperties_2.Method.Width_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"> $\mu$ m</a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Width_Unit" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s"> $\mu$ m</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Unit for width property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Width_Unit</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Width Unit</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateMorphologyProperties_2</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateMorphologyProperties_2.Method.Width_ONOFF.Unit</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s"> $\mu$ m</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s> $\mu$ m</
s><s>px</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s> $\mu$ m</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Length_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Turn the length calculation ON/OFF</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Length_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Length</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>

```

```
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateMorphologyProperties_2</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateMorphologyProperties_2.Method.Length_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"> $\mu\text{m}$ </a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Length_Unit" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s"> $\mu\text{m}$ </a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Unit for length property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Length_Unit</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Width Unit</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateMorphologyProperties_2</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateMorphologyProperties_2.Method.Length_ONOFF.Unit</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s"> $\mu\text{m}$ </a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s> $\mu\text{m}$ </s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s> $\mu\text{m}$ </s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="RatioWidthToLength_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Turn the ratio width to length calculation ON/OFF</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">RatioWidthToLength_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Ratio Width to Length</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateMorphologyProperties_2</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateMorphologyProperties_2.Method.RatioWidthToLength_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
```

```
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SuffixForPropertyNames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Spot</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Common prefix for the property names</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">SuffixForPropertyNames</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Output Properties</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultNamingIsUsed" t="i">1</a>
<a n="DefaultString" t="s">Spot</a>
<a n="OriginalDefault" t="s">Spot</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="UsedListCounter" t="i">0</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateMorphologyProperties_2</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateMorphologyProperties_2.SuffixForPropertyNames</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Spot</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="FromInputs2Main" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="RegionTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>_Region1</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>FindSpots</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>16</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spots found in Nucleus
Region2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot;Nucleus
Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Exp2Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">4</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="__initialBuildMinor" t="i">110719</a>
<a n="__initialversion" t="s">6</a>
<a n="__ProcOpenStatus" t="i">1</a>
<a n="__version" t="s">6</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OutputClass" t="s">Output Properties</a>
<a n="OutputName" t="s">Spot</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SelectPopulation_2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="BBHasBeenSaved" t="i">1</a>
<a n="bbType" t="s">builtin</a>
<a n="IDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_2</a>
<a n="ImageView" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Replace me</a>
<a n="Tabs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PopulationSelectPopulation_2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Spots</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">PopulationSelectPopulation_2</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Number of selected objects: 160; Number of discarded objects: 0; Total number
of objects: 160</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2"
t="string"><s>Selected Objects</s><s>Discarded Objects</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Properties Spots</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.PopulationSelectPopulation_2</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTable0n" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Summary</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttrTypeTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s">SingleDefaultOverLayMixed</a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20class@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">yellow</a>
```

```
<a n="default_color" t="s">yellow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Spot</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">red</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">red</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="default_color" t="s">green</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Discarded Objects</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">body</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Selected Objects</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@205@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@206@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20pri
ority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@207@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20pri
ority@2c@20style@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">body</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Discarded@20Objects" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">violet</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">2</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">2</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Selected@20Objects" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">blue</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Spot" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__cnt_defaults" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@Discarded@200objects" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="color" t="s">violet</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">2</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">2</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Selected@200objects" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">blue</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Controls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="general" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Render_Colormode_Standard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TranslateColormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="TranslateColormode" title="ColorMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0"
disabled="0" /></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</
s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
```

```
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Labels_Labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ColoringMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</
s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAMAAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
```

```
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="palette" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
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</m>
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<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="Palette" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /></
CallbackList></m>
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<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="2" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsz0="2" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
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</m>
</a>
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label="ReloadFrames" title="ReloadFrames" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</
s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="f">NaN</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="5"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBH/UMK0CDPZThAKE4HABJFgMv
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="5" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMAEAAAUAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
```

```
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="rainbowsize" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="value" t="f">10</a>
</m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
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</a>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGQEAJAAQ=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</
s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYgQAAAFAAI=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="3"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xfmid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxz5ny4ZM7vU/Yau9T45bads2cAgwf2AH7mCIk=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xmax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxLjg7Zk7U4DC1bqvD0q09DgXgE0kAAHicCAM=
</vdata>
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```

```
</m>
</a>
<a n="xmin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJyzV3/5SjhN3yFBN+BluLe1AwMUAAB19AYD
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ymax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBD/YMaDQAI0Djg==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<a n="ymid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBB/YMaDQAIP0DXg==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
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Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMA0AAAYAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="image_title" t="s">Channels</a>
<a n="stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s></s><s></s><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>yellow</
s><s>green</s><s>red</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>yellow</s><s>green</s><s>red</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGEAAAAGAAM=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Spot</
s><s>Selected Objects</s><s>Discarded Objects</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="3"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="priority" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="3"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Border</
s><s>body</s><s>body</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="stencil_title" t="s">Overlays</a>
<a n="tracker" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
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</a>
<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation_2.Outputs.Wholecells_ForIllustration.dataite
m</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="cIViewRelatedPopulationData" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Illustration@20SelectPopulation_2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="TabName"
t="s">FilteredSelectPopulation_2</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>yellow</s><s>green</s><s>red</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Border</
s><s>body</s><s>body</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">green</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">body</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Selected@200Objects" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">blue</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Discarded@200Objects" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">violet</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="s">0</a>
<a n="cRenderSettings" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Render" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="Colormode_ColorTranslator" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Colormode"
t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Colormode</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="colormode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Images</a>
<a n="palette" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">ScaleBar</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="f">NaN</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">Stencils</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="rainbowsize" t="f">10</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Spots" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Spots</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">Spots</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString"
```

```
t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation_2.Outputs.Wholecells_ForIllustration.dataitem</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="FilteredSelectPopulation_2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Spots Selected</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">FilteredSelectPopulation_2</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Qualified objects (160).</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIClass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Properties Spots Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.FilteredSelectPopulation_2</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
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</vdata>
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</m>
</a>
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</vdata>
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</a>
<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s">SingleDefaultOverLay</a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20class@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Spot</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Spot" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
```

```
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
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c="container"><a n="Spot" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
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</m>
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</m>
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<a n="Render_Colormode_Standard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
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c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
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</a>
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label="TranslateColormode" title="ColorMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="">
disabled="0" /></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</
s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
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dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
```

```
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
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<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Labels_Labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
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<a n="Render_Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
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label="ReloadFrames" title="ColoringMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList></m>
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<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</
s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
```

```
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="palette" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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label="ReloadFrames" title="Palette" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /></
CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
</m>
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<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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dimsize0="2" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjyIAAAAAIAAE=
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
```

```
</a>
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<a n="ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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</m>
</a>
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label="ReloadFrames" title="ReloadFrames" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
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</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</
s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="f">NaN</a>
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</vdata>
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</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="5" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
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<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</
s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
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<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="3"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xfmid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxz5ny4ZM7vU/Yau9T45bads2cAgwf2AH7mCIk=
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</m>
</a>
<a n="xmax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxLjg7Zk87U4DC1bqvD0q09DgxgE0kAAHicCAM=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xmin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJyzV3/5SjhN3yFBN+BluleLAWMUAAB19AYD
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ymax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBD/YMaDQAI0Djg==
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
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<a n="ymid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBB/YMaDQAI0DXg==
</vdata>
```

```
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMAOAAAYAAE=
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
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</a>
<a n="image_title" t="s">Channels</a>
<a n="stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjBAAAAGAC
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</m>
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<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="priority" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="stencil_title" t="s">0overlays</a>
<a n="tracker" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
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</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation_2.Outputs.WholeCells_filtered.DataItem</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="cIViewRelatedPopulationData" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Spots" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="TabName" t="s">PopulationSelectPopulation_2</
a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
```

```
c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Selected" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Spots Selected</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">@Spots@20Selected</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString"
t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation_2.Outputs.WholeCells_filtered.DataItem</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Callbacks" t="i">0</a>
<a n="current_tab" t="s">PopulationSelectPopulation_2</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Inputs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="WholeCells_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select an input population based on which a new population should be
created.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Population</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SelectedPopulation" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spots</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>WholeCells</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spots</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RefString" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.CalculateMorphologyProperties_2.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ValidFlag" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OriginRef" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>FindSpots</s></vdata>
</m>
```

```
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>CalculateMorphologyProperties_2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJwTZGBgAAAASAAS
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="Hidden" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="InternalIDNumber" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="InvalidatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="NewPopulation" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OverTakenFrom" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>FindSpots</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="MyPopulationTypes" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Objects</s></vdata>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_2</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_2.WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Spots</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Nuclei</
s><s>Nuclei Selected</s><s>Spots</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spots</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Method" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Filter by Property</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a method by which a new population should be created</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_2</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_2.Method.title</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Filter by Property</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Filter by
Property</s><s>Common Filters</s><s>Linear Classifier</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Filter
by Property</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Attribute1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper value for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Attribute1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="f">3.00000000000000018e+34</a>
<a n="min" t="f">-3.00000000000000018e+34</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_2</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_2.Method.Attribute1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0.5</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="13" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="13"
Transfer-Encoding=zlib base64">
eJxj2sMqJGJ/zJ4BDB7YM0ys+21V8Mre+r5/7/S8T/Yu3TnPf6/8bv+wSmSd+8M/
9vamcbs8eRgd+HQ3zX2/nNnhrppb41RnNgeIPIfDhqKMiW9ruB3qs/aUTJbgc1A3
5FgjEyXgAAB6Gik9
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="f">0.32619999999999999</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttributeName1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Property by which the filtering criterion is defined</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="EvalString" t="s">AAL::GetSelectedRegion(SelectedLabel=AttributeName1, RegionTable=ScalarTable|
ScalarTable_1=TableForSelectedRegion, SelectedScalarRowIndex=SelectedRegionRowIndex)</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeName1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="FinalFilterText" t="s"> _Scalar8&gt;0.5 and
_Scalar11&gt;0.7 and _Scalar12&lt;3</a>
<a n="MaxUsedNumberOfFilters" t="i">4</a>
<a n="NumberOfFilters" t="i">4</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_2</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
```

```
<a n="TableForSelectedRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot to Region Intensity</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Scalar</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>_Scalar8</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>FindSpots</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>16</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot to Region
Intensity</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Average intensity of search
region to which the spot object belongs to</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot to Region Intensity</
s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Exp2Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot to Region
Intensity</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot to Region Intensity</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="_order" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjZ2BgAAAAIAAI
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_2.Method.Attribute1.label</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Spot to Region Intensity</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="12"><vdata k="12" t="string"><s></
s><s>Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Corrected Spot Intensity</s><s>Uncorrected Spot Peak
Intensity</s><s>Spot Contrast</s><s>Spot Background Intensity</s><s>Spot Area [px<sup>2</sup>]</s><s>Region
Intensity</s><s>Spot to Region Intensity</s><s>Spot Area [μm<sup>2</sup>]</s><s>Spot Roundness</s><s>Spot Ratio
Width to Length</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot to
Region Intensity</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</a>
<a n="AttributeQualifier1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper qualifier for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="display" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</
s><s>?</s><s>&lt;</s><s>?</s><s>=</s><s>?</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeQualifier1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
```

```
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_2</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_2.Method.Attribute1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</
s><s>&gt;=</s><s><&lt;=</s><s>=</s><s>!=</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>&gt;</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Attribute2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper value for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Attribute2</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="f">3.00000000000000018e+34</a>
<a n="min" t="f">-3.00000000000000018e+34</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_2</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_2.Method.Attribute2</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0.7</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="13" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="13"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJwBaACX/08eFmpN8+Q/ZmZmZmZm5j99rrZif9nnP5T2Bl+YT0k/qz5XW7G/6j/C
hqdXyjLsP9n091Pjpe0/8BZIUPwY7z8Sg8DKoUXwP8uhRbbz/fA/7nw/NV668T+m
m8QgsHLyP1665QwCK/M/J+024A==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="f">0.0453</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttributeName2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Property by which the filtering criterion is defined</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="EvalString" t="s">AAL::GetSelectedRegion(SelectedLabel=AttributeName2, RegionTable=ScalarTable|
ScalarTable_2=TableForSelectedRegion, SelectedScalarRowIndex_2=SelectedRegionRowIndex)</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeName2</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
```

```

</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_2</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot Roundness</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Scalar</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>_Scalar11</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>CalculateMorphologyProperties_2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>17</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot Roundness</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Roundness of Spot</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot;Nucleus
Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Roundness</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Roundness</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Roundness</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="_order" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJzjZGBgAAAAKAAK
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_2.Method.Attribute2.label</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Spot Roundness</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="12"><vdata k="12" t="string"><s></
s><s>Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Corrected Spot Intensity</s><s>Uncorrected Spot Peak
Intensity</s><s>Spot Contrast</s><s>Spot Background Intensity</s><s>Spot Area [px<sup>2</sup></s><s>Region
Intensity</s><s>Spot to Region Intensity</s><s>Spot Area [μm<sup>2</sup></s><s>Spot Roundness</s><s>Spot Ratio
Width to Length</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot
Roundness</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttributeQualifier2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper qualifier for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="display" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</
s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s></vdata>
</m>

```

```
</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeQualifier2</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_2</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_2.Method.Attribute2.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</
s><s>&gt;=</s><s>&lt;</s><s>&lt;</s><s>=</s><s>!=</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>&gt;</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Attribute3" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper value for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Attribute3</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="f">3.00000000000000018e+34</a>
<a n="min" t="f">-3.00000000000000018e+34</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_2</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_2.Method.Attribute3</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">3</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="13" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="13"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJw7FXJwRK/A/bl++ZL6d+0Ye+Smf+h9eQTe9/PfcElKm/te6fnCTUf+GSvuKEo
Y+Lbb/ZbTpQBVf6293hYJbL0/b/9uxp707hdjA7mnY4JTY8w0zR0de70ec7qwAAG
HA5ePEza7WJcDgDLAS2t
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="f">0.261099999999999999</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttributeName3" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Property by which the filtering criterion is defined</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="EvalString" t="s">AAL::GetSelectedRegion(SelectedLabel=AttributeName3, RegionTable=ScalarTable|
ScalarTable_3=TableForSelectedRegion, SelectedScalarRowIndex_3=SelectedRegionRowIndex)</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeName3</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
```

```
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_2</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot Ratio Width to Length</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Scalar</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>_Scalar12</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>CalculateMorphologyProperties_2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>17</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot Ratio Width to
Length</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Ratio Width to Length of
Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot;Nucleus
Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Ratio Width to Length</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Ratio Width to
Length</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Ratio Width to Length</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="_order" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJzjYmBgAAAALAAL
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_2.Method.Attribute3.label</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Spot Ratio Width to Length</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="12"><vdata k="12" t="string"><s></
s><s>Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Corrected Spot Intensity</s><s>Uncorrected Spot Peak
Intensity</s><s>Spot Contrast</s><s>Spot Background Intensity</s><s>Spot Area [px<sup>2</sup></s><s>Region
Intensity</s><s>Spot to Region Intensity</s><s>Spot Area [μm<sup>2</sup></s><s>Spot Roundness</s><s>Spot Ratio
Width to Length</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot
Ratio Width to Length</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
```

```

</a>
<a n="AttributeQualifier3" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper qualifier for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="display" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeQualifier3</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_2</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_2.Method.Attribute3.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">&lt;</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>&lt;</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Attribute4" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper value for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Attribute4</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_2</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_2.Method.Attribute4</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttributeName4" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Property by which the filtering criterion is defined</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="EvalString" t="s">AAL:GetSelectedRegion(SelectedLabel=AttributeName4, RegionTable=ScalarTable|
ScalarTable_4=TableForSelectedRegion, SelectedScalarRowIndex_4=SelectedRegionRowIndex)</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeName4</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>

```

```
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_2</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>None</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>None</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_2.Method.Attribute4.label</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s"></a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="12"><vdata k="12" t="string"><s></s></s><s>Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Corrected Spot Intensity</s><s>Uncorrected Spot Peak Intensity</s><s>Spot Contrast</s><s>Spot Background Intensity</s><s>Spot Area [px<sup>2</sup>]</s><s>Region Intensity</s><s>Spot to Region Intensity</s><s>Spot Area [μm<sup>2</sup>]</s><s>Spot Roundness</s><s>Spot Ratio Width to Length</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttributeQualifier4" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper qualifier for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="display" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</s><s>?</s><s><sup></sup></s><s>?</s><s>=</s><s>?</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeQualifier4</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
```

```
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_2</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_2.Method.Attribute4.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</s></vdata>
<s><s>&gt;</s><s>&lt;</s><s>&lt;</s><s>=</s><s>!=</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>&gt;</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="BooleanOperations" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s"> F1 and F2 and
F3</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define boolean operations between filters, e.g. (F1 OR F2) AND F3. As
deafult AND operations are used.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">BooleanOperations</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Boolean Operations</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultNamingIsUsed" t="i">1</a>
<a n="DefaultString" t="s"> F1 and F2 and F3</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_2</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_2.Method.More.BooleanOperations</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s"> F1 and F2 and F3</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OutputName" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Spots Selected</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Name of the output population.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">OutputName</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Output Population</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultNamingIsUsed" t="i">1</a>
<a n="DefaultString" t="s">Spots Selected</a>
<a n="OriginalDefault" t="s">Spots Selected</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="UsedListCounter" t="i">1</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_2</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
```

```
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_2.OutputName</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Spots Selected</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="FromInputs2Main" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="RegionTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>_Region1</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>FindSpots</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>16</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spots found in Nucleus
Region2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot;Nucleus
Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Exp2Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="__initialBuildMinor" t="i">110719</a>
<a n="__initialversion" t="s">2.7</a>
<a n="__ProcOpenStatus" t="i">1</a>
<a n="__UsedPopulationNamesInCurrentBBRun" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata
k="1" t="string"><s>Spots Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="__version" t="s">2.7</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OutputClass" t="s">Output Population</a>
<a n="OutputName" t="s">Spots Selected</a>
<a n="SaveKeys" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>TrainingData</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SelectPopulation_4" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="BBHasBeenSaved" t="i">1</a>
<a n="bbType" t="s">builtin</a>
<a n="IDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_4</a>
<a n="ImageView" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Replace me</a>
```

```
<a n="Tabs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PopulationSelectPopulation_4" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Spots Selected</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">PopulationSelectPopulation_4</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Number of selected objects: 36; Number of discarded objects: 124; Total number
of objects: 160</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2"
t="string"><s>Selected Objects</s><s>Discarded Objects</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Properties Spots Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.PopulationSelectPopulation_4</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTable0n" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Summary</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttrTypeTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s">SingleDefaultOverLayMixed</a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20class@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">yellow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">yellow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Spot</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">red</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">red</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="default_color" t="s">green</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Discarded Objects</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">body</a>
</m>
```

```
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Selected Objects</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@205@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@206@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20pri
ority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
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n="@Container@3a@207@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20pri
ority@2c@20style@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">body</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Discarded@200bjects" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">violet</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">2</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">2</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Selected@200bjects" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">blue</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Spot" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
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c="container"><a n="@Discarded@200bjects" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="color" t="s">violet</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">2</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">2</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Selected@200bjects" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">blue</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Controls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="general" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Render_Colormode_Standard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TranslateColormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
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label="TranslateColormode" title="ColorMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0"
disabled="0" /></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</
s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
```

```
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<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Labels_Labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ColoringMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</
s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAMAAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="palette" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
```

```
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="Palette" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /></
CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="2" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="2" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYIAAAAAIAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
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</a>
```

```
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<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</
s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="f">NaN</a>
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</vdata>
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</m>
</a>
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</vdata>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
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<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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</a>
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n="memblock" c="container"><a n="value" t="f">10</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
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```

```
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
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</a>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
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s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
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<a n="xfmid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="xmax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="xmin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJzzEdR5IsIg7dBULrp47hsVBwYoAABUnwV7
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<a n="ymid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
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</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="image_title" t="s">Channels</a>
<a n="stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s></s><s></s><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>yellow</
s><s>green</s><s>red</s></vdata>
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t="string"><s>yellow</s><s>green</s><s>red</s></vdata>
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s><s>Selected Objects</s><s>Discarded Objects</s></vdata>
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</a>
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<a n="priority" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="3"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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s><s>body</s><s>body</s></vdata>
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</a>
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<a n="tracker" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
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</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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</m>
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t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation_4.Outputs.Wholecells_ForIllustration.dataite
m</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="cIViewRelatedPopulationData" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Selected@20Illustration@20SelectPopulation_4" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="TabName" t="s">FilteredSelectPopulation_4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>yellow</s><s>green</s><s>red</s></vdata>
```

```
</m>
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<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
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<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
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</m>
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c="container"><a n="Colormode_ColorTranslator" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Colormode"
t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Colormode</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="colormode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Images</a>
<a n="palette" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
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<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="f">NaN</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">Stencils</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="rainbowsize" t="f">10</a>
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<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Spots Selected</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">@Spots@20Selected</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString"
t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation_4.Outputs.Wholecells_ForIllustration.dataitem</a>
</m>
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<a n="FilteredSelectPopulation_4" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="TabItemName" t="s">FilteredSelectPopulation_4</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Qualified objects (36).</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
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```



```
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c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Render_Colormode_Standard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TranslateColormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
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<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</
s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
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</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
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dimsize="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
</vdata>
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</m>
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<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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</a>
<a n="Render_Labels_Labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
```

```
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<a n="Render_Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</
s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
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</a>
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</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
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dimsize=3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAMAAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
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<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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</m>
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<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
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```

```
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<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="2" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="2" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjyIAAAAAIAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ReloadFrames" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
```

```
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="f">NaN</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="5"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBH/UMK0CDPZThAKE4HABJFgMv
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="5" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMAEAAAUAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGQEAAAJAAQ=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
```

```
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGAAAAAGAAI=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xfmid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxL2390q7TinD2bnJfJmonH7RnA4IE9AHfHCBw=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xmax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJy7t9z82n/NJgfbqzuPqK2b4sAABpE0AJJlCSE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xmin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJzzEdR5IsIg7dBULrp47hsVBwYoAABUnwV7
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ymax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBD/YMaDQAI0Djg==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ymid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBB/YMaDQAI0DXg==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ymin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMA0AAAYAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="image_title" t="s">Channels</a>
<a n="stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjBAAAAGAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="priority" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="stencil_title" t="s">Overlays</a>
<a n="tracker" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation_4.Outputs.WholeCells_filtered.DataItem</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="cIViewRelatedPopulationData" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Selected" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="TabName"
t="s">PopulationSelectPopulation_4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="current_frame" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Micronucleoli" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Micronucleoli</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">Micronucleoli</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString"
t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation_4.Outputs.WholeCells_filtered.DataItem</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Callbacks" t="i">0</a>
<a n="current_tab" t="s">PopulationSelectPopulation_4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Inputs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="WholeCells_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select an input population based on which a new population should be
created.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Population</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SelectedPopulation" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spots Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>WholeCells_filtered</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spots</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RefString" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation_2.Outputs.WholeCells_filtered.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ValidFlag" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OriginRef" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectPopulation_2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectPopulation_2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJwTYmBgAAAATAAT
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="Hidden" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="InternalIDNumber" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZmBgAAAEEAAE
</vdata>
```

```
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="InvalidatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="NewPopulation" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OverTakenFrom" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectPopulation_2</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="MyPopulationTypes" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Objects</s></vdata>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_4</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_4.WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Spots Selected</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="4"><vdata k="4" t="string"><s>Nuclei</
s><s>Spots</s><s>Nuclei Selected</s><s>Spots Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spots
Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Method" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Filter by Property</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a method by which a new population should be created</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_4</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_4.Method.title</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Filter by Property</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Filter by
Property</s><s>Common Filters</s><s>Linear Classifier</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Filter
by Property</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Attribute1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0.0</a>
```

```
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper value for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Attribute1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="f">3.00000000000000018e+34</a>
<a n="min" t="f">-3.00000000000000018e+34</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_4</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_4.Method.Attribute1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">10</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="13" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="13"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJz7d6XipZqh2AG/JIEIyy2/7IWaD5xaeFTRYdZMIJA0cAjaIdf60tDcgev64gLb
LjsHBhB440QQ03/oq0aNmWNYWsLLQWsd+80qLb40Hg+rRNYtD3D4pgFUURrksKTA
luu6c4gDAEg/LCg=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="f">7.21699999999999964</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttributeName1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Property by which the filtering criterion is defined</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="EvalString" t="s">AAL::GetSelectedRegion(SelectedLabel=AttributeName1, RegionTable=ScalarTable|
ScalarTable_1=TableForSelectedRegion, SelectedScalarRowIndex=SelectedRegionRowIndex)</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeName1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="FinalFilterText" t="s"> _Scalar10&lt;10</a>
<a n="MaxUsedNumberOfFilters" t="i">3</a>
<a n="NumberOfFilters" t="i">3</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_4</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot Area [μm<sup>2</sup></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Scalar</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>_Scalar10</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
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<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>CalculateMorphologyProperties_2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>17</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot Area [μm<sup>2</sup></s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Area of Spot [ $\mu\text{m}$ ]</vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot;Nucleus
Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Area</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s> $\mu\text{m}$ </s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Area [ $\mu\text{m}$ ]</vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Area [ $\mu\text{m}$ ]</vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="__order" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJzjYGBgAAAAJAAJ
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_4.Method.Attribute1.label</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Spot Area [ $\mu\text{m}$ ]\text{px}]</s><s>Region Intensity</s><s>Spot to Region Intensity</s><s>Spot Area [ $\mu\text{m}$ ]</s><s>Spot Roundness</s><s>Spot Ratio Width to Length</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot Area [ $\mu\text{m}$ ]</vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</a>
<a n="AttributeQualifier1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper qualifier for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="display" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</s><s>?</s><s>< &lt;</s><s>?</s><s>=</s><s>?</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeQualifier1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_4</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_4.Method.Attribute1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">&lt;</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</s><s>&gt;=</s><s>&lt;</s><s>&lt;=</s><s>!=</s></vdata>
</m>
```

```
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>&lt;/s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Attribute2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper value for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Attribute2</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_4</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_4.Method.Attribute2</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttributeName2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Property by which the filtering criterion is defined</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="EvalString" t="s">AAL::GetSelectedRegion(SelectedLabel=AttributeName2, RegionTable=ScalarTable|
ScalarTable_2=TableForSelectedRegion, SelectedScalarRowIndex_2=SelectedRegionRowIndex)</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeName2</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_4</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>None</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>None</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
```

```

</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</m>
</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_4.Method.Attribute2.label</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s"></a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="12"><vdata k="12" t="string"><s></s></s><s>Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Corrected Spot Intensity</s><s>Uncorrected Spot Peak Intensity</s><s>Spot Contrast</s><s>Spot Background Intensity</s><s>Spot Area [px<sup>2</sup>]</s><s>Region Intensity</s><s>Spot to Region Intensity</s><s>Spot Area [μm<sup>2</sup>]</s><s>Spot Roundness</s><s>Spot Ratio Width to Length</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</a>
<a n="AttributeQualifier2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper qualifier for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="display" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</s><s>?</s><s>&lt;</s><s>?</s><s>=</s><s>?</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeQualifier2</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_4</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_4.Method.Attribute2.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</s><s>&gt;</s><s>&lt;</s><s>&lt;=</s><s>=</s><s>!=</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>&gt;</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Attribute3" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper value for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Attribute3</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>

```

```
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_4</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_4.Method.Attribute3</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIslider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttributeName3" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Property by which the filtering criterion is defined</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="EvalString" t="s">AAL::GetSelectedRegion(SelectedLabel=AttributeName3, RegionTable=ScalarTable|
ScalarTable_3=TableForSelectedRegion, SelectedScalarRowIndex_3=SelectedRegionRowIndex)</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeName3</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_4</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>None</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>None</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
```

```

<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_4.Method.Attribute3.label</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s"></a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="12"><vdata k="12" t="string"><s></s></s><s>Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Corrected Spot Intensity</s><s>Uncorrected Spot Peak Intensity</s><s>Spot Contrast</s><s>Spot Background Intensity</s><s>Spot Area [px<math>\leq</math>]</s><s>Region Intensity</s><s>Spot to Region Intensity</s><s>Spot Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2</math>]</s><s>Spot Roundness</s><s>Spot Ratio Width to Length</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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</a>
<a n="AttributeQualifier3" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper qualifier for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="display" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</s><s>?</s><s>&lt;</s><s>?</s><s>=</s><s>?</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeQualifier3</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_4</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_4.Method.Attribute3.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</s><s>&gt;</s><s>&lt;</s><s>&lt;=</s><s>!=</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>&gt;</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OutputName" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Spots Selected Selected</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Name of the output population.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">OutputName</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Output Population</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultNamingIsUsed" t="i">0</a>
<a n="DefaultString" t="s">Spots Selected Selected</a>
<a n="OriginalDefault" t="s">Spots Selected Selected</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="UsedListCounter" t="i">1</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_4</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>$ 
```

```
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_4.OutputName</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Micronucleoli</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="FromInputs2Main" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="RegionTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>_Region1</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>FindSpots</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>16</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spots found in Nucleus
Region2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot;Nucleus
Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Exp2Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="__initialBuildMinor" t="i">110719</a>
<a n="__initialversion" t="s">2.7</a>
<a n="__ProcOpenStatus" t="i">1</a>
<a n="__UsedPopulationNamesInCurrentBBRun" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata
k="1" t="string"><s>Micronucleoli</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="__version" t="s">2.7</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OutputClass" t="s">Output Population</a>
<a n="OutputName" t="s">Micronucleoli</a>
<a n="SaveKeys" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>TrainingData</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CalculateIntensityProperties_4" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="BBHasBeenSaved"
t="i">1</a>
<a n="bbType" t="s">builtin</a>
<a n="IDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_4</a>
<a n="ImageView" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Replace me</a>
```

```
<a n="Tabs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PopulationCalculateIntensityProperties_4" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered"
t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">PopulationCalculateIntensityProperties_4</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Population Nuclei Selected with region Nucleus Region by which the new
properties are calculated.</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Nucleus Region</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Properties Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.PopulationCalculateIntensityProperties_4</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTable0n" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Summary</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttrTypeTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s">SingleDefaultOverLay</a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
<a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20class@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Cell</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Ring Region (2)</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
```

```
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="flag"
t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Spot Borders</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label"
t="s">Spots</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20open@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="open"
t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Cytoplasm</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20label@2c@20open@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20open@2c@20priority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2c@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20label@2c@20open@2c@20priority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Membrane</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@205@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@205@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20priority@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@206@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20pri
ority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@207@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20pri
ority@2c@20style@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nucleus@20Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass"
t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Missing</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">4</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">-1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">4</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">4</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nucleus@20Region2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">7</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">7</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Ring@20Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">5</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">5</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Ring@20Region@20@282@29" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">6</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">6</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spot@20Borders" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">9</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">9</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Cell" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
```

```
c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Cytoplasm" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">3</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">3</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Membrane" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">2</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">2</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Spots" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">8</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">8</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__cnt_defaults" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@Nucleus@20Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverlayClass"
t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Missing</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">4</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">-1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">4</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">4</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Controls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="general" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
```

```
<a n="Render_Colormode_Standard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TranslateColormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="TranslateColormode" title="ColorMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0"
disabled="0" /></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="priorities" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjyGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</
s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAAMAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
```

```
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Labels_Labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ColoringMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priorities" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</
s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
```

```
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="palette" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="Palette" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /></
CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priorities" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="2" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize="2" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYIAAAAAIAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
```

```
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ReloadFrames" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priorities" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</
s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="f">NaN</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="5"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBH/UMKOCDPZThAKE4HABJFgMv
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="5" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMAEAAAUAEE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
```

```
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="rainbowsize" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="value" t="f">10</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGQEAJAAQ=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</
s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGEAAAGAAM=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
```



```
eJxjYCAeAAAAAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="priority" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="11" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="11"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYCAOMAIxAAAwAAI=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Border</
s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</
s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>solid</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="stencil_title" t="s">0overlays</a>
<a n="tracker" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.CalculateIntensityProperties_4.0Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="s">0</a>
<a n="cRenderSettings" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Render" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="Colormode_ColorTranslator" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Colormode"
t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Colormode</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="colormode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Images</a>
<a n="palette" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">ScaleBar</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="f">NaN</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">Stencils</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="rainbowsize" t="f">10</a>
</m>
```

```

</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString"
t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.CalculateIntensityProperties_4.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SkipTab" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ButtonDef" t="s">
    set(UI_in=UI)
    set(UI=ocnt())
    UI::C_Layout(&quot;(1)&quot;, vec(&quot;Controls&quot;),
cellalign=&quot;center&quot;, class=&quot;packer&quot;);
    //UI::C_Input(&quot;Keep View&quot;;,0,0,&quot;b&quot;;,description=&quot;Include the
current tab to the return result view.&quot;;,insert=&quot;controls.export&quot;);
    set(Buttons=UI)
    set(UI=UI_in)
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</
a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Callbacks" t="i">0</a>
<a n="current_tab" t="s">PopulationCalculateIntensityProperties_4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Inputs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="channel_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Exp1Cam1</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select channel by which the intensity statistics should be calculated</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="EvalString" t="s">AAL::GetCurrentFrameImages(EvaluationData=EvaluationData)
set(Signal=FrameImages.Exp3Cam2)</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">channel_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Channel</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_4</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_4.channel_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Exp3Cam2</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="WholeCells_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nuclei</a>

```

```
<a n="Description" t="s">Select population</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Population</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SelectedPopulation" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>@Nuclei@20Selected1</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RefString" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation_4.Outputs.@Nuclei@20Selected1.dataitem</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="ValidFlag" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OriginRef" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectPopulation</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectPopulation_4</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJwTzmBgAAAUAUAAU
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="Hidden" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="InternalIDNumber" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZmBgAAAEEAAE
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="InvalidatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="NewPopulation" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OverTakenFrom" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectPopulation_2</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="MyPopulationTypes" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Objects</s></vdata>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_4</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
```

```
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_4.WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>Nuclei/
s><s>Spots Selected</s><s>Spots</s><s>Nuclei Selected</s><s>Micronucleoli</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei
Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Cell</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a region which should be characterized</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Region</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Region</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_4</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedPropertyOrRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector"
t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>_Region5</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectCellRegion</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>7</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus Region</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus Region;%</
s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
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<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="_order" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYWBgAAAAFAAF
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">4</a>
</m>
```

```
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_4.Region</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nucleus Region</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="10"><vdata k="10"
t="string"><s>Nucleus</s><s>Cell</s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Ring
Region</s><s>Ring Region (2)</s><s>Nucleus Region2</s><s>Spots</s><s>Spot Borders</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus
Region</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Method" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a method. Please note that you can enter method sub-section and
switch the individual properties ON/OFF.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Contrast_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="CV_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Max_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Mean_ONOFF" t="s">1</a>
<a n="Median_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Min_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="QuantileFraction" t="s">50</a>
<a n="Quantile_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Stddev_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Sum_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_4</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_4.Method.title</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Standard</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Standard</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Mean_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">1</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the mean intensity</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Mean_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
```

```
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_4</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_4.Method.Mean_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Stddev_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the standard deviation</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Stddev_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Standard Deviation</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_4</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_4.Method.Stddev_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CV_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the coefficient of variance</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">CV_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Coefficient of Variance</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_4</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_4.Method.CV_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Median_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the median intensity</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
```

```
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Median_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Median</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_4</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_4.Method.More.Median_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Sum_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the sum/integral intensity</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Sum_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Sum</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_4</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_4.Method.More.Sum_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Max_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the maximum intensity</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Max_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Maximum</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_4</a>
```

```
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_4.Method.More.Max_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Min_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the minimum intensity</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Min_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Minimum</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_4</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_4.Method.More.Min_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="QuantileFraction" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">50</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Quantile fraction</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">QuantileFraction</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Quantile Fraction</a>
<a n="max" t="s">100</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_4</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">5</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_4.Method.More.QuantileFraction</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s">%</a>
<a n="value" t="s">50</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">10</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Quantile_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the quantile intensity</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
```

```
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Quantile_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Quantile</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_4</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_4.Method.More.QuantileFraction.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Contrast_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the contrast</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Contrast_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Contrast</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
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<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_4</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_4.Method.More.Contrast_ONOFF</
a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SuffixForPropertyNames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Intensity
Nucleus Region Exp3Cam2</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Common prefix for the property names</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">SuffixForPropertyNames</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Output Properties</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultNamingIsUsed" t="i">1</a>
<a n="DefaultString" t="s">Intensity Nucleus Region Exp3Cam2</a>
<a n="OriginalDefault" t="s">Intensity Nucleus Region Exp3Cam2</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
```

```
<a n="UsedListCounter" t="i">0</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_4</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_4.SuffixForPropertyNames</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Intensity Nucleus Region Exp3Cam2</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
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<a n="__initialversion" t="s">3</a>
<a n="__ProcOpenStatus" t="i">1</a>
<a n="__version" t="s">3</a>
</m>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="OutputClass" t="s">Output Property</a>
<a n="OutputName" t="s">Intensity Nucleus Region Exp3Cam2 Mean</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CalculateIntensityProperties_5" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="BBHasBeenSaved"
t="i">1</a>
<a n="bbType" t="s">builtin</a>
<a n="IDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_5</a>
<a n="ImageView" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Replace me</a>
<a n="Tabs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PopulationCalculateIntensityProperties_5" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered"
t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Spots Selected</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">PopulationCalculateIntensityProperties_5</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Population Spots Selected with region Spot by which the new properties are
calculated.</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Properties Spots Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.PopulationCalculateIntensityProperties_5</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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</a>
<a n="SummaryTable0n" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
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```

```
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<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s">SingleDefaultOverlay</a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
</m>
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<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20class@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Spot</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
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<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
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n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
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</m>
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<a n="Controls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="general" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Render_Colormode_Standard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TranslateColormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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label="TranslateColormode" title="ColorMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0"
disabled="0" /></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="priorities" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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</m>
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</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
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<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
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<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
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<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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</a>
<a n="Render_Labels_Labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="Render_Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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```

```
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base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</
s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
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<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
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t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
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<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="palette" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
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<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
```

```
base64">
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<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
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<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
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<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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<a n="ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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```

```
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<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ReloadFrames" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priorities" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</
s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="f">NaN</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="5"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBH/UMK0CDPZThAKE4HABJFgMv
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="5" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMAEAAAUAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="rainbowsize" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="value" t="f">10</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGQEAJAAQ=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</
s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGAEAAEAAI=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="3"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xfmid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJy7PVGrcYHuaftFRSorr10+b1/3IGFpG9d1ewCehAyP
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xmax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJwL/rXz0kKeJgeLeX4JMf0rHS7N4WP8zFPtAACT2grX
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xmin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJybv/XAiqPZJg7/CyPePNfwdciX7P6ePsPXAQCmawXh
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ymax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBD/YMaDQAI0Djg==
```

```
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ymid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBB/YMaDQAIP0DXg==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ymin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMA0AAAYAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="image_title" t="s">Channels</a>
<a n="stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s></s></s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>rainbow</
s><s>#FF930A</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2"
t="string"><s>rainbow</s><s>#FF930A</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="2" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="2" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZAQAAAUAAw==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Spot</
s><s>Highlighted Objects</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="2" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="2"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYIAAAAAIAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="priority" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="2" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="2"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgYARiAAAMAAI=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Border</
s><s>solid</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="stencil_title" t="s">0overlays</a>
<a n="tracker" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.CalculateIntensityProperties_5.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
```

```

<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="s">0</a>
<a n="cRenderSettings" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Render" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="Colormode_ColorTranslator" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Colormode"
t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Colormode</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="colormode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Images</a>
<a n="palette" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">ScaleBar</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="f">NaN</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">Stencils</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="rainbowsize" t="f">10</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Selected" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Spots Selected</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">@Spots@20Selected</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString"
t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.CalculateIntensityProperties_5.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SkipTab" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ButtonDef" t="s">
    set(UI_in=UI)
    set(UI=ocnt())
    UI::C_Layout(&quot;(1)&quot;; vec(&quot;Controls&quot;),
cellalign=&quot;center&quot;; class=&quot;&quot;; packer=&quot;&quot;;
//UI::C_Input(&quot;Keep View&quot;;,0,0,&quot;b&quot;;,description=&quot;Include the
current tab to the return result view.&quot;;,insert=&quot;controls.export&quot;;)
    set(Buttons=UI)
    set(UI=UI_in)
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</
a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Callbacks" t="i">0</a>

```

```
<a n="current_tab" t="s">PopulationCalculateIntensityProperties_5</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Inputs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="channel_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Exp1Cam1</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select channel by which the intensity statistics should be calculated</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="EvalString" t="s">AAL::GetCurrentFrameImages(EvaluationData=EvaluationData)
set(Signal=FrameImages,Exp3Cam2)</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">channel_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Channel</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_5</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_5.channel_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Exp3Cam2</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="WholeCells_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select population</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Population</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SelectedPopulation" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spots Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>WholeCells</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spots</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RefString" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation_4.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ValidFlag" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OriginRef" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectPopulation_2</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectPopulation_4</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJwTZmBgAAAAUAAU
</vdata>
```

```
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="Hidden" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="InternalIDNumber" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="InvalidatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="NewPopulation" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OverTakenFrom" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectPopulation_2</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="MyPopulationTypes" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0objects</s></vdata>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_5</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_5.WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Spots Selected</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>Nuclei</
s><s>Spots Selected</s><s>Spots Selected</s><s>Micronucleoli</s><s>Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spots
Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Spot</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a region which should be characterized</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Region</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Region</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_5</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedPropertyOrRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector"
t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
```

```
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>_Region1</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>FindSpots</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>16</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spots found in Nucleus
Region2</s></vdata>
</m>
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Region</s></vdata>
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<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Spot</a>
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</m>
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</m>
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</m>
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<a n="Method" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a method. Please note that you can enter method sub-section and
switch the individual properties ON/OFF.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
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</a>
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<a n="CV_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Max_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Mean_ONOFF" t="s">1</a>
<a n="Median_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Min_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="QuantileFraction" t="s">50</a>
<a n="Quantile_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
```

```

<a n="Stddev_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Sum_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_5.Method.title</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Standard</a>
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<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the mean intensity</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Mean_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
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c="container"></m>
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<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_5.Method.Mean_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
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<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Stddev_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Standard Deviation</a>
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<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
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<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_5</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
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<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
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```

```
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<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">CV_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Coefficient of Variance</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
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<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_5</a>
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<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
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<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
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<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Median_ONOFF</a>
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<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
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<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
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<a n="Item" t="s">Sum_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Sum</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
```

```
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<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
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<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_5.Method.More.Sum_ONOFF</a>
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<a n="Item" t="s">Max_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Maximum</a>
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<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Min_ONOFF</a>
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<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
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<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
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<a n="Item" t="s">QuantileFraction</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Quantile Fraction</a>
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<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Quantile_ONOFF</a>
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<a n="step" t="s"></a>
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<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Contrast_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Contrast</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
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```
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<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_5</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_5.Method.More.Contrast_ONOFF</
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<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
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<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
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<a n="SuffixForPropertyNames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Intensity
Spot Exp3Cam2</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Common prefix for the property names</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">SuffixForPropertyNames</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Output Properties</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultNamingIsUsed" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="OriginalDefault" t="s">Intensity Spot Exp3Cam2</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_5.SuffixForPropertyNames</a>
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<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Intensity Spot Exp3Cam2</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
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<a n="__version" t="s">3</a>
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t="i">1</a>
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<a n="IDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_6</a>
<a n="ImageView" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Replace me</a>
<a n="Tabs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PopulationCalculateIntensityProperties_6" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered"
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```
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<a n="TabItemName" t="s">PopulationCalculateIntensityProperties_6</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Population Micronucleoli with region Spot by which the new properties are
calculated.</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
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t="string"><s>Properties Micronucleoli</s></vdata>
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<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.PopulationCalculateIntensityProperties_6</a>
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<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s">SingleDefault0verLay</a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
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t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Spot</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
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<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
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n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
```

```
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n="priorities" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
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<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</
s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
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<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
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t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
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c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
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<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
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s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
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<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
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```

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<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
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s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
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<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
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s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
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```
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<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
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<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</
s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
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<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
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<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="5"
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eJxjYACBH/UMKOCDPZThAKE4HABJFgMv
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<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
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<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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n="memblock" c="container"><a n="value" t="f">10</a>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
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<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
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</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
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```
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Encoding="zlib base64">
eJybv/XAiqPZJg7/CyPePNfwdciX7P6ePsPXAQCmawXh
</vdata>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="ymax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBD/YMaDQAIt0Djg==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ymid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBB/YMaDQAIP0DXg==
</vdata>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="ymin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMAOAAAYAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="image_title" t="s">Channels</a>
<a n="stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s></s><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>rainbow</
s><s>#FF930A</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2"
t="string"><s>rainbow</s><s>#FF930A</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="2" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="2" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZAQAAUAaw==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
```

```
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="2" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="2"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYIAAAAAIAAE=
</vdata>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="priority" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="2" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="2"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Border</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="stencil_title" t="s">0overlays</a>
<a n="tracker" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s></vdata></m></a><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.CalculateIntensityProperties_6.0Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="s">0</a>
<a n="cRenderSettings" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Render" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="Colormode_ColorTranslator" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Colormode"
t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Colormode</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="colormode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Images</a>
<a n="palette" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">ScaleBar</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
```

```

<a n="ScaleBar" t="f">NaN</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">Stencils</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="rainbowsize" t="f">10</a>
</m>
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</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Micronucleoli" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Micronucleoli</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">Micronucleoli</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString"
t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.CalculateIntensityProperties_6.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SkipTab" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ButtonDef" t="s">
    set(UI_in=UI)
    set(UI=ocnt())
    UI::C_Layout(&quot;(1)&quot;;, vec(&quot;&quot;;Controls&quot;)),
cellalign=&quot;center&quot;;, class=&quot;packer&quot;;)
//UI::C_Input(&quot;Keep View&quot;;,0,0,&quot;b&quot;;,description=&quot;Include the
current tab to the return result view.&quot;;,insert=&quot;controls.export&quot;;)
    set(Buttons=UI)
    set(UI=UI_in)
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Callbacks" t="i">0</a>
<a n="current_tab" t="s">PopulationCalculateIntensityProperties_6</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Inputs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="channel_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Exp1Cam1</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select channel by which the intensity statistics should be calculated</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="EvalString" t="s">AAL::GetCurrentFrameImages(EvaluationData=EvaluationData)
set(Signal=FrameImages.Exp3Cam2)</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">channel_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Channel</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_6</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_6.channel_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Exp3Cam2</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s>
<s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>

```

```
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="WholeCells_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select population</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Population</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SelectedPopulation" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Micronucleoli</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>WholeCells_filtered</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spots</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RefString" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation_4.Outputs.WholeCells_filtered.dataitem</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="ValidFlag" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OriginRef" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectPopulation_4</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectPopulation_4</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJwTzmBgAAAUAUAAU
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="Hidden" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="InternalIDNumber" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYWBgAAAAFAAF
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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</m>
<m n="NewPopulation" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
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</m>
<m n="OverTakenFrom" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectPopulation_4</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="MyPopulationTypes" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0bjects</s></vdata>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
```

```
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_6</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_6.WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Micronucleoli</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>Nuclei/</s><s>Spots</s><s>Micronucleoli</s><s>Nuclei Selected</s><s>Spots Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Micronucleoli</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Spot</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a region which should be characterized</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Region</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Region</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_6</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedPropertyOrRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector"
t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>_Region1</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>FindSpots</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>16</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spots found in Nucleus
Region2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot;Nucleus
Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Exp2Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
```

```
<m n="_order" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</m>
</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_6.Region</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Spot</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Method" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a method. Please note that you can enter method sub-section and
switch the individual properties ON/OFF.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Contrast_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="CV_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Max_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Mean_ONOFF" t="s">1</a>
<a n="Median_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Min_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="QuantileFraction" t="s">50</a>
<a n="Quantile_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Stddev_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Sum_ONOFF" t="s">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_6</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_6.Method.title</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Standard</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Standard</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Mean_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">1</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the mean intensity</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Mean_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
```

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c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_6</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_6.Method.Mean_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Stddev_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the standard deviation</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Stddev_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Standard Deviation</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_6</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_6.Method.Stddev_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CV_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the coefficient of variance</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">CV_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Coefficient of Variance</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_6</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_6.Method.CV_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>

```

```
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Median_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the median intensity</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Median_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Median</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_6</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_6.Method.More.Median_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Sum_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the sum/integral intensity</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Sum_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Sum</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_6</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_6.Method.More.Sum_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Max_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the maximum intensity</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Max_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Maximum</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</a>
```

```

<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_6</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_6.Method.More.Max_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Min_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the minimum intensity</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Min_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Minimum</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_6</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_6.Method.More.Min_ONOFF</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="QuantileFraction" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">50</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Quantile fraction</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">QuantileFraction</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Quantile Fraction</a>
<a n="max" t="s">100</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_6</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">5</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_6.Method.More.QuantileFraction</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s">%</a>
<a n="value" t="s">50</a>

```

```
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">10</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Quantile_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the quantile intensity</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Quantile_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Quantile</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_6</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_6.Method.More.QuantileFraction.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Contrast_ONOFF" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate the contrast</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Contrast_ONOFF</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Contrast</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_6</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_6.Method.More.Contrast_ONOFF</
a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SuffixForPropertyNames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Intensity
Spot Exp3Cam2</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Common prefix for the property names</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">SuffixForPropertyNames</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Output Properties</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultNamingIsUsed" t="i">1</a>
```

```
<a n="DefaultString" t="s">Intensity Spot Exp3Cam2</a>
<a n="OriginalDefault" t="s">Intensity Spot Exp3Cam2</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="UsedListCounter" t="i">0</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">CalculateIntensityProperties_6</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.CalculateIntensityProperties_6.SuffixForPropertyNames</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Intensity Spot Exp3Cam2</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__initialBuildMinor" t="i">110719</a>
<a n="__initialversion" t="s">3</a>
<a n="__ProcOpenStatus" t="i">1</a>
<a n="__version" t="s">3</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OutputClass" t="s">Output Property</a>
<a n="OutputName" t="s">Intensity Spot Exp3Cam2 Mean</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="FindSpots_2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="BBHasBeenSaved" t="i">1</a>
<a n="bbType" t="s">builtin</a>
<a n="IDName" t="s">FindSpots_2</a>
<a n="ImageView" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Replace me</a>
<a n="Tabs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SpotsFindSpots_2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Spots (2)</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">SpotsFindSpots_2</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Detected Spots</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Properties Spots (2)</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.SpotsFindSpots_2</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTable0n" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Summary</s></vdata>
</m>
```

```
</a>
<a n="AttrTypeTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s">SingleDefaultOverLay</a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20class@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Spot</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Spot" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__cnt_defaults" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="Spot" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Controls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="general" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Render_Colormode_Standard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TranslateColormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="TranslateColorMode" title="ColorMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0"
disabled="0" /></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="priorities" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</
s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
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dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
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n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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</a>
</m>
</a>
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```

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c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priorities" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
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</m>
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<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
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s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
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</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
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<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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```

```
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n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
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</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
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<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
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s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
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<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
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</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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```

```
</a>
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<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
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</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</
s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
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<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="5"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
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</m>
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<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="5" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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</m>
```

```
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<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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</m>
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<a n="Render_Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="rainbowsize" t="m"><m
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<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</
s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
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</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
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</a>
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s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
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<a n="xfmid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJy7PVGrcYHuaftFRSorr10+b1/3IGFpG9d1ewCehAyP
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<a n="xmax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJwL/rXz0kKeJgeLeX4JMf0rHS7N4WP8zFPtAACT2grX
```

```
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Encoding="zlib base64">
eJybv/XAiqPZJg7/CyPePNfwdciX7P6ePsPXAQCmawxH
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="image_title" t="s">Channels</a>
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t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s></s></s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>rainbow</
s><s>#FF930A</s></vdata>
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<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2"
t="string"><s>rainbow</s><s>#FF930A</s></vdata>
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eJxjZAQAAAUAAw==
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<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Spot</
s><s>Highlighted Objects</s></vdata>
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Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYIAAAAAIAAE=
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Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</a>
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s><s>solid</s></vdata>
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<a n="stencil_title" t="s">0overlays</a>
<a n="tracker" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
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```

```
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</m>
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<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.FindSpots_2.Outputs.Spots.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="cIViewRelatedPopulationData" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="TabName"
t="s">PopulationFindSpots_2</a>
</m>
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</m>
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<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>border</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">border</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Spot" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
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<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
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<a n="current_frame" t="s">0</a>
<a n="cRenderSettings" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Render" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="Colormode_ColorTranslator" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Colormode"
t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Colormode</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="colormode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Images</a>
<a n="palette" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">ScaleBar</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="f">NaN</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">Stencils</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="rainbowsize" t="f">10</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Spots (2)</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString" t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.FindSpots_2.Outputs.Spots.dataitem</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
```

```

</a>
<a n="SkipTab" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ButtonDef" t="s">
    set(UI_in=UI)
    set(UI=ocnt())
    UI::C_Layout(&quot;(1)&quot;;, vec(&quot;Controls&quot;)),
cellalign=&quot;center&quot;;, class=&quot;packer&quot;);
//UI::C_Input(&quot;Keep View&quot;;,0,0,&quot;b&quot;;,description=&quot;Include the
current tab to the return result view.&quot;;,insert=&quot;controls.export&quot;);
set(Buttons=UI)
set(UI=UI_in)
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</
a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="spotmethodwizardFindSpots_2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Spots</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">spotmethodwizardFindSpots_2</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Detected Spots</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Properties Spots</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.spotmethodwizardFindSpots_2</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTable0n" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Summary</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttrTypeTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s">SingleDefaultOverLay</a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Spot</a>
</m>
</a>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Spot" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"

```

```
c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__cnt_defaults" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="Spot" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Controls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Images" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGQEAAAJAQAQ=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</
s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGAEAAAEEAAI=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjBAAAAGAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```

</m>
</a>
<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.FindSpots_2.Outputs.spotmethodwizard.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Spot" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="i">0</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="spotmethodwizard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">spotmethodwizard</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">spotmethodwizard</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString" t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.FindSpots_2.Outputs.spotmethodwizard.dataitem</
a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SkipTab" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ButtonDef" t="s">
    set(UI_in=UI)
    set(UI=ocnt())
    UI::C_Layout(&quot;(1)&quot;; vec(&quot;Controls&quot;);
cellalign=&quot;center&quot;; class=&quot;&quot;; packer&quot;);
    //UI::C_Input(&quot;Keep View&quot;; 0,0,&quot;&quot;;b&quot;;description=&quot;Include the
current tab to the return result view.&quot;;insert=&quot;controls.export&quot;);
    set(Buttons=UI)
    set(UI=UI_in)
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</
a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="PopulationFindSpots_2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">PopulationFindSpots_2</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Region where spots are searched and detected spots.</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2"
t="string"><s>Nucleus Region2</s><s>Spot Borders</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Properties Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.PopulationFindSpots_2</a>

```

```
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTable0n" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Summary</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttrTypeTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s">SingleDefaultOverLay</a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
<a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20class@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Cell</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Ring Region (2)</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="flag"
t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Spots (2)</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label"
t="s">Spot Borders (2)</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20open@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="open"
t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20priority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="priority" t="i">0</a>
```

```
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Cytoplasm</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20label@2c@20open@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20open@2c@20priority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2c@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20label@2c@20open@2c@20priority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Membrane</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@205@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@205@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20priority@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@206@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20pri
ority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@207@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20pri
ority@2c@20style@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
```

```
</a>
<a n="@Nucleus@20Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">4</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nucleus@20Region2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass"
t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">6</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">6</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">6</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">6</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">7</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">7</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Ring@20Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">5</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">5</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Ring@20Region@20@282@29" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">6</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">6</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spot@20Borders" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">9</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">9</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spot@20Borders@20@282@29" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">11</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">11</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
```

```
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">10</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">10</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Cell" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Cytoplasm" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">3</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">3</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Membrane" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">2</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">2</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Spots" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">8</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">8</a>
</m>
</a>
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</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__cnt_defaults" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@Nucleus@20Region2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass"
t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">6</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">6</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">6</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">6</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">7</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">7</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="@Spot@20Borders" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">9</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">9</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Controls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="general" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Render_Colormode_Standard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TranslateColormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="TranslateColormode" title="ColorMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0"
disabled="0" /></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="priorities" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</
s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAAMAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
```

```
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Labels_Labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ColoringMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priorities" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize=0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</
s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAMAAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="palette" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="Palette" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /></
CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priorities" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
</m>
```

```
</a>
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dimsize0="2" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYIAAAAAIAAE=
</vdata>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
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<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ReloadFrames" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priorities" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None/<
s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
```

```
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="f">NaN</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="5"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBH/UMK0CDPZThAKE4HABJFgMv
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="5" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMAEAAAUAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGQEAJAAQ=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</
s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
```



```
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="13" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="13" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYAADRiBkYAQAABgABA==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="13"><vdata k="13" t="string"><s>Nucleus</
s><s>Cell</s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Ring Region</s><s>Ring Region
(2)</s><s>Nucleus Region2</s><s>Spots</s><s>Spot Borders</s><s>Spots (2)</s><s>Spot Borders (2)</
s><s>Highlighted Objects</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="13" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="13"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYCAAAAAANAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="priority" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="13" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="13"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYCANMAIxAAA4AAI=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="13"><vdata k="13" t="string"><s>Border</
s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</
s><s>Border</s><s>border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>solid</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="stencil_title" t="s">0overlays</a>
<a n="tracker" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.FindSpots_2.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="cIViewRelatedPopulationData" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="TabName" t="s">SpotsFindSpots_2</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="4"><vdata k="4" t="string"><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</
s><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="4"><vdata k="4" t="string"><s>border</
s><s>Border</s><s>border</s><s>Border</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">border</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spot@20Borders" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```

<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString" t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.FindSpots_2.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SkipTab" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ButtonDef" t="s">
    set(UI_in=UI)
    set(UI=ocnt())
    UI::C_Layout(&quot;(1)&quot;;, vec(&quot;Controls&quot;),
cellalign=&quot;center&quot;;, class=&quot;packer&quot;);
    //UI::C_Input(&quot;Keep View&quot;;,0,0,&quot;b&quot;;,description=&quot;Include the
current tab to the return result view.&quot;;,insert=&quot;controls.export&quot;);
    set(Buttons=UI)
    set(UI=UI_in)
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="imCorrectedImageFindSpots_2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Background Correction</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">imCorrectedImageFindSpots_2</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Background corrected image</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Background Corrected Image</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="0" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="0" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="0" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="0"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.imCorrectedImageFindSpots_2</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTable0n" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Summary</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>

```

```
<a n="AttrTypeTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s"></a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="Controls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Images" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjBAAAAGAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Gray</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjBAAAAGAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Background
Corrected Image</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="0" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="0"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">

</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
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<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="0" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="0" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">

</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="0" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="0" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">

</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Image_title" t="s">Background corrected image</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="i">0</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="imCorrectedImage" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">imCorrectedImage</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">imCorrectedImage</a>
<a n="Images_RefString"
t="s">set(Images=EvaluationData.Procedures.FindSpots_2.Outputs.imCorrectedImage.dataitem)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">set(Stencils=Vec())</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SkipTab" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ButtonDef" t="s">
```

```

        set(UI_in=UI)
        set(UI=ocnt())
        UI::C_Layout(&quot;(1)&quot;;, vec(&quot;Controls&quot;)),
cellalign=&quot;center&quot;;, class=&quot;packer&quot;);
        //UI::C_Input(&quot;Keep View&quot;;,0,0,&quot;b&quot;;,description=&quot;Include the
current tab to the return result view.&quot;;,insert=&quot;controls.export&quot;);
        set(Buttons=UI)
        set(UI=UI_in)
    </a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Callbacks" t="i">0</a>
<a n="current_tab" t="s">SpotsFindSpots_2</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Inputs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="channel_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Exp1Cam1</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select channel for spot detection</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="EvalString" t="s">set(signal=FrameImages[q(channel_string)])</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">channel_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Channel</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select channel by which the spot-like features should be detected.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Channel selection</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots_2</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots_2.channel_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Exp3Cam2</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s>
<s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="WholeCells_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a population with the region where the spot-like features should be
searched and detected</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Population</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SelectedPopulation" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>WholeCells</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RefString" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"

```

```
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.CalculateIntensityProperties_4.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ValidFlag" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OriginRef" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectPopulation</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>CalculateIntensityProperties_4</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJwTYWBgAAAAVAAV
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="Hidden" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="InternalIDNumber" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="InvalidatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="NewPopulation" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OverTakenFrom" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectPopulation_4</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="MyPopulationTypes" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Objects</s></vdata>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select a population with the region where the spot-like features should be searched and detected.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Select population</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots_2</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots_2.WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>Nuclei</s><s>Spots</s><s>Nuclei Selected</s><s>Spots Selected</s><s>Micronucleoli</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Cell</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select region where the spot-like features should be searched and detected</a>
```

```
a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Region</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Region</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select region where the spot-like features should be searched and
detected.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Select Region</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots_2</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedPropertyOrRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector"
t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus Region2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>_Region8</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus Region2</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectCellRegion_3</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>15</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus Region2</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus Region;%</
s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="_order" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjZ2BgAAAAIAAI
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots_2.Region</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nucleus Region2</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="10"><vdata k="10"
t="string"><s>Nucleus</s><s>Cell</s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Ring
Region</s><s>Ring Region (2)</s><s>Nucleus Region2</s><s>Spots</s><s>Spot Borders</s></vdata>
```

```

</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus
Region2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Method" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">A</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a method for detecting or characterizing spot-like features</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Iview_Wizard" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>spotmethodwizardFindSpots_2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="A" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="dBackgroundCorrection" t="s">0.5</a>
<a n="DetectionSensitivity" t="s">0.5</a>
<a n="MinRelativeSignal" t="s">0.03</a>
<a n="SplittingCoefficient" t="s">1</a>
<a n="SplittingSensitivity" t="s">0.5</a>
<a n="SpotMaximumRadius" t="s">50</a>
<a n="SpotMaximumRadius__MyUnit" t="s">px</a>
<a n="SpotMinimumContrast" t="s">0</a>
<a n="SpotMinimumDistance" t="s">2</a>
<a n="SpotMinimumDistance__MyUnit" t="s">px</a>
<a n="SpotMinimumToCellIntensity" t="s">0.1</a>
<a n="SpotPeakRadius" t="s">0</a>
<a n="SpotPeakRadius__MyUnit" t="s">px</a>
<a n="UnitType" t="s">px</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="D" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="dBackgroundCorrection" t="s">0.035</a>
<a n="DetectionSensitivity" t="s">0.95</a>
<a n="MinRelativeSignal" t="s">0.03</a>
<a n="SplittingCoefficient" t="s">1</a>
<a n="SplittingSensitivity" t="s">0.5</a>
<a n="SpotMaximumRadius" t="s">50</a>
<a n="SpotMaximumRadius__MyUnit" t="s">px</a>
<a n="SpotMinimumContrast" t="s">0</a>
<a n="SpotMinimumDistance" t="s">2</a>
<a n="SpotMinimumDistance__MyUnit" t="s">px</a>
<a n="SpotMinimumToCellIntensity" t="s">0.1</a>
<a n="SpotPeakRadius" t="s">0</a>
<a n="SpotPeakRadius__MyUnit" t="s">px</a>
<a n="UnitType" t="s">px</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select a method for detecting or characterizing spot-like features.</
a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots_2</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots_2.Method.title</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">D</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="4"><vdata k="4" t="string"><s>A/<
s><s>B</s><s>C</s><s>D</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>D</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>

```

```
<a n="MinRelativeSignal" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0.03</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Lower limit for relative spot intensity, spot candidates with property value
less than the limit are discarded. Range: 0..1</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">MinRelativeSignal</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Relative Spot Intensity</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1.0</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select the appropriate value for the lower limit of the parameter,
spot candidates with property value less than the limit are discarded.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Relative Spot Intensity</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots_2</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">0.005</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots_2.Method.MinRelativeSignal</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0.03</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="6" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="6"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJyrFlnn/rBqiv0UdbXgTvm2VeD+Uug9BZ7YzA4bD9rJgictAcAJKIWRg==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">0.05</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="DetectionSensitivity" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0.5</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Determines how intense a spot must be. Higher values return generally more
spots and the detected spot appear also larger. Range: 0..1.0.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">DetectionSensitivity</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Detection Sensitivity</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1.0</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select the appropriate value for the parameter. Range: 0..1.0.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Detection Sensitivity</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots_2</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">0.05</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots_2.Method.DetectionSensitivity</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0.95</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="6" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="6"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJybNRMETtobg8Fl+1lg/k17Bj4ABV/DBV/aQ8A6rQTxQ==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">0.05</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SplittingCoefficient" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">1</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Controls splitting of stuck spot candidates. Higher values return
increasingly more splitting events. Range: 0..1.0.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">SplittingCoefficient</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Splitting Coefficient</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1.0</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select the appropriate value for the parameter. Higher values return
increasingly more splitting events. Range: 0..1.0.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Splitting Coefficient</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots_2</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">0.005</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots_2.Method.SplittingCoefficient</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="6" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="6"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBB/ZpYPMftZMEHhpf/YMCLyBir+zBytj+GAPA0C0FBw=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">0.05</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SplittingSensitivity" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0.5</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Controls splitting of stuck spot candidates. Higher values return
increasingly more splitting events. Range: 0..1.0.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">SplittingSensitivity</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Splitting Coefficient</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1.0</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select the appropriate value for the parameter. Higher values return
increasingly more splitting events. Range: 0..1.0.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Splitting Coefficient</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots_2</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">0.005</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots_2.Method.SplittingSensitivity</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0.5</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="6" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="6"
```

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Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">0.05</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="dBackGroundCorrection" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0.5</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Tuning parameter for selecting background correction. Value 0 yields nearly
constant background.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">dBackGroundCorrection</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Background Correction</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1.0</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Iview_Wizard" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>imCorrectedImageFindSpots_2</
s><s>SpotsFindSpots_2</s><s>PopulationFindSpots_2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots_2</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">0.005</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots_2.Method.More.dBackGroundCorrection</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0.035</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="7" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="7"
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">0.05</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AddPropertiesAndRegions" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">1</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Calculate properties and add them to output populations</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AddPropertiesAndRegions</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Calculate Spot Properties</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots_2</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots_2.Method.More.AddPropertiesAndRegions</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
```

```

<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SpotMaximumRadius" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">50</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Upper limit for radius of spot-like features. Determines the maximum radius
of regions created around the local intensity maxima.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">SpotMaximumRadius</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Radius</a>
<a n="max" t="s">100.1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0.99</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDefaultTab" t="s">SpotClassificationFindSpots_2</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Define the approximate upper limit for radius of spot-like features.
The parameter determines the maximum radius of regions created around the local intensity maxima.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Radius</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots_2</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s">&amp;le;</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">0.1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots_2.Method.More.SpotMaximumRadius</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s">px</a>
<a n="value" t="s">50</a>
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="UnitType" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">px</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Unit for the inputs Radius, Distance and Spot Peak Radius.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">UnitType</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Unit</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots_2</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots_2.Method.More.SpotMaximumRadius.Unit</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">px</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>µm</s>
<s>px</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>px</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>

```

```
</a>
<a n="SpotMinimumContrast" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Minimum allowed contrast for spot-like features, objects with contrast less
than the limit are discarded.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">SpotMinimumContrast</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Contrast</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1.0</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDefaultTab" t="s">SpotClassificationFindSpots_2</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select a proper value for the main classification parameter. Objects
with contrast less than the limit are discarded.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Contrast</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots_2</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">0.01</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots_2.Method.More.SpotMinimumContrast</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="15" t="double" rank="1" dimsize="15"
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">0.05</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SpotMinimumToCellIntensity" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0.1</
a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Minimum allowed spot to region intensity ratio, objects with the parameter
value less than the limit are discarded.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">SpotMinimumToCellIntensity</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Uncorrected Spot to Region Intensity</a>
<a n="max" t="s">10.0</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDefaultTab" t="s">SpotClassificationFindSpots_2</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select a proper value for the classification parameter, objects with
the parameter value less than the limit are discarded.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Spot to Region Intensity</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots_2</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">0.1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots_2.Method.More.SpotMinimumToCellIntensity</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0.1</a>
```

```

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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">0.1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SpotMinimumDistance" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">2</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Minimum allowed distance between two local intensity maxima (spot centers).
If distance is less than the limit two maxima are regarded as a single object.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">SpotMinimumDistance</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Distance</a>
<a n="max" t="s">20.1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0.99</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDefaultTab" t="s">SpotClassificationFindSpots_2</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select a proper value for the parameter, which defines a minimum
allowed distance between two local intensity maxima (spot centers).</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Distance</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots_2</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s">&amp;ge;</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">0.1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots_2.Method.More.SpotMinimumDistance</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s">px</a>
<a n="value" t="s">2</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="7" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="7"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYAADBwJFAaUfOLQILJaA0gpQWwUBADSoAkk=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SpotPeakRadius" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Radius of the disk, where the spot peak intensity is calculated. In the most
cases there is no need to change the default value 0, which means that the peak intensity is equal to
the intensity of the maximum point.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">SpotPeakRadius</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spot Peak Radius</a>
<a n="max" t="s">10.1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardDescription" t="s">Select a proper value for the parameter. In the most cases the default
value could be used.</a>
<a n="WizardLabel" t="s">Spot Peak Radius</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots_2</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>

```

```
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s">0.1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots_2.Method.More.SpotPeakRadius</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s">px</a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="7" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="7"
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OutputName" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Spots (2)</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Name of the output population of spot-like features.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">OutputName</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Output Population</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultNamingIsUsed" t="i">1</a>
<a n="DefaultString" t="s">Spots (2)</a>
<a n="OriginalDefault" t="s">Spots</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="UsedListCounter" t="i">2</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">FindSpots_2</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.FindSpots_2.OutputName</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Spots (2)</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="FromInputs2Main" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="RegionTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="10"><vdata k="10" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s><s>Cell</s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus
Region</s><s>Ring Region</s><s>Ring Region (2)</s><s>Nucleus Region2</s><s>Spots</s><s>Spot Borders</
s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="10"><vdata k="10" t="string"><s>Region</s><s>Region</
s><s>Region</s><s>Region</s><s>Region</s><s>Region</s><s>Region</s><s>Region</s><s>Region</
s><s>Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="10"><vdata k="10" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s><s>_Region2</
s><s>_Region3</s><s>_Region4</s><s>_Region5</s><s>_Region6</s><s>_Region7</s><s>_Region8</
s><s>_Region9</s><s>_Region10</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="10"><vdata k="10" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s><s>Cell</
s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Ring Region</s><s>Ring Region (2)</
s><s>Nucleus Region2</s><s>Spots</s><s>Spot Borders</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="10"><vdata k="10" t="string"><s>FindNuclei</
s><s>FindCytoplasm</s><s>FindCytoplasm</s><s>FindCytoplasm</s><s>SelectCellRegion</
s><s>SelectCellRegion_2</s><s>SelectCellRegion_4</s><s>SelectCellRegion_3</s><s>FindSpots</
s><s>FindSpots</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="10"><vdata k="10" t="string"><s>2</s><s>6</s><s>6</
s><s>6</s><s>7</s><s>8</s><s>9</s><s>15</s><s>16</s><s>16</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="10"><vdata k="10" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s><s>Cell</
s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Ring Region</s><s>Ring Region</s><s>Nucleus
Region</s><s>Spots</s><s>Spot Borders</s></vdata>
```

```
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="10"><vdata k="10" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s><s>Cell</s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Ring Region</s><s>Ring Region (2)</s><s>Nucleus Region2</s><s>Spots</s><s>Spot Borders</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="10"><vdata k="10" t="string"><s></s><s>Cell by channel Exp2Cam2, method B</s><s>Cell border by channel Exp2Cam2, method B</s><s>Cytoplasm by channel Exp2Cam2, method B</s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s>Spots in Nucleus Region2</s><s>Spots in Nucleus Region2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="10"><vdata k="10" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s><s>Cell</s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region;%</s><s>Ring Region;%</s><s>Ring Region;%</s><s>Nucleus Region;%</s><s>Spots</s><s>Spot Borders</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="10"><vdata k="10" t="string"><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="10"><vdata k="10" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp2Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="10"><vdata k="10" t="string"><s>0</s><s>0</s><s>0</s><s>0</s><s>0</s><s>0</s><s>0</s><s>0</s><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="10"><vdata k="10" t="string"><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="10"><vdata k="10" t="string"><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="10"><vdata k="10" t="string"><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="10"><vdata k="10" t="string"><s>d</s><s>d</s><s>d</s><s>d</s><s>d</s><s>d</s><s>d</s><s>d</s></vdata>
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<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="10"><vdata k="10" t="string"><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">4</a>
</m>
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</a>
</m>
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</m>
<a n="__initialBuildMinor" t="i">110719</a>
<a n="__initialVersion" t="s">7</a>
<a n="__ProcOpenStatus" t="i">1</a>
<a n="__UsedPopulationNamesInCurrentBBRun" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spots (2)</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="__version" t="s">7</a>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="OutputClass" t="s">Output Population</a>
<a n="OutputName" t="s">Spots (2)</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SelectPopulation_3" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="BBHasBeenSaved" t="i">1</a>
<a n="bbType" t="s">builtin</a>
<a n="IDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_3</a>
<a n="ImageView" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Replace me</a>
<a n="Tabs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PopulationSelectPopulation_3" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Spots (2)</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">PopulationSelectPopulation_3</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Number of selected objects: 127; Number of discarded objects: 90; Total number of objects: 217</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Selected Objects</s><s>Discarded Objects</s></vdata>
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```

```
</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Properties Spots (2)</s></vdata>
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<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.PopulationSelectPopulation_3</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<a n="SummaryTable0n" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="SummaryTableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
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</m>
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<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s">SingleDefaultOverLayMixed</a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20class@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">yellow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">yellow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Spot</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">red</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">red</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="default_color" t="s">green</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Discarded Objects</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">body</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Selected Objects</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@205@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@206@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20pri
```

```
ority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
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</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@207@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20pri
ority@2c@20style@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">body</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Discarded@200bjects" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">violet</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">2</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">2</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Selected@200bjects" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">blue</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Spot" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
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<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
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t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="color" t="s">violet</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">2</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">2</a>
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</a>
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n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">blue</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">1</a>
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</m>
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<a n="Controls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="general" t="m"><m n="memblock"
```

```
c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Render_Colormode_Standard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TranslateColormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
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<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
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<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</
s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
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</a>
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</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
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dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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</a>
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<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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</a>
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<a n="Render_Labels_Labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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```
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<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
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c="container"></m>
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<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</
s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
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<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
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t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
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dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
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</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
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<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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</m>
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<a n="palette" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
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c="container"></m>
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</a>
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```

```
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<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
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<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
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</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
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<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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</a>
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<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
```

```
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
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<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="f">NaN</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="5"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBH/UMKOCDPZThAKE4HABJFgMv
</vdata>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="5" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
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</m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
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<a n="Render_Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="rainbowsize" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="value" t="f">10</a>
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<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
```

```
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<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</
s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
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</a>
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t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
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<a n="xfmid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxz5Ny4ZM7vU/Yau9T45bads2cAgwf2AH7mCIk=
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</a>
<a n="xmax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxLjg7Zk87U4DC1bqvD0q09DgxgE0kAAHicCAM=
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</m>
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<a n="xmin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
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eJyzV3/5SjhN3yFBN+BluLeLAWmUAABl9AYD
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<a n="image_title" t="s">Channels</a>
<a n="stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s></s><s></s><s></s></vdata>
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```

```
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</m>
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<a n="tracker" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation_3.Outputs.Wholecells_ForIllustration.dataitem</s></vdata>
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<a n="@spots@20@282@29@20Illustration@20SelectPopulation_3" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="TabName" t="s">FilteredSelectPopulation_3</a>
</m>
</a>
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</a>
<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>yellow</s><s>green</s><s>red</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Border</s><s>body</s><s>body</s></vdata>
</m>
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<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">body</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Selected@200bjects" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">blue</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Discarded@200bjects" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">violet</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
```

```
</m>
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c="container"><a n="Colormode_ColorTranslator" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Colormode"
t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Colormode</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
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<a n="Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="colormode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Images</a>
<a n="palette" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
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<a n="ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">ScaleBar</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="f">NaN</a>
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</a>
<a n="Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">Stencils</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="rainbowsize" t="f">10</a>
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<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
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</m>
</a>
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</a>
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<a n="TabItemName" t="s">FilteredSelectPopulation_3</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Qualified objects (127).</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
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```

```
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<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
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t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
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<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
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c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
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c="container"></m>
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</m>
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<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</
s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
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<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
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<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="Render_Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
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c="container"></m>
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```
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<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</
s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
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<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
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<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
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c="container"></m>
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<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
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s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
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<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
```

```
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<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
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<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="f">NaN</a>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
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<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
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t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
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```
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjBAAAAGAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
```

```
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Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="priority" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="stencil_title" t="s">Overlays</a>
<a n="tracker" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation_3.Outputs.WholeCells_filtered.DataItem</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="cIViewRelatedPopulationData" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="TabName"
t="s">PopulationSelectPopulation_3</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Spots (2) Selected</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString"
t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation_3.Outputs.WholeCells_filtered.DataItem</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</
```

```
a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Callbacks" t="i">0</a>
<a n="current_tab" t="s">PopulationSelectPopulation_3</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Inputs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="WholeCells_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select an input population based on which a new population should be
created.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Population</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SelectedPopulation" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spots (2)</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spots</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spots</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RefString" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.FindSpots_2.Outputs.Spots.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ValidFlag" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OriginRef" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>FindSpots_2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>FindSpots_2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJwT2ZBgAAAAYAAAY
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="Hidden" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="InternalIDNumber" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYmBgAAAADAAD
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="InvalidatedAtNo" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="NewPopulation" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="OverTakenFrom" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>FindSpots_2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="MyPopulationTypes" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0objects</s></vdata>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
```

```

</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_3</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_3.WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Spots (2)</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>Nuclei/
s</s><s>Spots</s><s>Spots Selected</s><s>Micronucleoli</s><s>Nuclei Selected</s><s>Spots (2)</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spots
(2)</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Method" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Filter by Property</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a method by which a new population should be created</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s"></a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_3</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_3.Method.title</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Filter by Property</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Filter by
Property</s><s>Common Filters</s><s>Linear Classifier</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Filter
by Property</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Attribute1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper value for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Attribute1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="f">3.00000000000000018e+34</a>
<a n="min" t="f">-3.00000000000000018e+34</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_3</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>

```

```
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_3.Method.Attribute1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1.2</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="13" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="13"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJwBaACX/wkbnl4py+I/s3vysFBR6j+gGi/dJAbxP6JFtvP91PQ/Di2yne+n+D8Q
WDM0yHb8P4lBYOXIqBACtejd0KAKDByqFFtvMDQEJg5dAi2wVAw/UoXI/CB0B5
6SYxCKwJQPP+arx0kwtAZDAw8Q==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="f">0.238300000000000012</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttributeName1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Property by which the filtering criterion is defined</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="EvalString" t="s">AAL::GetSelectedRegion(SelectedLabel=AttributeName1, RegionTable=ScalarTable|
ScalarTable_1=TableForSelectedRegion, SelectedScalarRowIndex_1=SelectedRegionRowIndex)</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeName1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="FinalFilterText" t="s"> _Scalar8&gt;1.2</a>
<a n="MaxUsedNumberOfFilters" t="i">3</a>
<a n="NumberOfFilters" t="i">3</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_3</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot to Region Intensity</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Scalar</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>_Scalar8</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>FindSpots_2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>23</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot to Region
Intensity</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Average intensity of search
region to which the spot object belongs to</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot to Region Intensity</
s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot to Region
Intensity</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot to Region Intensity</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
</m>
```

```
<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="__order" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjZ2BgAAAAIAAI
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_3.Method.Attribute1.label</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Spot to Region Intensity</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="9"><vdata k="9" t="string"><s></
s><s>Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Corrected Spot Intensity</s><s>Uncorrected Spot Peak
Intensity</s><s>Spot Contrast</s><s>Spot Background Intensity</s><s>Spot Area [px<math>\leq</math>]</s><s>Region
Intensity</s><s>Spot to Region Intensity</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot to
Region Intensity</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttributeQualifier1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper qualifier for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="display" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</
s><s>?</s><s>&lt;</s><s>?</s><s>=</s><s>?</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s"></a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeQualifier1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_3</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_3.Method.Attribute1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</
s><s>&gt;=</s><s>&lt;</s><s>&lt;</s><s>=</s><s>!=</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>&gt;</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Attribute2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper value for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Attribute2</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
```

```

<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_3</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_3.Method.Attribute2</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttributeName2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Property by which the filtering criterion is defined</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="EvalString" t="s">AAL:GetSelectedRegion(SelectedLabel=AttributeName2, RegionTable=ScalarTable|
ScalarTable_2=TableForSelectedRegion, SelectedScalarRowIndex_2=SelectedRegionRowIndex)</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeName2</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_3</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>None</s></vdata>
</m>
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<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s"></a>
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```

```

s><s>Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Corrected Spot Intensity</s><s>Uncorrected Spot Peak
Intensity</s><s>Spot Contrast</s><s>Spot Background Intensity</s><s>Spot Area [px<math>\leq</math>]</s><s>Region
Intensity</s><s>Spot to Region Intensity</s></vdata>
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s><s>?</s><s>&lt;</s><s>?</s><s>=</s><s>?</s></vdata>
</m>
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<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeQualifier2</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
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<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
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<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_3</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_3.Method.Attribute2.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
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<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</
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<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Attribute3</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
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<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_3</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_3.Method.Attribute3</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
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</a>
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<a n="Description" t="s">Property by which the filtering criterion is defined</a>

```

```
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="EvalString" t="s">AAL::GetSelectedRegion(SelectedLabel=AttributeName3, RegionTable=ScalarTable|
ScalarTable_3=TableForSelectedRegion, SelectedScalarRowIndex_3=SelectedRowIndex)</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeName3</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
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c="container"></m>
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<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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</a>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>None</s></vdata>
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<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
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<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_3.Method.Attribute3.label</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s"></a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="9"><vdata k="9" t="string"><s></
s><s>Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Corrected Spot Intensity</s><s>Uncorrected Spot Peak
Intensity</s><s>Spot Contrast</s><s>Spot Background Intensity</s><s>Spot Area [px<math>\leq</math>]</s><s>Region
Intensity</s><s>Spot to Region Intensity</s></vdata>
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<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></
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</a>
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<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper qualifier for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="display" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</
s><s>?</s><s>&lt;</s><s>?</s><s>=</s><s>?</s></vdata>
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```

```
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<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeQualifier3</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
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<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_3</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_3.Method.Attribute3.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</
s><s>&gt;=</s><s>=</s><s>!=</s></vdata>
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<a n="Description" t="s">Name of the output population.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">OutputName</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Output Population</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultNamingIsUsed" t="i">1</a>
<a n="DefaultString" t="s">Spots (2) Selected</a>
<a n="OriginalDefault" t="s">Spots (2) Selected</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_3.OutputName</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Spots (2) Selected</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
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c="container"><a n="RegionTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Region</s></vdata>
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<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>_Region1</s></vdata>
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</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>23</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
```

```
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spots found in Nucleus
Region2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot;Nucleus
Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
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<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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<a n="__initialBuildMinor" t="i">110719</a>
<a n="__initialversion" t="s">2.7</a>
<a n="__ProcOpenStatus" t="i">1</a>
<a n="__UsedPopulationNamesInCurrentBBRun" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata
k="1" t="string"><s>Spots (2) Selected</s></vdata>
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<a n="__version" t="s">2.7</a>
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</a>
<a n="OutputClass" t="s">Output Population</a>
<a n="OutputName" t="s">Spots (2) Selected</a>
<a n="SaveKeys" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>TrainingData</s></vdata>
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<a n="SelectPopulation_5" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="BBHasBeenSaved" t="i">1</a>
<a n="bbType" t="s">builtin</a>
<a n="IDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_5</a>
<a n="ImageView" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Replace me</a>
<a n="Tabs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PopulationSelectPopulation_5" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">PopulationSelectPopulation_5</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Number of selected objects: 1; Number of discarded objects: 63; Total number of
objects: 64</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2"
t="string"><s>Selected Objects</s><s>Discarded Objects</s></vdata>
</m>
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<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Properties Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
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<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">Feedback.PopulationSelectPopulation_5</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
```

```
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</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTable0n" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
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eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
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t="string"><s>Summary</s></vdata>
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<a n="AttrTypeTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
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</m>
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<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s">SingleDefaultOverLayMixed</a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
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<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
<a n="color" t="s">red</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">red</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Discarded Objects</a>
</m>
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<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20class@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
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t="s">magenta</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">cyan</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Cell</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
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n="default_color" t="s">purple</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Ring Region (2)</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
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t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Spots (2)</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
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<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label"
t="s">Selected Objects</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20open@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="open"
t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20priority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
```

```
n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">body</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20style@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style"
t="s">body</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="default_color" t="s">yellow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="default_color" t="s">magenta</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Cytoplasm</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20label@2c@20open@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20open@2c@20priority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2c@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20label@2c@20open@2c@20priority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Nucleus</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Membrane</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20priority@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@205@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@205@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@205@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20priority@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
```

```
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@206@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20pri
ority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@207@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20pri
ority@2c@20style@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Discarded@20Objects" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">violet</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">13</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">13</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nucleus@20Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">4</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nucleus@20Region2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">7</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">7</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Ring@20Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">5</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">5</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Ring@20Region@20@282@29" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">6</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">6</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Selected@20Objects" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">blue</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">12</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">12</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spot@20Borders" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">9</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">9</a>
```

```
</m>
</a>
</m>
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<a n="@Spot@20Borders@20@282@29" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">11</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">11</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">10</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">10</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Cell" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Cytoplasm" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">3</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">3</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Membrane" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">2</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">2</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Spots" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">8</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">8</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__cnt_defaults" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@Discarded@20Objects" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="color" t="s">violet</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">13</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">13</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
```

```
</a>
<a n="@Selected@200bjects" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">blue</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">12</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">12</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
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</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Controls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="general" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Render_Colormode_Standard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TranslateColormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="TranslateColormode" title="ColorMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="">
disabled="0" /></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</
s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
```

```
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Labels_Labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ColoringMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</
s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize=3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
```

```
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="palette" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="Palette" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /></
CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="2" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="2" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjyIAAAAAIAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
```

```
</a>
<a n="Render_ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ReloadFrames" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</
s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="f">NaN</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="5"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBH/UMK0CDPZThAKE4HABJFgMv
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="5" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMAEAAAUAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="Render_Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="rainbowsize" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="value" t="f">10</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGQEAJAAQ=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</
s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGAAAGAAI=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="3"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xfmid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJwze3RCedLXM/ZPz0x7/KnrpD0DGDyWbWCo+Atj
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xmax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxzKqvdpiBX7/BybqzG9o29DgXgE0kAAHQ6B8I=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xmin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJy7bh5o8NJax+G0k88XqZ0mDgxQAABxSwbF
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ymax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBD/YMaDQAI0Djg==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
```



```
<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation_5.Outputs.Wholecells_ForIllustration.dataite
m</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="cIViewRelatedPopulationData" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20Illustration@20SelectPopulation_5" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="TabName" t="s">FilteredSelectPopulation_5</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>yellow</s><s>green</s><s>red</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Border</
s><s>body</s><s>body</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">green</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">body</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Selected@20Objects" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">blue</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Discarded@20Objects" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">violet</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="s">0</a>
<a n="cRenderSettings" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Render" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="Colormode_ColorTranslator" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Colormode"
t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Colormode</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="colormode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Images</a>
<a n="palette" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">ScaleBar</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="f">NaN</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Stencils_Stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="methodclass" t="s">Stencils</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="rainbowsize" t="f">10</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString"
t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation_5.Outputs.Wholecells_ForIllustration.dataitem</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</
a>
a
```

```
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="FilteredSelectPopulation_5" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">many spots cells</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">FilteredSelectPopulation_5</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Qualified objects (1).</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Cell</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Properties many spots cells</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.FilteredSelectPopulation_5</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTable0n" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Summary</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttrTypeTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s">SingleDefaultOverLay</a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
<a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20class@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Cell</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Ring Region (2)</a>
```

```
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="flag"
t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Spots (2)</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label"
t="s">Spot Borders (2)</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20open@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="open"
t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20priority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Cytoplasm</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20label@2c@20open@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20open@2c@20priority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2c@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20label@2c@20open@2c@20priority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Membrane</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@205@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@205@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20priority@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@206@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20pri
ority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@207@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20pri
ority@2c@20style@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nucleus@20Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">4</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nucleus@20Region2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">7</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">7</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Ring@20Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">5</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">5</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Ring@20Region@20@282@29" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">6</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">6</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spot@20Borders" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">9</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">9</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spot@20Borders@20@282@29" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">11</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">11</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
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n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">10</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">10</a>
</m>
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<a n="Cell" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">1</a>
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c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">3</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">3</a>
</m>
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<a n="Membrane" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">2</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">2</a>
</m>
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<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
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<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
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c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">8</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">8</a>
</m>
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c="container"><a n="Cell" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">1</a>
</m>
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</m>
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</m>
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</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Controls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="general" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Render_Colormode_Standard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TranslateColormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
```

```
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</m>
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label="TranslateColorMode" title="ColorMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0"
disabled="0" /></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</
s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
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<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize=0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjyEAAAAAMAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
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<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
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</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Labels_Labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
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</m>
</a>
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label="ReloadFrames" title="ColoringMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</
s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
</m>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
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<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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</m>
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<a n="palette" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
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</m>
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<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="Palette" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /></
CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</a>
```

```
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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dimsize0="2" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYIAAAAAIAAE=
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
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<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
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<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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></CallbackList></m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</s></vdata>
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<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
```

```
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<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="5"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBH/UMKOCDPZThAKE4HABJFgMv
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="5" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMAEAAAUAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
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<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGQEAAAJAAQ=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</
s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
```



```
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="12"><vdata k="12" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s><s>Cell</s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Ring Region</s><s>Ring Region (2)</s><s>Nucleus Region2</s><s>Spots</s><s>Spot Borders</s><s>Spots (2)</s><s>Spot Borders (2)</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="12" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="12" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYCANAAAAMAAB
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<a n="priority" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="12" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="12" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYCANAAAAMAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="12"><vdata k="12" t="string"><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="stencil_title" t="s">0overlays</a>
<a n="tracker" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation_5.Outputs.WholeCells_filtered.DataItem</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="cIViewRelatedPopulationData" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="TabName" t="s">PopulationSelectPopulation_5</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">many spots cells</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">@many@20spots@20cells</a>
```

```
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString"
t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation_5.Outputs.WholeCells_filtered.DataItem</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</a>
a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Callbacks" t="i">0</a>
<a n="current_tab" t="s">PopulationSelectPopulation_5</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Inputs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="WholeCells_string" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select an input population based on which a new population should be
created.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Population</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
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k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
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</m>
<m n="ItemType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RefString" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation_3.Outputs.@Nuclei@20Selected0.dataitem</s></vdata>
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</vdata>
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</m>
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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base64">
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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```

```
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<m n="MyPopulationTypes" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Objects</s></vdata>
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</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_5</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_5.WholeCells_string</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="7"><vdata k="7" t="string"><s>Nuclei/
s><s>Spots</s><s>Spots Selected</s><s>Micronucleoli</s><s>Spots (2)</s><s>Nuclei Selected</s><s>Spots
(2) Selected</s></vdata>
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</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei
Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Method" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Filter by Property</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a method by which a new population should be created</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_5</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_5.Method.title</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Filter by Property</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Filter by
Property</s><s>Common Filters</s><s>Linear Classifier</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Filter
by Property</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Attribute1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper value for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Attribute1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
```

```
<a n="max" t="f">3.00000000000000018e+34</a>
<a n="min" t="f">-3.00000000000000018e+34</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_5</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_5.Method.Attribute1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">4</a>
<a n="ValuesForScan" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="13" t="double" rank="1" dimsize="13"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJwzNgaBx/YMYPDBPg0MvtmfPQMCf+xnzQBRgcIn8UBoo7DAazNmNsBop4PK18A
5QtB1Yk4QPSL0gAAKK4mjA==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="f">0.40000000000000022</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttributeName1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Property by which the filtering criterion is defined</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="EvalString" t="s">AAL::GetSelectedRegion(SelectedLabel=AttributeName1, RegionTable=ScalarTable|
ScalarTable_1=TableForSelectedRegion, SelectedScalarRowIndex=SelectedRegionRowIndex)</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeName1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="FinalFilterText" t="s"> _Scalar14>>4</a>
<a n="MaxUsedNumberOfFilters" t="i">3</a>
<a n="NumberOfFilters" t="i">3</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_5</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Number of Spots</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Scalar</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>_Scalar14</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus Region2</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>FindSpots</s></vdata>
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<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>16</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spots</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Number of Spots</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Number of spots in the
region Nucleus Region2</s></vdata>
</m>
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</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Number of Spots</s></vdata>
</m>
```

```
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Exp2Cam2</s></vdata>
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<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Number of Spots</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Number of Spots</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
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<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="_order" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
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</vdata>
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<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_5.Method.Attribute1.label</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Number of Spots</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="18"><vdata k="18" t="string"><s></s></s><s>Nucleus Area [μm<sup>2</sup>]</s><s>Nucleus Roundness</s><s>Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</s><s>Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</s><s>Intensity Nucleus Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>Intensity Ring Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>Intensity Nucleoplasm Mean</s><s>Formula</s><s>Formula (2)</s><s>Total Spot Area</s><s>Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Number of Spots</s><s>Intensity Nucleus Region Exp3Cam2 Mean</s><s>Total Spot Area (2)</s><s>Relative Spot to Background Intensity (2)</s><s>Number of Spots (2)</s></vdata>
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</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Number of Spots</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttributeQualifier1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper qualifier for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="display" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</s><s>?</s><s>&lt;</s><s>?</s><s>=</s><s>?</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeQualifier1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_5</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_5.Method.Attribute1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</s><s>&gt;</s><s>&lt;</s><s>&lt;</s><s>=</s><s>!=</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>&gt;</s></vdata>
</m>
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```

```

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<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Attribute2</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_5</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_5.Method.Attribute2</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttributeName2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Property by which the filtering criterion is defined</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="EvalString" t="s">AAL::GetSelectedRegion(SelectedLabel=AttributeName2, RegionTable=ScalarTable|
ScalarTable_2=TableForSelectedRegion, SelectedScalarRowIndex=SelectedRegionRowIndex)</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeName2</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
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</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_5</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>None</s></vdata>
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<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>None</s></vdata>
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<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>

```

```

</m>
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<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
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<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</m>
</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_5.Method.Attribute2.label</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s"></a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="18"><vdata k="18" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
<s><s>Nucleus Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]/</s><s>Nucleus Roundness</s><s>Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</s><s>Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</s><s>Intensity Nucleus Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>Intensity Ring Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>Intensity Nucleoplasm Mean</s><s>Formula</s><s>Formula (2)</s><s>Total Spot Area</s><s>Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Number of Spots</s><s>Intensity Nucleus Region Exp3Cam2 Mean</s><s>Total Spot Area (2)</s><s>Relative Spot to Background Intensity (2)</s><s>Number of Spots (2)</s></vdata>
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</a>
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<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper qualifier for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="display" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</s><s>?</s><s>&lt;</s><s>?</s><s>=</s><s>?</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeQualifier2</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_5</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_5.Method.Attribute2.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</s><s>&gt;=</s><s>&lt;</s><s>&lt;=</s><s>!=</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>&gt;</s></vdata>
</m>
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<a n="Attribute3" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0.0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper value for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">d</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Attribute3</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>

```

```
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_5</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_5.Method.Attribute3</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttributeName3" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Property by which the filtering criterion is defined</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="EvalString" t="s">AAL::GetSelectedRegion(SelectedLabel=AttributeName3, RegionTable=ScalarTable|
ScalarTable_3=TableForSelectedRegion, SelectedScalarRowIndex_3=SelectedRegionRowIndex)</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeName3</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_5</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableForSelectedRegion" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>None</s></vdata>
</m>
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</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
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</m>
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<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_5.Method.Attribute3.label</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s"></a>
```

```

<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="18"><vdata k="18" t="string"><s></s><s>Nucleus Area [μm<sup>2</sup>]</s><s>Nucleus Roundness</s><s>Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</s><s>Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</s><s>Intensity Nucleus Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>Intensity Ring Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>Intensity Nucleoplasm Mean</s><s>Formula</s><s>Formula (2)</s><s>Total Spot Area</s><s>Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Number of Spots</s><s>Intensity Nucleus Region Exp3Cam2 Mean</s><s>Total Spot Area (2)</s><s>Relative Spot to Background Intensity (2)</s><s>Number of Spots (2)</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttributeQualifier3" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a proper qualifier for the selection criterion</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="display" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</s><s>?</s><s>&lt;</s><s>?</s><s>=</s><s>?</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">AttributeQualifier3</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_5</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_5.Method.Attribute3.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">&gt;</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>&gt;</s><s>&gt;=</s><s>&lt;</s><s>&lt;=</s><s>!=</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>&gt;</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OutputName" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nuclei Selected Selected</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Name of the output population.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">OutputName</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Output Population</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultNamingIsUsed" t="i">0</a>
<a n="DefaultString" t="s">Nuclei Selected Selected</a>
<a n="OriginalDefault" t="s">Nuclei Selected Selected</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="UsedListCounter" t="i">1</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">SelectPopulation_5</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.SelectPopulation_5.OutputName</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>

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```
<a n="UIslider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">many spots cells</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="FromInputs2Main" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="RegionTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string"
k="12"><vdata k="12" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s><s>Cell</s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus
Region</s><s>Ring Region</s><s>Ring Region (2)</s><s>Nucleus Region2</s><s>Spots</s><s>Spot Borders</
s><s>Spots (2)</s><s>Spot Borders (2)</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="12"><vdata k="12" t="string"><s>Region</s><s>Region</
s><s>Region</s><s>Region</s><s>Region</s><s>Region</s><s>Region</s><s>Region</s><s>Region</s><s>Region</
s><s>Region</s><s>Region</s><s>Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="12"><vdata k="12" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s><s>_Region2</
s><s>_Region3</s><s>_Region4</s><s>_Region5</s><s>_Region6</s><s>_Region7</s><s>_Region8</
s><s>_Region9</s><s>_Region10</s><s>_Region11</s><s>_Region12</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="12"><vdata k="12" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s><s>Cell</
s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Ring Region</s><s>Ring Region (2)</
s><s>Nucleus Region2</s><s>Spots</s><s>Spot Borders</s><s>Spots (2)</s><s>Spot Borders (2)</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="12"><vdata k="12" t="string"><s>FindNuclei</
s><s>FindCytoplasm</s><s>FindCytoplasm</s><s>FindCytoplasm</s><s>SelectCellRegion</
s><s>SelectCellRegion_2</s><s>SelectCellRegion_4</s><s>SelectCellRegion_3</s><s>FindSpots</
s><s>FindSpots</s><s>FindSpots_2</s><s>FindSpots_2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="12"><vdata k="12" t="string"><s>2</s><s>6</s><s>6</
s><s>6</s><s>7</s><s>8</s><s>9</s><s>15</s><s>16</s><s>16</s><s>23</s><s>23</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="12"><vdata k="12" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s><s>Cell</
s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Ring Region</s><s>Ring Region</s><s>Nucleus
Region</s><s>Spots</s><s>Spot Borders</s><s>Spots</s><s>Spot Borders</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="12"><vdata k="12" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s><s>Cell</
s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Ring Region</s><s>Ring Region (2)</
s><s>Nucleus Region2</s><s>Spots</s><s>Spot Borders</s><s>Spots (2)</s><s>Spot Borders (2)</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="12"><vdata k="12" t="string"><s></s><s>Cell by channel
Exp2Cam2, method B</s><s>Cell border by channel Exp2Cam2, method B</s><s>Cytoplasm by channel
Exp2Cam2, method B</s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s>Spots in Nucleus Region2</s><s>Spots in Nucleus
Region2</s><s>Spots in Nucleus Region2</s></vdata>
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<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="12"><vdata k="12" t="string"><s>Nucleus</
s><s>Cell</s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region;%</s><s>Ring Region;%</s><s>Ring
Region;%</s><s>Nucleus Region;%</s><s>Spots</s><s>Spot Borders</s><s>Spots</s><s>Spot Borders</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="12"><vdata k="12" t="string"><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></
s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="12"><vdata k="12" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s><s>Exp2Cam2</
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp2Cam2</
s><s>Exp3Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="12"><vdata k="12" t="string"><s>0</s><s>0</s><s>0</
s><s>0</s><s>0</s><s>0</s><s>0</s><s>0</s><s>0</s><s>0</s><s>0</s><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="12"><vdata k="12" t="string"><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></
s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s></vdata>
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<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="12"><vdata k="12" t="string"><s></s><s></s><s></
s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s></vdata>
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<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="12"><vdata k="12" t="string"><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></
s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="12"><vdata k="12" t="string"><s>d</s><s>d</s><s>d</s><s>d</
s><s>d</s><s>d</s><s>d</s><s>d</s><s>d</s><s>d</s><s>d</s></vdata>
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<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="12"><vdata k="12" t="string"><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></
s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s></vdata>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">4</a>
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```

```
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<a n="__initialBuildMinor" t="i">110719</a>
<a n="__initialVersion" t="s">2.7</a>
<a n="__ProcOpenStatus" t="i">1</a>
<a n="__UsedPopulationNamesInCurrentBBRun" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>many spots cells</s></vdata>
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<a n="__version" t="s">2.7</a>
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</a>
<a n="OutputClass" t="s">Output Population</a>
<a n="OutputName" t="s">many spots cells</a>
<a n="SaveKeys" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>TrainingData</s></vdata>
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<a n="ReturnResults" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="BBHasBeenSaved" t="i">1</a>
<a n="bbType" t="s">builtin</a>
<a n="HasResolution" t="i">1</a>
<a n="IDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="ImageView" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Replace me</a>
<a n="PreviousTables" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="__ResultsTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="title" t="s">Results</a>
<a n="v_TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.ReturnResults.Outputs.DefinedOutputParameters_illustrative.DataTableItem</s></vdata>
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<a n="IsCurrentTable" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SummaryTableOn" t="i">0</a>
<a n="AttrTypeTable" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SummaryTableLabel" t="s">Summary</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="i">0</a>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="Tabs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20SelectedReturnResults" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">@Nuclei@20SelectedReturnResults</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Population: Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Cell</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Properties Nuclei Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.@Nuclei@20SelectedReturnResults</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTableOn" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAAACAAC
</vdata>
```

```
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<a n="SummaryTableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Summary</s></vdata>
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</a>
<a n="AttrTypeTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s">SingleDefaultOverLay</a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
<a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20class@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Cell</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Ring Region (2)</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="flag"
t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Spots (2)</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label"
t="s">Spot Borders (2)</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20open@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="open"
t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20priority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Cytoplasm</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20label@2c@20open@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20open@2c@20priority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2c@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20label@2c@20open@2c@20priority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Membrane</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@205@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@205@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20priority@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@206@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20pri
ority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a
n="@Container@3a@207@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20pri
ority@2c@20style@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nucleus@20Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">4</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">4</a>
</m>
</a>
</a>
</a>
<a n="@Nucleus@20Region2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
```

```
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">7</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">7</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Ring@20Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">5</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">5</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Ring@20Region@20@282@29" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">6</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">6</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spot@20Borders" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">9</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">9</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spot@20Borders@20@282@29" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">11</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">11</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">10</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">10</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Cell" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Cytoplasm" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">3</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">3</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Membrane" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">2</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">2</a>
```

```
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Spots" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">8</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">8</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__cnt_defaults" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="Cell" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Controls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="general" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Render_Colormode_Standard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TranslateColormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="TranslateColormode" title="ColorMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0"
disabled="0" /></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="priorities" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
```

```
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAMAAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Labels_Labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ColoringMode" trigger="onchange" priority="" category="" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priorities" t="m"><m
```

```
n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</
s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="palette" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="Palette" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /></
CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priorities" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
```

```
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="2" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="2" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYIAAAAAIAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
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</vdata>
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<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
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s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
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<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
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<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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n="memblock" c="container"><a n="value" t="f">10</a>
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```

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<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
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<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
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s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
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</vdata>
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<a n="ymid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
```



```
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s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
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</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="6"><vdata k="6" t="string"><s>Border</
s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s></vdata>
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<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
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<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
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t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="methodclass" t="s">Colormode</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
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<a n="methodclass" t="s">Images</a>
<a n="palette" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
</m>
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<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="f">NaN</a>
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<a n="pluginclass" t="s">Render</a>
<a n="rainbowsize" t="f">10</a>
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<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString" t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation_5.Outputs.WholeCells.dataitem</
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</m>
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<a n="NucleiReturnResults" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">NucleiReturnResults</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Population: Nuclei</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
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```
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t="string"><s>Properties Nuclei</s></vdata>
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<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
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<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
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<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20class@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
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t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
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<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
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n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
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<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
```

```
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c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TranslateColormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
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<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</
s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
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<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
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eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
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```

```
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
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<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priorities" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</
s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
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<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
</m>
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<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAAAE=
```

```
</vdata>
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</m>
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<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="palette" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
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</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
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</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
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n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="2" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="2" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYIAAAAAIAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
```

```
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
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<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ReloadFrames" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priorities" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</
s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="f">NaN</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="5"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBH/UMKOCDPZThAKE4HABJFgMv
```

```
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="5" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMAEAAAUAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGQEAJAAQ=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</
s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGAAAGAAI=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
```

```
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="3"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xfmid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJy7PVGrcYHuaftFRSorr10+b1/3IGFpG9d1ewCehAyP
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xmax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJwL/rXz0kKeJgeLeX4JMf0rHS7N4WP8zFPtAACT2grX
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xmin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJybv/XAiqPZJg7/CyPePNfwdciX7P6ePsPXAQCmawxH
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<a n="ymax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="ymid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMA0AAAYAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="image_title" t="s">Channels</a>
<a n="stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjBAAAAGAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nucleus</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="priority" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="stencil_title" t="s">Overlays</a>
<a n="tracker" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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</m>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.ReturnResults.Outputs.__FieldResult_Nuclei.dataitem</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Nuclei" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">Nuclei</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString" t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation_5.Outputs.Nuclei0.dataitem</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</
a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SpotsReturnResults" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Spots</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">SpotsReturnResults</a>
```

```
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Population: Spots</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIClass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Properties Spots</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.SpotsReturnResults</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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</a>
<a n="SummaryTable0n" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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t="string"><s>Summary</s></vdata>
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</a>
<a n="AttrTypeTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s">SingleDefaultOverLay</a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20class@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Spot</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Spot" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
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c="container"><a n="Spot" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
```

```
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
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</m>
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</a>
<a n="Controls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="general" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Render_Colormode_Standard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TranslateColormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="TranslateColormode" title="ColorMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0"
disabled="0" /></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="priorities" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</
s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
```

```
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Labels_Labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ColoringMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priorities" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjyGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</
s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
```

```
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="palette" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="Palette" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /></
CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priorities" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="2" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="2" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
```

```
eJxjYIAAAAAIAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ReloadFrames" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priorities" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</
s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
```

```
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="f">NaN</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="5"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBH/UMKOCDPZThAKE4HABJFgMv
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="5" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMAEAAAUAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGQEAJAAQ=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</
s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
```

```
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGAAAAAGAAI=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="3"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xfmid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJy7PVGrcYHuaftFRSorr10+b1/3IGFpG9d1ewCehAyP
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xmax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJwL/rXz0kKeJgeLeX4JMf0rHS7N4WP8zFPtAACT2grX
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xmin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJybv/XAiqPZJg7/CyPePNfwdciX7P6ePsPXAQCmawxH
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ymax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBD/YMaDQAIt0Djg==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ymid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBB/YMaDQAIP0DXg==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ymin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMA0AAAYAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="image_title" t="s">Channels</a>
<a n="stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjBAAAAGAC
</vdata>
```

```
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="priority" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="stencil_title" t="s">Overlays</a>
<a n="tracker" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.ReturnResults.Outputs.__FieldResult_Spots.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Spot" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Spots" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Spots</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">Spots</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString" t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation_5.Outputs.Spots1.dataitem</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20SelectedReturnResults" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Spots Selected</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">@Spots@20SelectedReturnResults</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Population: Spots Selected</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
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<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Properties Spots Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.@Spots@20SelectedReturnResults</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTable0n" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
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<a n="SummaryTableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
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dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s">SingleDefault0verLay</a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20class@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Spot</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Spot" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
```

```
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n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
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<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
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<a n="Controls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="general" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Render_Colormode_Standard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TranslateColormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
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</m>
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</m>
</a>
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label="TranslateColormode" title="ColorMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0"
disabled="0" /></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="priorities" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</
s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAAMAAE=
</vdata>
```

```
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
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<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Labels_Labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="Render_Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ColoringMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priorities" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</
```

```
s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
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</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
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<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
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<a n="palette" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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label="ReloadFrames" title="Palette" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /></
CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priorities" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
```

```
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
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dimsize0="2" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYIAAAAAIAAE=
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
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<a n="Render_ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
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<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ReloadFrames" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priorities" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
```

```
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="f">NaN</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="5"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBH/UMKOCDPZThAKE4HABJFgMv
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="5" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMAEAAAUAAE=
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
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<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGQEAAAJAAQ=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
```

```
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGAAAAAGAAI=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xfmid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJy7PVGrcYHuaftFRSorr10+b1/3IGFpG9d1ewCehAyP
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xmax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</m>
</a>
<a n="xmin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJybv/XAiqPZJg7/CyPePNfwdciX7P6ePsPXAQCmawxH
</vdata>
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<a n="ymax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBD/YMaDQAIt0Djg==
</vdata>
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<a n="ymid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBB/YMaDQAIP0DXg==
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eJxjYMAOAAAYAAE=
</vdata>
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</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="image_title" t="s">Channels</a>
<a n="stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjBAAAAC
</vdata>
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</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="priority" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
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</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="stencil_title" t="s">0overlays</a>
<a n="tracker" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.ReturnResults.Outputs.__FieldResult_@Spots@20Selected.dataite
m</s></vdata>
</m>
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<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
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</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Spot" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Selected" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Spots Selected</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">@Spots@20Selected</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
```

```
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString"
t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation_5.Outputs.@Spots@20Selected2.dataitem</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</a>
a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="MicronucleoliReturnResults" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Micronucleoli</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">MicronucleoliReturnResults</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Population: Micronucleoli</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Properties Micronucleoli</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.MicronucleoliReturnResults</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
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<a n="SummaryTable0n" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAACAAC
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t="string"><s>Summary</s></vdata>
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</a>
<a n="AttrTypeTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s">SingleDefaultOverLay</a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20class@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Spot</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Spot" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
```

```
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__cnt_defaults" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="Spot" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
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</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
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</a>
<a n="Controls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="general" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Render_Colormode_Standard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TranslateColormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="TranslateColormode" title="ColorMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0"
disabled="0" /></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="priorities" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</
s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
```

```
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAAAE=
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</a>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Labels_Labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
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</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ColoringMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priorities" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
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</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
```

```
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<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
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eJxjYEAAAAAAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="palette" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback label="ReloadFrames" title="Palette" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priorities" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
```

```
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="2" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="2" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYIAAAAAIAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
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base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
</a>
</m>
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</m>
</a>
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<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="f">NaN</a>
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Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBH/UMKOCDPZThAKE4HABJFgMv
</vdata>
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</a>
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dimsize0="5" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
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</m>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
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<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
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<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
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</a>
</m>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
</m>
</a>
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c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
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s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
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</m>
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<a n="xfmid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<a n="xmax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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</m>
</a>
<a n="xmin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJybv/XAiqPZJg7/CyPePNfwdciX7P6ePsPXAQCmawXH
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ymax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMAOAAAYAAE=
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<a n="image_title" t="s">Channels</a>
```

```
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t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
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Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</a>
<a n="priority" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</
s></vdata>
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</a>
<a n="stencil_title" t="s">0overlays</a>
<a n="tracker" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
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<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.ReturnResults.Outputs.__FieldResult_Micronucleoli.dataitem</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Spot" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
```

```
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<a n="current_frame" t="s">0</a>
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<a n="Micronucleoli" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Micronucleoli</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">Micronucleoli</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString"
t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation_5.Outputs.Micronucleoli3.dataitem</a>
</m>
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</m>
</a>
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</a>
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<a n="TabItemName" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29ReturnResults</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Population: Spots (2)</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Properties Spots (2)</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.@Spots@20@282@29ReturnResults</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
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dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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t="string"><s>Summary</s></vdata>
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dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</a>
<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s">SingleDefaultOverlay</a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@20@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
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<a n="@Container@3a@20@20elements@3a@20class@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
```

```
<a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Spot</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Spot" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
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c="container"><a n="Spot" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
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</a>
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</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Controls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="general" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Render_Colormode_Standard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TranslateColormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
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label="TranslateColormode" title="ColorMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0"
disabled="0" /></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="priorities" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
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</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
```

```
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Labels_Labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="Render_Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ColoringMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priorities" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
```

```
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="palette" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="Palette" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /></
CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priorities" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="2" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="2" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYIAAAAAIAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
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```
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label="ReloadFrames" title="ReloadFrames" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priorities" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</
s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="f">NaN</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="5"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBH/UMK0CDPZThAKE4HABJFgMv
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="5" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
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<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGQEAJAAQ=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</
s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="3"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
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<a n="xfmid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJy7PVGrcYHuaftFRSorr0+b1/3IGFpG9d1ewCehAyP
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
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<a n="xmax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJwL/rXz0kKeJgeLeX4JMf0rHS7N4WP8zFPtAACT2grX
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xmin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJybv/XAiqPZJg7/CyPePNfwdciX7P6ePsPXAQCmawxH
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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</a>
<a n="ymax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="ymid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<a n="ymin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
```

```
Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="image_title" t="s">Channels</a>
<a n="stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjBAAAgAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="priority" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="stencil_title" t="s">Overlays</a>
<a n="tracker" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.ReturnResults.Outputs.__FieldResult_@Spots@20@282@29.dataitem
</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Spot" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
```

```
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Spots (2)</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString"
t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation_5.Outputs.@Spots@20@282@294.dataitem</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20SelectedReturnResults" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered"
t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">Spots (2) Selected</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20SelectedReturnResults</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Population: Spots (2) Selected</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Properties Spots (2) Selected</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.@Spots@20@282@29@20SelectedReturnResults</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTable0n" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Summary</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttrTypeTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s">SingleDefaultOverLay</a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
```

```
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20class@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Spot</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Spot" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__cnt_defaults" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="Spot" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverlayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
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</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
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c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Render_Colormode_Standard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TranslateColormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="TranslateColormode" title="ColorMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0"
disabled="0" /></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="priorities" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
```

```
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
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</m>
</a>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
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<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Labels_Labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
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</a>
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label="ReloadFrames" title="ColoringMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priorities" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</
s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
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dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAMAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="palette" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
```

```
label="ReloadFrames" title="Palette" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /></
CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priorities" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</
s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="2" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="2" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYIAAAAAIAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
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<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
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<a n="Render_ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
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<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ReloadFrames" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priorities" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</
s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="f">NaN</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="5"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBH/UMKOCDPZThAKE4HABJFgMv
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="5" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMAEAAAUAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
```

```
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGQEAJAAQ=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</
s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGAAAGAAI=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="3"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAMAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
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<a n="xfmid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJy7PVGrcYHuaftFRSorrL0+b1/3IGFpG9d1ewCehAyP
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xmax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJwL/rXz0kKeJgeLeX4JMf0rHS7N4WP8zFPtAACT2grX
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xmin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJybv/XAiqPZJg7/CyPePNfwdciX7P6ePsPXAQCmawxH
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ymax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBD/YMaDQAI0Djg==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
```

```
</a>
<a n="ymid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBB/YMaDQAIP0DXg==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ymin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMA0AAAYAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="image_title" t="s">Channels</a>
<a n="stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjBAAAgAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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</a>
<a n="priority" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="stencil_title" t="s">0overlays</a>
<a n="tracker" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.ReturnResults.Outputs.__FieldResult_@Spots@20@282@29@20Select
ed.dataitem</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
```

```
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Border</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Spot" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">Spots (2) Selected</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString"
t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation_5.Outputs.@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected5.dataitem</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cellsReturnResults" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered"
t="i">1</a>
<a n="TabLabel" t="s">many spots cells</a>
<a n="TabItemName" t="s">@many@20spots@20cellsReturnResults</a>
<a n="TabTitle" t="s">Population: many spots cells</a>
<a n="Skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIclass" t="s">sticky</a>
<a n="NewDefaultChannel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NewDefaultStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Cell</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="OKButtons" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Properties many spots cells</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Export" t="i">0</a>
<a n="UIinsert" t="s">FeedBack.@many@20spots@20cellsReturnResults</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTable0n" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="SummaryTableLabel" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>Summary</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="AttrTypeTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1"
```

```
dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGBgAAAACAAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="WizardImageView" t="i">0</a>
<a n="TypeofOverlays" t="s">SingleDefaultOverLay</a>
<a n="coloring_mode" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="scopeforimages" t="s">script</a>
<a n="yFrame2Timepoint" t="i">0</a>
<a n="cnt_overlays" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@Container@3a@200@20elements@2e"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s"></a>
<a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20class@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">1</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Cell</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Ring Region (2)</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="flag"
t="i">0</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Spots (2)</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label"
t="s">Spot Borders (2)</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20open@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="open"
t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@201@20elements@3a@20priority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="default_color" t="s">rainbow</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Cytoplasm</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20label@2c@20open@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@202@20elements@3a@20open@2c@20priority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2c@20default_color@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="flag" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@203@20elements@3a@20label@2c@20open@2c@20priority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20class@2c@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Nucleus</a>
<a n="open" t="i">0</a>
<a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="label" t="s">Membrane</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@204@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@205@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="open" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@205@20elements@3a@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20priority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@206@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20priority@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priority" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Container@3a@207@20elements@3a@20color@2c@20default_color@2c@20flag@2c@20label@2c@20open@2c@20priority@2c@20style@2e" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nucleus@20Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">4</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">4</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nucleus@20Region2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverlayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverlayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">7</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">7</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="@Ring@20Region" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">5</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">5</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Ring@20Region@20@282@29" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">6</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">6</a>
</m>
</a>
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</a>
<a n="@Spot@20Borders" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">9</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">9</a>
</m>
</a>
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<a n="@Spot@20Borders@20@282@29" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">11</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">11</a>
</m>
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</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">10</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">10</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Cell" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Cytoplasm" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">3</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">3</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Membrane" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">2</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">2</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Nucleus" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">0</a>
```

```
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">0</a>
</m>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="Spots" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="OverLayClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">NonDefault</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">8</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">8</a>
</m>
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n="memblock" c="container"><a n="LastUsedNonDefault" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color"
t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OverLayClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="OverLayOldClass" t="s">Default</a>
<a n="Position" t="i">1</a>
<a n="PositionOld" t="i">1</a>
</m>
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</m>
</a>
<a n="Controls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="general" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Render_Colormode_Standard" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="TranslateColormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="TranslateColormode" title="ColorMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0"
disabled="0" /></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="priorities" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard</
s><s>Enhanced</s><s>Highlight</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
```

```
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage:Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>MaxValue:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Plain</s><s>WeightedAverage:Extended</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
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</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
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<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Labels_Labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_Images_Images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="colormode" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ColoringMode" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priorities" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAAAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Coloring mode</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Adaptive</s><s>Fixed</s><s>Regular Color</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">WeightedAverage</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>WeightedAverage</s><s>Sum</s><s>MaxValue</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="palette" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback label="ReloadFrames" title="Palette" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priorities" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
```

```
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Color palette</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</s><s>Simple</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Extended</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Extended</s><s>Plain</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="2" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="2" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYIAAAAIAAE=
</vdata>
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c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Render_ScaleBar_ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ScaleBar" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autosubmit" t="s"></a>
<a n="callback" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ReloadFrames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="closure" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="closure"><a n="@bound" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="data" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="CallbackList" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="XmlNode" t="elem"><CallbackList><Callback
label="ReloadFrames" title="ReloadFrames" trigger="onchange" category="" priority="0" disabled="0" /
></CallbackList><a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="priorities" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYGBgAAAABAAB
</vdata>
```

```
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="defaultValue" t="s"></a>
<a n="description" t="s"></a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="highlight" t="s"></a>
<a n="inputtype" t="s">s</a>
<a n="label" t="s">Show scale</a>
<a n="labels" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="5"><vdata k="5" t="string"><s>None</s><s>Bottom Left</s><s>Top Left</s><s>Top Right</s><s>Bottom Right</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="f">NaN</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="5"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBH/UMKOCDPZThAKE4HABJFgMv
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="value_disabled" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="5" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="5" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMAEAAAUAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">input</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">replace</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="target" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="target" t="s">value</a>
<a n="upCount" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">input</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">menu</a>
<a n="uirowmode" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">1</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="attr" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="class" t="s">container</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="docID" t="s"></a>
<a n="insertmode" t="s">simple</a>
<a n="is_root" t="i">0</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="tabulate" t="i">0</a>
<a n="ui" t="s">container</a>
<a n="uiclass" t="s">container</a>
```

```
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="general_title" t="s">General controls</a>
<a n="images" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="autocontrast" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGQEAJAAQ=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</
s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3"
t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjZGAAAGAAI=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Exp1Cam1</
s><s>Exp2Cam2</s><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="3"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYEAAAAAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xfmid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJy7PVGrcYHuaftFRSorr0+b1/3IGFpG9d1ewCehAyP
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xmax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJwL/rXz0kKeJgeLeX4JMf0rHS7N4WP8zFPtAACT2grX
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="xmin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJybv/XAiqPZJg7/CyPePNfwdciX7P6ePsPXAQCmawxH
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ymax" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBD/YMaDQAIt0Djg==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ymid" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYACBB/YMaDQAIP0DXg==
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ymin" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="3" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="3" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYMA0AAAYAAE=
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
```

```
</a>
<a n="image_title" t="s">Channels</a>
<a n="stencils" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="class" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="12"><vdata k="12" t="string"><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="12"><vdata k="12" t="string"><s>rainbow</
s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</
s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="default_color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="12"><vdata k="12"
t="string"><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</
s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="flag" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="12" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="12" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYGSAAwAAAFwAC
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="label" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="12"><vdata k="12" t="string"><s>Nucleus</
s><s>Cell</s><s>Membrane</s><s>Cytoplasm</s><s>Nucleus Region</s><s>Ring Region</s><s>Ring Region
(2)</s><s>Nucleus Region2</s><s>Spots</s><s>Spot Borders</s><s>Spots (2)</s><s>Spot Borders (2)</s></
vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="open" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="12" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="12"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYCANAAAAMAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="priority" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="12" t="signed int" rank="1" dimsize0="12"
Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjYCANAAAAMAAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="12"><vdata k="12" t="string"><s>Border</
s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</
s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="stencil_title" t="s">0overlays</a>
<a n="tracker" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"
t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s><s>Gray</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="skip" t="i">1</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.ReturnResults.Outputs.__FieldResult_@many@20spots@20cells.dat
aitem</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="DefaultStencilControls" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</
s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</s><s>rainbow</
s><s>rainbow</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="style" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Border</
s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</
s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s><s>Border</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultColor" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="DefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
```

```
<a n="last_standardvalues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Cell" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="color" t="s">rainbow</a>
<a n="style" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="NonDefaultStyle" t="s">Border</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="current_frame" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Frames" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="FrameLabel" t="s">many spots cells</a>
<a n="FrameItemName" t="s">@many@20spots@20cells</a>
<a n="Images_RefString" t="s">Set(Images=AAL::GetValidImages().v_images)</a>
<a n="Stencils_RefString" t="s">Set(Stencils=AAL::GetImageViewStencils(ListRefString).v_stencils)</a>
<a n="Type" t="s">Standard</a>
<a n="ListRefString"
t="s">EvaluationData.Procedures.SelectPopulation_5.Outputs.WholeCells_filtered.dataitem</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="__version" t="f">2.79999999999999982</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@sticky:10003" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="Callbacks" t="i">0</a>
<a n="current_tab" t="s">@Nuclei@20SelectedReturnResults</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Tables" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="__ResultsTable" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="title" t="s">Results</a>
<a n="v_TableRefString" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>EvaluationData.Procedures.ReturnResults.Outputs.DefinedOutputParameters_illustrative.Da
taItem</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="IsCurrentTable" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SummaryTableOn" t="i">0</a>
<a n="AttrTypeTable" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SummaryTableLabel" t="s">Summary</a>
<a n="UseCommonTableStencil" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Inputs" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="@isordered" t="i">1</a>
<a n="Method1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">List of Outputs</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a method for defining output parameters. For deleting the current
method section select the last empty item.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Method1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.title</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
```

```

<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">List of Outputs</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="4"><vdata k="4" t="string"><s>List of
Outputs</s><s>Standard Output</s><s>Formula Output</s><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>List of
Outputs</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Number@20of@200bjects1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox to report a number of objects in the current
population</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Number@20of@200bjects1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Number of Objects</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20Number@20of@200bjects1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Area@20@5b@c2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Area@20@5b@c2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Nucleus Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20Nucleus@20Area@20@5b@c2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</

```

```

s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Area@20@5b@c2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Area@20@5b@c2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20Nucleus@20Area@20@5b@c2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Roundness1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Roundness1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Nucleus Roundness</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20Nucleus@20Roundness1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Roundness1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>

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<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Roundness1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20Nucleus@20Roundness1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20Nucleus@20Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
```

```
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20Nucleus@20Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Exp1Cam1@20Mean1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Exp1Cam1@20Mean1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Exp1Cam1@20Mean1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Exp1Cam1@20Mean1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Exp1Cam1@20Mean1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
```

```
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Exp1Cam1@20Mean1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Exp1Cam1@20Maximum1_stat1" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Exp1Cam1@20Maximum1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Exp1Cam1@20Maximum1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean/</s>
<s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</s>
<s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean/</s>
</vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Exp1Cam1@20Maximum1_onoff" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Exp1Cam1@20Maximum1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
```

```
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Exp1Cam1@20Maximum1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Region@20Exp2Cam2@20Mean1_stat1" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Region@20Exp2Cam2@20Mean1_stat1</
a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Intensity Nucleus Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Region@20Exp2Cam2@20Mean1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Region@20Exp2Cam2@20Mean1_onoff" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Region@20Exp2Cam2@20Mean1_onoff</
a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
```

```

@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Region@20Exp2Cam2@20Mean1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Intensity@20Ring@20Region@20Exp2Cam2@20Mean1_stat1" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Intensity@20Ring@20Region@20Exp2Cam2@20Mean1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Intensity Ring Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20Intensity@20Ring@20Region@20Exp2Cam2@20Mean1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Intensity@20Ring@20Region@20Exp2Cam2@20Mean1_onoff" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Intensity@20Ring@20Region@20Exp2Cam2@20Mean1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20Intensity@20Ring@20Region@20Exp2Cam2@20Mean1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>

```

```
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleoplasm@20Mean1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleoplasm@20Mean1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Intensity Nucleoplasm Mean</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20Intensity@20Nucleoplasm@20Mean1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleoplasm@20Mean1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleoplasm@20Mean1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20Intensity@20Nucleoplasm@20Mean1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Formula1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
```

```

<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Formula1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Formula</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20Formula1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Formula1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Formula1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20Formula1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Formula@20@282@291_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Formula@20@282@291_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Formula (2)</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>

```

```

</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20Formula@20@282@291_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean/<
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min/<
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean/<
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Formula@20@282@291_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Formula@20@282@291_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20Formula@20@282@291_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Total@20Spot@20Area1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Total@20Spot@20Area1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Total Spot Area</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>

```

```
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20Total@20Spot@20Area1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Total@20Spot@20Area1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Total@20Spot@20Area1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20Total@20Spot@20Area1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Relative Spot to Background Intensity</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
```

```

<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Number@20of@20Spots1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Number@20of@20Spots1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Number of Spots</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Number@20of@20Spots1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">ALL</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>ALL</s></vdata>

```

```
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Number@20of@20Spots1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Number@20of@20Spots1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20Number@20of@20Spots1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Region@20Exp3Cam2@20Mean1_stat1" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Region@20Exp3Cam2@20Mean1_stat1</
a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Intensity Nucleus Region Exp3Cam2 Mean</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Region@20Exp3Cam2@20Mean1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Region@20Exp3Cam2@20Mean1_onoff" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
```

```
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Region@20Exp3Cam2@20Mean1_onoff</
a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Region@20Exp3Cam2@20Mean1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Total@20Spot@20Area@20@282@291_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Total@20Spot@20Area@20@282@291_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Total Spot Area (2)</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20Total@20Spot@20Area@20@282@291_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Total@20Spot@20Area@20@282@291_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Total@20Spot@20Area@20@282@291_onoff</a>
```

```

<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20Total@20Spot@20Area@20@282@291_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity@20@282@291_stat1"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item"
t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity@20@282@291_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Relative Spot to Background Intensity (2)</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity@20@282@291_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean/<
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min/<
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean/<
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity@20@282@291_onoff"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item"
t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity@20@282@291_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"

```

```

c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity@20@282@291_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Number@20of@20Spots@20@282@291_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Number@20of@20Spots@20@282@291_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Number of Spots (2)</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20Number@20of@20Spots@20@282@291_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Number@20of@20Spots@20@282@291_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20Number@20of@20Spots@20@282@291_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>

```

```
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20Number@20of@20Spots@20@282@291_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20many@20spots@20cells1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20many@20spots@20cells1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">many spots cells</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20many@20spots@20cells1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20many@20spots@20cells1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d@20many@20spots@20cells1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
```

```

t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Nuclei@20Selected1.@Nuclei@20Selected@20@2d
@20many@20spots@20cells1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20@2d@20Number@20of@20objects1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox to report a number of objects in the current
population</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20@2d@20Number@20of@20objects1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Number of Objects</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextNuclei1.@Nuclei@20@2d@20Number@20of@20object
s1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Area@20@5b@c2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Area@20@5b@c2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Nucleus Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextNuclei1.@Nuclei@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Area@20@5b
@c2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>

```

```

</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Area@20@5b@c2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Area@20@5b@c2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextNuclei1.@Nuclei@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Area@20@5b
@c2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Roundness1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Roundness1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Nucleus Roundness</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextNuclei1.@Nuclei@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Roundness1
_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean/<
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean/<
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Roundness1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>

```

```
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Roundness1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextNuclei1.@Nuclei@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Roundness1
_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextNuclei1.@Nuclei@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Ratio@20Wi
dth@20to@20Length1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
```

```
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextNuclei1.@Nuclei@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Ratio@20Wi
dth@20to@20Length1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Exp1Cam1@20Mean1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Exp1Cam1@20Mean1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextNuclei1.@Nuclei@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@
20Exp1Cam1@20Mean1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Exp1Cam1@20Mean1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Exp1Cam1@20Mean1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
```

```

</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextNuclei1.@Nuclei@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@
20Exp1Cam1@20Mean1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Exp1Cam1@20Maximum1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Exp1Cam1@20Maximum1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextNuclei1.@Nuclei@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@
20Exp1Cam1@20Maximum1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean/<
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min/<
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean/<
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Exp1Cam1@20Maximum1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Exp1Cam1@20Maximum1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>

```

```

<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextNuclei1.@Nuclei@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@
20Exp1Cam1@20Maximum1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20@2d@20Nuclei@20Selected1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20@2d@20Nuclei@20Selected1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Nuclei Selected</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextNuclei1.@Nuclei@20@2d@20Nuclei@20Selected1_s
tat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Nuclei@20@2d@20Nuclei@20Selected1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Nuclei@20@2d@20Nuclei@20Selected1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextNuclei1.@Nuclei@20@2d@20Nuclei@20Selected1_s
tat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>

```

```
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@2d@2d@2d@Number@20of@20objects1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox to report a number of objects in the current
population</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@2d@2d@2d@Number@20of@20objects1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Number of Objects</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextSpots1.@Spots@2d@2d@2d@Number@20of@20objects1
_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@2d@2d@2d@Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@2d@2d@2d@Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Relative Spot to Background Intensity</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextSpots1.@Spots@2d@2d@2d@Relative@20Spot@20to@2
0Background@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@2d@2d@2d@Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
```

```

<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextSpots1.@Spots@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@2
0Background@20Intensity1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@2d@20Corrected@20Spot@20Intensity1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@2d@20Corrected@20Spot@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Corrected Spot Intensity</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextSpots1.@Spots@20@2d@20Corrected@20Spot@20Int
ensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@2d@20Corrected@20Spot@20Intensity1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@2d@20Corrected@20Spot@20Intensity1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>

```

```

<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextSpots1.@Spots@20@2d@20Corrected@20Spot@20Int
ensity1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@2d@20Uncorrected@20Spot@20Peak@20Intensity1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@2d@20Uncorrected@20Spot@20Peak@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Uncorrected Spot Peak Intensity</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextSpots1.@Spots@20@2d@20Uncorrected@20Spot@20P
eak@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@2d@20Uncorrected@20Spot@20Peak@20Intensity1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@2d@20Uncorrected@20Spot@20Peak@20Intensity1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>

```

```
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextSpots1.@Spots@20@2d@20Uncorrected@20Spot@20P
eak@20Intensity1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Contrast1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue"
t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Contrast1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spot Contrast</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextSpots1.@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Contrast1_stat1
</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Contrast1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue"
t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Contrast1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
```

```

<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextSpots1.@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Contrast1_stat1
.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spot Background Intensity</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextSpots1.@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Background@20In
tensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Background@20Intensity1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Background@20Intensity1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextSpots1.@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Background@20In
tensity1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>

```

```
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5bpx@c2@b2@5d1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5bpx@c2@b2@5d1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spot Area [px<=]</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextSpots1.@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5bpx@c2
@b2@5d1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
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s></vdata>
</m>
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</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5bpx@c2@b2@5d1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5bpx@c2@b2@5d1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextSpots1.@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5bpx@c2
@b2@5d1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@2d@20Region@20Intensity1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
```

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<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@2d@20Region@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Region Intensity</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextSpots1.@Spots@20@2d@20Region@20Intensity1_st
at1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
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s></vdata>
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<a n="@Spots@20@2d@20Region@20Intensity1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
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<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@2d@20Region@20Intensity1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextSpots1.@Spots@20@2d@20Region@20Intensity1_st
at1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20to@20Region@20Intensity1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20to@20Region@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spot to Region Intensity</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"

```

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c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
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<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextSpots1.@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20to@20Region@20I
ntensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
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<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
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</m>
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<a n="@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20to@20Region@20Intensity1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20to@20Region@20Intensity1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
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t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextSpots1.@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20to@20Region@20I
ntensity1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5b@c2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5b@c2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spot Area [ $\mu$ m<sup>2</sup></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>

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</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextSpots1.@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5b@c2@b
5m@c2@b2@5d1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5b@c2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5b@c2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextSpots1.@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5b@c2@b
5m@c2@b2@5d1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Roundness1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue"
t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Roundness1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spot Roundness</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextSpots1.@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Roundness1_stat
1</a>
```

```
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</s></vdata>
</m>
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<a n="@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Roundness1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Roundness1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextSpots1.@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Roundness1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spot Ratio Width to Length</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextSpots1.@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
```

```
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextSpots1.@Spots@20@2d@20Spot@20Ratio@20Width@2
0to@20Length1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@2d@20Spots@20Selected1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue"
t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@2d@20Spots@20Selected1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spots Selected</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextSpots1.@Spots@20@2d@20Spots@20Selected1_stat
1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</s>
<s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</s>
<s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</s>
</vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="@Spots@20@2d@20Spots@20Selected1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue"
t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@2d@20Spots@20Selected1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextSpots1.@Spots@20@2d@20Spots@20Selected1_stat
1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Number@20of@200objects1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox to report a number of objects in the current
population</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Number@20of@200objects1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Number of Objects</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20Selected1.@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@2
0Number@20of@200objects1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Relative Spot to Background Intensity</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
```

```
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20Selected1.@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@2
0Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_onoff" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20Selected1.@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@2
0Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Corrected@20Spot@20Intensity1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Corrected@20Spot@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Corrected Spot Intensity</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
```

```
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20Selected1.@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@2
0Corrected@20Spot@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Corrected@20Spot@20Intensity1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Corrected@20Spot@20Intensity1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20Selected1.@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@2
0Corrected@20Spot@20Intensity1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Uncorrected@20Spot@20Peak@20Intensity1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Uncorrected@20Spot@20Peak@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Uncorrected Spot Peak Intensity</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20Selected1.@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@2
```

```
0Uncorrected@20Spot@20Peak@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Uncorrected@20Spot@20Peak@20Intensity1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Uncorrected@20Spot@20Peak@20Intensity1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20Selected1.@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Uncorrected@20Spot@20Peak@20Intensity1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Contrast1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Contrast1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spot Contrast</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20Selected1.@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Contrast1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
```

```
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Contrast1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Contrast1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20Selected1.@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Contrast1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spot Background Intensity</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20Selected1.@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
```

```
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Background@20Intensity1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Background@20Intensity1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20Selected1.@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@2
0Spot@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5bpx@c2@b2@5d1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5bpx@c2@b2@5d1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spot Area [px<math>\leq</math>]</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20Selected1.@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@2
0Spot@20Area@20@5bpx@c2@b2@5d1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">ALL</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>ALL</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5bpx@c2@b2@5d1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
```

```
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5bpx@c2@b2@5d1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20Selected1.@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@2
0Spot@20Area@20@5bpx@c2@b2@5d1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Region@20Intensity1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Region@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Region Intensity</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20Selected1.@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@2
0Region@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Region@20Intensity1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Region@20Intensity1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
```

```
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20Selected1.@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@2
0Region@20Intensity1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20to@20Region@20Intensity1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20to@20Region@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spot to Region Intensity</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20Selected1.@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@2
0Spot@20to@20Region@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">ALL</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>ALL</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20to@20Region@20Intensity1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20to@20Region@20Intensity1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
```

```

</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20Selected1.@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@2
0Spot@20to@20Region@20Intensity1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5bc2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5bc2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spot Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20Selected1.@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@2
0Spot@20Area@20@5bc2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5bc2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5bc2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"

```

```
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20Selected1.@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@2
0Spot@20Area@20@5b@c2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Roundness1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Roundness1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spot Roundness</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20Selected1.@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@2
0Spot@20Roundness1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Roundness1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Roundness1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20Selected1.@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@2
0Spot@20Roundness1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
```

```

</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spot Ratio Width to Length</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20Selected1.@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@2
0Spot@20Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20Selected1.@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@2
0Spot@20Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Micronucleoli1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="
DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>

```

```

<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Micronucleoli1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Micronucleoli</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20Selected1.@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@2
0Micronucleoli1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Micronucleoli1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Micronucleoli1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20Selected1.@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@2
0Micronucleoli1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Intensity@20Spot@20Exp3Cam2@20Mean1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Intensity@20Spot@20Exp3Cam2@20Mean1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Intensity Spot Exp3Cam2 Mean</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</a>

```

```
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20Selected1.@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@2
0Intensity@20Spot@20Exp3Cam2@20Mean1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean/<
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean/<
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Intensity@20Spot@20Exp3Cam2@20Mean1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@20Intensity@20Spot@20Exp3Cam2@20Mean1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20Selected1.@Spots@20Selected@20@2d@2
0Intensity@20Spot@20Exp3Cam2@20Mean1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Number@20of@200bjects1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox to report a number of objects in the current
population</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Number@20of@200bjects1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Number of Objects</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
```

```
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextMicronucleoli1.@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Number
@20of@20Objects1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Relative Spot to Background Intensity</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextMicronucleoli1.@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Relati
ve@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_onoff" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
```

```

<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextMicronucleoli1.@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Relati
ve@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Corrected@20Spot@20Intensity1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Corrected@20Spot@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Corrected Spot Intensity</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextMicronucleoli1.@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Correc
ted@20Spot@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Corrected@20Spot@20Intensity1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Corrected@20Spot@20Intensity1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextMicronucleoli1.@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Correc
ted@20Spot@20Intensity1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>

```

```
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Uncorrected@20Spot@20Peak@20Intensity1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Uncorrected@20Spot@20Peak@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Uncorrected Spot Peak Intensity</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextMicronucleoli1.@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Uncorr
ected@20Spot@20Peak@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Uncorrected@20Spot@20Peak@20Intensity1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Uncorrected@20Spot@20Peak@20Intensity1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextMicronucleoli1.@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Uncorr
ected@20Spot@20Peak@20Intensity1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@20Contrast1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
```

```
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@20Contrast1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spot Contrast</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextMicronucleoli1.@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@2
0Contrast1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@20Contrast1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@20Contrast1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextMicronucleoli1.@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@2
0Contrast1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spot Background Intensity</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextMicronucleoli1.@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@2
0Background@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@20Background@20Intensity1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@20Background@20Intensity1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextMicronucleoli1.@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@2
0Background@20Intensity1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5bpx@c2@b2@5d1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5bpx@c2@b2@5d1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spot Area [px<math>\leq</math>]</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextMicronucleoli1.@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@2
0Area@20@5bpx@c2@b2@5d1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5bpx@c2@b2@5d1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5bpx@c2@b2@5d1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextMicronucleoli1.@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@2
0Area@20@5bpx@c2@b2@5d1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Region@20Intensity1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Region@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Region Intensity</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextMicronucleoli1.@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Region
@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
```

```
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Micronucleoli@2d@20Region@20Intensity1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Micronucleoli@2d@20Region@20Intensity1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextMicronucleoli1.@Micronucleoli@2d@20Region@20Intensity1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Micronucleoli@2d@20Spot@20to@20Region@20Intensity1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Micronucleoli@2d@20Spot@20to@20Region@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spot to Region Intensity</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextMicronucleoli1.@Micronucleoli@2d@20Spot@20to@20Region@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@20to@20Region@20Intensity1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@20to@20Region@20Intensity1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextMicronucleoli1.@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@2
0to@20Region@20Intensity1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5b@c2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5b@c2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spot Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextMicronucleoli1.@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@2
0Area@20@5b@c2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</s>
<s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</s>
<s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</s>
</vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5b@c2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
```

```

c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5b@c2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextMicronucleoli1.@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@2
0Area@20@5b@c2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@20Roundness1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@20Roundness1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spot Roundness</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextMicronucleoli1.@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@2
0Roundness1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean/<
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean/<
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@20Roundness1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@20Roundness1_onoff</a>

```

```

<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextMicronucleoli1.@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@2
0Roundness1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@20Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@20Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spot Ratio Width to Length</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextMicronucleoli1.@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@2
0Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@20Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@20Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>

```

```
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextMicronucleoli1.@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Spot@20Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Intensity@20Spot@20Exp3Cam2@20Mean1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Intensity@20Spot@20Exp3Cam2@20Mean1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Intensity Spot Exp3Cam2 Mean</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextMicronucleoli1.@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Intens
ity@20Spot@20Exp3Cam2@20Mean1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean/<
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean/<
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Intensity@20Spot@20Exp3Cam2@20Mean1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Intensity@20Spot@20Exp3Cam2@20Mean1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
```

```
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.TextMicronucleoli1.@Micronucleoli@20@2d@20Intens
ity@20Spot@20Exp3Cam2@20Mean1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Number@20of@20Objects1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox to report a number of objects in the current
population</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Number@20of@20Objects1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Number of Objects</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@291.@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20N
umber@20of@20Objects1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Relative Spot to Background Intensity</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@291.@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20R
elative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
```

```
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_onoff" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@291.@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20R
elative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Corrected@20Spot@20Intensity1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Corrected@20Spot@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Corrected Spot Intensity</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@291.@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20C
orrected@20Spot@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</s>
<s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</s>
<s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</s>
</vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Corrected@20Spot@20Intensity1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Corrected@20Spot@20Intensity1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@291.@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20C
orrected@20Spot@20Intensity1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Uncorrected@20Spot@20Peak@20Intensity1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Uncorrected@20Spot@20Peak@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Uncorrected Spot Peak Intensity</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@291.@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20U
ncorrected@20Spot@20Peak@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Uncorrected@20Spot@20Peak@20Intensity1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
```

```
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Uncorrected@20Spot@20Peak@20Intensity1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@291.@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20U
ncorrected@20Spot@20Peak@20Intensity1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Spot@20Contrast1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Spot@20Contrast1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spot Contrast</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@291.@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20S
pot@20Contrast1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Spot@20Contrast1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Spot@20Contrast1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@291.@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@205
pot@20Contrast1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@205Spot@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@205Spot@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spot Background Intensity</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@291.@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@205
pot@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@205Spot@20Background@20Intensity1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@205Spot@20Background@20Intensity1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@291.@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20S
pot@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5bpx@c2@b2@5d1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5bpx@c2@b2@5d1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spot Area [px<math>\leq</math>]</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@291.@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20S
pot@20Area@20@5bpx@c2@b2@5d1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5bpx@c2@b2@5d1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5bpx@c2@b2@5d1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@291.@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20S
```

```
pot@20Area@20@5bp@c2@b2@5d1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Region@20Intensity1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Region@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Region Intensity</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@291.@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20R
egion@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Region@20Intensity1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Region@20Intensity1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@291.@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20R
egion@20Intensity1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
```

```
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Spot@20to@20Region@20Intensity1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Spot@20to@20Region@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spot to Region Intensity</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@291.@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20S
pot@20to@20Region@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Spot@20to@20Region@20Intensity1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Spot@20to@20Region@20Intensity1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@291.@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20S
pot@20to@20Region@20Intensity1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Spots@20@282@29@20Selected1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
```

```
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Spots@20@282@29@20Selected1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spots (2) Selected</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@291.@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20S
pots@20@282@29@20Selected1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Spots@20@282@29@20Selected1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20Spots@20@282@29@20Selected1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@291.@Spots@20@282@29@20@2d@20S
pots@20@282@29@20Selected1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Number@20of@20Objects1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox to report a number of objects in the current
population</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Number@20of@20Objects1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Number of Objects</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
```

```
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected1.@Spots@20@282@2
9@20Selected@20@2d@20Number@20of@20objects1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item"
t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Relative Spot to Background Intensity</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected1.@Spots@20@282@2
9@20Selected@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_onoff"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item"
t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
```

```

<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected1.@Spots@20@282@2
9@20Selected@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Corrected@20Spot@20Intensity1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Corrected@20Spot@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Corrected Spot Intensity</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected1.@Spots@20@282@2
9@20Selected@20@2d@20Corrected@20Spot@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Corrected@20Spot@20Intensity1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Corrected@20Spot@20Intensity1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>

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```
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected1.@Spots@20@282@2
9@20Selected@20@2d@20Corrected@20Spot@20Intensity1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Uncorrected@20Spot@20Peak@20Intensity1_stat1" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Uncorrected@20Spot@20Peak@20Intensity1_stat1</
a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Uncorrected Spot Peak Intensity</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected1.@Spots@20@282@2
9@20Selected@20@2d@20Uncorrected@20Spot@20Peak@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Uncorrected@20Spot@20Peak@20Intensity1_onoff" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Uncorrected@20Spot@20Peak@20Intensity1_onoff</
a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected1.@Spots@20@282@2
9@20Selected@20@2d@20Uncorrected@20Spot@20Peak@20Intensity1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
```

```
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Contrast1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Contrast1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spot Contrast</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected1.@Spots@20@282@2
9@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Contrast1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">ALL</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>ALL</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Contrast1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Contrast1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected1.@Spots@20@282@2
9@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Contrast1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
```

```
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spot Background Intensity</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected1.@Spots@20@282@2
9@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Background@20Intensity1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Background@20Intensity1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected1.@Spots@20@282@2
9@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5bpx@c2@b2@5d1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5bpx@c2@b2@5d1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spot Area [px<math>\leq</math>]</a>
```

```
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected1.@Spots@20@282@2
9@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5bpx@c2@b2@5d1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5bpx@c2@b2@5d1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5bpx@c2@b2@5d1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected1.@Spots@20@282@2
9@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20Area@20@5bpx@c2@b2@5d1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Region@20Intensity1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Region@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Region Intensity</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
```

```
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected1.@Spots@20@282@2
9@20Selected@20@2d@20Region@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">ALL</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>ALL</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Region@20Intensity1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Region@20Intensity1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected1.@Spots@20@282@2
9@20Selected@20@2d@20Region@20Intensity1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20to@20Region@20Intensity1_stat1" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20to@20Region@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Spot to Region Intensity</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
```

```
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected1.@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20to@20Region@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">ALL</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean/</s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20to@20Region@20Intensity1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20to@20Region@20Intensity1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected1.@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected@20@2d@20Spot@20to@20Region@20Intensity1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">1</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Number@20of@200objects1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox to report a number of objects in the current population</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Number@20of@200objects1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Number of Objects</a>
<a n="max" t="s">1</a>
<a n="min" t="s">0</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Number@20of@200objects1_stat1</a>
```

```

<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s">1</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Area@20@5b@c2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_stat1" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Area@20@5b@c2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Nucleus Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells
@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Area@20@5b@c2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Area@20@5b@c2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_onoff" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Area@20@5b@c2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells
@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Area@20@5b@c2@b5m@c2@b2@5d1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>

```

```

<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Roundness1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Roundness1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Nucleus Roundness</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells
@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Roundness1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Roundness1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Roundness1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells
@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Roundness1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_stat1" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_stat1</a>

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<a n="Label" t="s">Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells
@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_onoff" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells
@20@2d@20Nucleus@20Ratio@20Width@20to@20Length1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Exp1Cam1@20Mean1_stat1" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Exp1Cam1@20Mean1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>

```

```
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells
@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Exp1Cam1@20Mean1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Exp1Cam1@20Mean1_onoff" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Exp1Cam1@20Mean1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells
@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Exp1Cam1@20Mean1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Exp1Cam1@20Maximum1_stat1" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Exp1Cam1@20Maximum1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
```

```

<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells
@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Exp1Cam1@20Maximum1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean/</s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean/</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Exp1Cam1@20Maximum1_onoff" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Exp1Cam1@20Maximum1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells
@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Exp1Cam1@20Maximum1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Region@20Exp2Cam2@20Mean1_stat1" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item"
t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Region@20Exp2Cam2@20Mean1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Intensity Nucleus Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells
@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Region@20Exp2Cam2@20Mean1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>

```

```

<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean/</s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean/</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Region@20Exp2Cam2@20Mean1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Region@20Exp2Cam2@20Mean1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Region@20Exp2Cam2@20Mean1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Intensity@20Ring@20Region@20Exp2Cam2@20Mean1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Intensity@20Ring@20Region@20Exp2Cam2@20Mean1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Intensity Ring Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Intensity@20Ring@20Region@20Exp2Cam2@20Mean1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean/</s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>

```

```
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Intensity@20Ring@20Region@20Exp2Cam2@20Mean1_onoff" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Intensity@20Ring@20Region@20Exp2Cam2@20Mean1_onoff</
a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells
@20@2d@20Intensity@20Ring@20Region@20Exp2Cam2@20Mean1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleoplasm@20Mean1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleoplasm@20Mean1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Intensity Nucleoplasm Mean</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells
@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleoplasm@20Mean1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleoplasm@20Mean1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleoplasm@20Mean1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells
@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleoplasm@20Mean1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Formula1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Formula1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Formula</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells
@20@2d@20Formula1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Formula1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
```

```
<a n="Item" t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Formula1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells
@20@2d@20Formula1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Formula@20@282@291_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Formula@20@282@291_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Formula (2)</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells
@20@2d@20Formula@20@282@291_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Formula@20@282@291_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a
n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Formula@20@282@291_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells
@20@2d@20Formula@20@282@291_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s"></a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Total@20Spot@20Area1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Total@20Spot@20Area1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Total Spot Area</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells
@20@2d@20Total@20Spot@20Area1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean/<
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min/<
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean/<
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Total@20Spot@20Area1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Total@20Spot@20Area1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
```

```
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells
@20@2d@20Total@20Spot@20Area1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item"
t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Relative Spot to Background Intensity</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells
@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_onoff" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item"
t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
```

```
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells
@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Number@20of@20Spots1_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Number@20of@20Spots1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Number of Spots</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells
@20@2d@20Number@20of@20Spots1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Number@20of@20Spots1_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Number@20of@20Spots1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells
@20@2d@20Number@20of@20Spots1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
```

```
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Region@20Exp3Cam2@20Mean1_stat1" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item"
t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Region@20Exp3Cam2@20Mean1_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Intensity Nucleus Region Exp3Cam2 Mean</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells
@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Region@20Exp3Cam2@20Mean1_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Region@20Exp3Cam2@20Mean1_onoff" t="m"><m
n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item"
t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Region@20Exp3Cam2@20Mean1_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells
@20@2d@20Intensity@20Nucleus@20Region@20Exp3Cam2@20Mean1_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Total@20Spot@20Area@20@282@291_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
```

```
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Total@20Spot@20Area@20@282@291_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Total Spot Area (2)</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells
@20@2d@20Total@20Spot@20Area@20@282@291_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Total@20Spot@20Area@20@282@291_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Total@20Spot@20Area@20@282@291_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells
@20@2d@20Total@20Spot@20Area@20@282@291_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity@20@282@291_stat1"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item"
t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity@20@282@291_stat1</
a>
</m>
```

```

<a n="Label" t="s">Relative Spot to Background Intensity (2)</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells
@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity@20@282@291_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity@20@282@291_onoff"
t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item"
t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity@20@282@291_onoff</
a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells
@20@2d@20Relative@20Spot@20to@20Background@20Intensity@20@282@291_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Number@20of@20Spots@20@282@291_stat1" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a statistical operation applied over objects in well</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Number@20of@20Spots@20@282@291_stat1</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Number of Spots (2)</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>

```

```
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells
@20@2d@20Number@20of@20Spots@20@282@291_stat1</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s><s>StdDev</s><s>Mean+StdDev</s><s>CV %</s><s>Mean+CV %</s><s>Sum</s><s>Max</s><s>Min</
s><s>Max+Min</s><s>Median</s><s>ALL</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="11"><vdata k="11" t="string"><s>Mean</
s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Number@20of@20Spots@20@282@291_onoff" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">0</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Activate the checkbox for reporting output parameter(s) based on the current
property</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">b</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">@many@20spots@20cells@20@2d@20Number@20of@20Spots@20@282@291_onoff</a>
<a n="Label" t="s"></a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder1.Text@many@20spots@20cells1.@many@20spots@20cells
@20@2d@20Number@20of@20Spots@20@282@291_stat1.qualifier</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">0</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Method2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Standard Output</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a method for defining output parameters. For deleting the current
method section select the last empty item.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Method2</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
```

```

<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder2.title</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Formula Output</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard
Output</s><s>Formula Output</s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Formula
Output</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Formula2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">a/b</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a formula in style  $100*(A-B)/C$  and thereupon specify below the
corresponding variables A, B, C etc. Please use only single characters (A, B,..,Y).</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Formula2</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Formula</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="FolderCounter" t="i">2</a>
<a n="FoundLetters" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>A</
s><s>B</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder2.Formula2</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">a/b</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="sPopulationTypeForFormulaOutput2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue"
t="s">Standard and Kinetic</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select population type</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">1</a>
<a n="display" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Objects</
s><s>Tracks</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">sPopulationTypeForFormulaOutput2</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Population Type</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder2.sPopulationTypeForFormulaOutput2</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>

```

```
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Standard and Kinetic</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Standard
and Kinetic</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Standard
and Kinetic</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Variable2A" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nuclei Selected -
Number of Objects</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select population - property pair to which the variable A in the formula
should correspond to</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s"></a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Variable2A</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Variable A</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefineResultsTableRow" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Number of Objects</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>ObjectCount</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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population Spots Selected</s></vdata>
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<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="LongLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spots Selected - Number of
Objects</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PopulationLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spots Selected</s></
vdata>
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base64">
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</vdata>
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```
base64">
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Objects</s></vdata>
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<m n="StatisticOverObjects" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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t="string"><s>SelectPopulation_2</s></vdata>
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<m n="PopulationCreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>SelectPopulation_5</s></vdata>
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<m n="PopulationItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>@Spots@20Selected2</
s></vdata>
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</vdata>
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<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
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</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder2.Variable2A</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Spots Selected - Number of Objects</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="103"><vdata k="103" t="string"><s>Nuclei
```



```
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<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Number of Objects,
population Spots (2) Selected</s></vdata>
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<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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<m n="LongLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spots (2) Selected - Number
of Objects</s></vdata>
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base64">
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<m n="ObjectCount_ON" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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```
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of Objects</s></vdata>
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<m n="PopulationOriginRef" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
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<m n="PopulationCreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>SelectPopulation_5</s></vdata>
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<m n="PopulationItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>@Spots@20@282@29@20Selected5</s></vdata>
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<m n="PopulationType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0Objects</s></vdata>
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<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder2.Variable2B</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Spots (2) Selected - Number of Objects</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="103"><vdata k="103" t="string"><s>Nuclei
Selected - Number of Objects</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Nucleus Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>Nuclei Selected -
Nucleus Roundness</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Nuclei Selected -
Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</
s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Nucleus Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Ring
Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Nucleoplasm Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected -
Formula</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Formula (2)</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Total Spot Area</s><s>Nuclei
Selected - Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Number of Spots</s><s>Nuclei
Selected - Intensity Nucleus Region Exp3Cam2 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Total Spot Area (2)</
s><s>Nuclei Selected - Relative Spot to Background Intensity (2)</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Number of
Spots (2)</s><s>Nuclei Selected - many spots cells</s><s>Nuclei - Number of Objects</s><s>Nuclei -
Nucleus Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>Nuclei - Nucleus Roundness</s><s>Nuclei - Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</
s><s>Nuclei - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</s><s>Nuclei - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</
s><s>Nuclei - Nuclei Selected</s><s>Spots - Number of Objects</s><s>Spots - Relative Spot to
Background Intensity</s><s>Spots - Corrected Spot Intensity</s><s>Spots - Uncorrected Spot Peak
Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot Contrast</s><s>Spots - Spot Background Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot Area
[ $\text{px}^2$ ]</s><s>Spots - Region Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot to Region Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot Area
[ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>Spots - Spot Roundness</s><s>Spots - Spot Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Spots - Spots
Selected</s><s>Spots Selected - Number of Objects</s><s>Spots Selected - Relative Spot to Background
Intensity</s><s>Spots Selected - Corrected Spot Intensity</s><s>Spots Selected - Uncorrected Spot
Peak Intensity</s><s>Spots Selected - Spot Contrast</s><s>Spots Selected - Spot Background
Intensity</s><s>Spots Selected - Spot Area [ $\text{px}^2$ ]</s><s>Spots Selected - Region Intensity</s><s>Spots
Selected - Spot to Region Intensity</s><s>Spots Selected - Spot Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>Spots Selected -
Spot Roundness</s><s>Spots Selected - Spot Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Spots Selected -
Micronucleoli</s><s>Spots Selected - Intensity Spot Exp3Cam2 Mean</s><s>Micronucleoli - Number of
Objects</s><s>Micronucleoli - Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Micronucleoli - Corrected
Spot Intensity</s><s>Micronucleoli - Uncorrected Spot Peak Intensity</s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot
Contrast</s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot Background Intensity</s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot Area [ $\text{px}^2$ ]</
s><s>Micronucleoli - Region Intensity</s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot to Region Intensity</
s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot Roundness</s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot
Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Micronucleoli - Intensity Spot Exp3Cam2 Mean</s><s>Spots (2) - Number of
Objects</s><s>Spots (2) - Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) - Corrected Spot
Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) - Uncorrected Spot Peak Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) - Spot Contrast</
s><s>Spots (2) - Spot Background Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) - Spot Area [ $\text{px}^2$ ]</s><s>Spots (2) - Region
Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) - Spot to Region Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) - Spots (2) Selected</s><s>Spots
(2) Selected - Number of Objects</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Relative Spot to Background Intensity</
s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Corrected Spot Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Uncorrected Spot Peak
Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Spot Contrast</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Spot Background
```

```

Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Spot Area [px<math>\leq</math>]</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Region Intensity</
s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Spot to Region Intensity</s><s>many spots cells - Number of Objects</
s><s>many spots cells - Nucleus Area [ $\mu\text{m}<math>\leq</math>]</s><s>many spots cells - Nucleus Roundness</s><s>many
spots cells - Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</s><s>many spots cells - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1
Mean</s><s>many spots cells - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</s><s>many spots cells - Intensity
Nucleus Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>many spots cells - Intensity Ring Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>many
spots cells - Intensity Nucleoplasm Mean</s><s>many spots cells - Formula</s><s>many spots cells -
Formula (2)</s><s>many spots cells - Total Spot Area</s><s>many spots cells - Relative Spot to
Background Intensity</s><s>many spots cells - Number of Spots</s><s>many spots cells - Intensity
Nucleus Region Exp3Cam2 Mean</s><s>many spots cells - Total Spot Area (2)</s><s>many spots cells -
Relative Spot to Background Intensity (2)</s><s>many spots cells - Number of Spots (2)</s></vdata>
</m>
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<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spots
(2) Selected - Number of Objects</s></vdata>
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</a>
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<a n="OutputNameFormula2" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Formula
Output 2</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Name of output parameter</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">OutputNameFormula2</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Output Name</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultNamingIsUsed" t="i">0</a>
<a n="DefaultString" t="s">Formula Output 2</a>
<a n="OriginalDefault" t="s">Formula Output</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="UsedListCounter" t="i">1</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder2.OutputNameFormula2</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Formula Output 2</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Method3" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Standard Output</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a method for defining output parameters. For deleting the current
method section select the last empty item.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Method3</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder3.title</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Formula Output</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard$ 
```

```

Output</s><s>Formula Output</s><s></s></vdata>
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Output</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Formula3" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">a/b</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a formula in style  $100*(A-B)/C$  and thereupon specify below the
corresponding variables A, B, C etc. Please use only single characters (A, B,..,Y).</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Formula3</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Formula</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="FolderCounter" t="i">3</a>
<a n="FoundLetters" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>A</
s><s>B</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
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</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder3.Formula3</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">a/b</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="sPopulationTypeForFormulaOutput3" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue"
t="s">Standard and Kinetic</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select population type</a>
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s><s>Tracks</s></vdata>
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<a n="Item" t="s">sPopulationTypeForFormulaOutput3</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Population Type</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="UIInsert"
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<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Standard and Kinetic</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Standard
and Kinetic</s><s>Tracks</s></vdata>
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```

```
and Kinetic</s></vdata>
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</m>
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Number of Objects</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select population - property pair to which the variable A in the formula
should correspond to</a>
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<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Variable3A</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Variable A</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
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<m n="StatisticOverObjects" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
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<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder3.Variable3A</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Spots Selected - Number of Objects</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="103"><vdata k="103" t="string"><s>Nuclei
Selected - Number of Objects</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Nucleus Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>Nuclei Selected -
Nucleus Roundness</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Nuclei Selected -
Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</
s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Nucleus Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Ring
Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Nucleoplasm Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected -
Formula</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Formula (2)</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Total Spot Area</s><s>Nuclei
Selected - Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Number of Spots</s><s>Nuclei
```



```
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<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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Objects</s></vdata>
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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Objects</s></vdata>
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```
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<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nuclei Selected - Number of Objects</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="103"><vdata k="103" t="string"><s>Nuclei
Selected - Number of Objects</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Nucleus Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>Nuclei Selected -
Nucleus Roundness</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Nuclei Selected -
Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</
s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Nucleus Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Ring
Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Nucleoplasm Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected -
Formula</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Formula (2)</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Total Spot Area</s><s>Nuclei
Selected - Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Number of Spots</s><s>Nuclei
Selected - Intensity Nucleus Region Exp3Cam2 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Total Spot Area (2)</
s><s>Nuclei Selected - Relative Spot to Background Intensity (2)</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Number of
Spots (2)</s><s>Nuclei Selected - many spots cells</s><s>Nuclei - Number of Objects</s><s>Nuclei -
Nucleus Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>Nuclei - Nucleus Roundness</s><s>Nuclei - Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</
s><s>Nuclei - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</s><s>Nuclei - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</
s><s>Nuclei - Nuclei Selected</s><s>Spots - Number of Objects</s><s>Spots - Relative Spot to
Background Intensity</s><s>Spots - Corrected Spot Intensity</s><s>Spots - Uncorrected Spot Peak
Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot Contrast</s><s>Spots - Spot Background Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot Area
[ $\text{px}^2$ ]</s><s>Spots - Region Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot to Region Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot Area
[ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>Spots - Spot Roundness</s><s>Spots - Spot Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Spots - Spots
Selected</s><s>Spots Selected - Number of Objects</s><s>Spots Selected - Relative Spot to Background
Intensity</s><s>Spots Selected - Corrected Spot Intensity</s><s>Spots Selected - Uncorrected Spot
Peak Intensity</s><s>Spots Selected - Spot Contrast</s><s>Spots Selected - Spot Background
Intensity</s><s>Spots Selected - Spot Area [ $\text{px}^2$ ]</s><s>Spots Selected - Region Intensity</s><s>Spots
Selected - Spot to Region Intensity</s><s>Spots Selected - Spot Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>Spots Selected -
Spot Roundness</s><s>Spots Selected - Spot Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Spots Selected -
Micronucleoli</s><s>Spots Selected - Intensity Spot Exp3Cam2 Mean</s><s>Micronucleoli - Number of
Objects</s><s>Micronucleoli - Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Micronucleoli - Corrected
Spot Intensity</s><s>Micronucleoli - Uncorrected Spot Peak Intensity</s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot
Contrast</s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot Background Intensity</s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot Area [ $\text{px}^2$ ]</
s><s>Micronucleoli - Region Intensity</s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot to Region Intensity</
s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot Roundness</s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot
Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Micronucleoli - Intensity Spot Exp3Cam2 Mean</s><s>Spots (2) - Number of
Objects</s><s>Spots (2) - Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) - Corrected Spot
Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) - Uncorrected Spot Peak Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) - Spot Contrast</
s><s>Spots (2) - Spot Background Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) - Spot Area [ $\text{px}^2$ ]</s><s>Spots (2) - Region
Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) - Spots (2) Selected</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Number of Objects</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Relative Spot to Background Intensity</
s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Corrected Spot Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Uncorrected Spot Peak
Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Spot Contrast</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Spot Background
Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Spot Area [ $\text{px}^2$ ]</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Region Intensity</
s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Spot to Region Intensity</s><s>many spots cells - Number of Objects</
s><s>many spots cells - Nucleus Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>many spots cells - Nucleus Roundness</s><s>many
spots cells - Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</s><s>many spots cells - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1
Mean</s><s>many spots cells - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</s><s>many spots cells - Intensity
Nucleus Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>many spots cells - Intensity Ring Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>many
spots cells - Intensity Nucleoplasm Mean</s><s>many spots cells - Formula</s><s>many spots cells -
Formula (2)</s><s>many spots cells - Total Spot Area</s><s>many spots cells - Relative Spot to
```

```

Background Intensity</s><s>many spots cells - Number of Spots</s><s>many spots cells - Intensity
Nucleus Region Exp3Cam2 Mean</s><s>many spots cells - Total Spot Area (2)</s><s>many spots cells -
Relative Spot to Background Intensity (2)</s><s>many spots cells - Number of Spots (2)</s></vdata>
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Selected - Number of Objects</s></vdata>
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Output 3</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Name of output parameter</a>
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<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">OutputNameFormula3</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Output Name</a>
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<a n="min" t="s"></a>
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<a n="OriginalDefault" t="s">Formula Output</a>
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<a n="UsedListCounter" t="i">1</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder3.OutputNameFormula3</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIslider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Spots per nuclei</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
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<a n="Method4" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Standard Output</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a method for defining output parameters. For deleting the current
method section select the last empty item.</a>
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<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Method4</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
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<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder4.title</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Formula Output</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard
Output</s><s>Formula Output</s><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Formula
Output</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>

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</a>
<a n="Formula4" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">a/b</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a formula in style  $100*(A-B)/C$  and thereupon specify below the
corresponding variables A, B, C etc. Please use only single characters (A, B,..,Y).</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Formula4</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Formula</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="FolderCounter" t="i">4</a>
<a n="FoundLetters" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>A</
s><s>B</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder4.Formula4</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">a/b</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="sPopulationTypeForFormulaOutput4" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue"
t="s">Standard and Kinetic</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select population type</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">1</a>
<a n="display" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>0objects</
s><s>Tracks</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">sPopulationTypeForFormulaOutput4</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Population Type</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert"
t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder4.sPopulationTypeForFormulaOutput4</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Standard and Kinetic</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Standard
and Kinetic</s><s>Tracks</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Standard
and Kinetic</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Variable4A" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nuclei Selected -
Number of Objects</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select population - property pair to which the variable A in the formula

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should correspond to</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Variable4A</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Variable A</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefineResultsTableRow" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Number of Objects</s></
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<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectPopulation_4</s></
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</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Number of Objects,
population Micronucleoli</s></vdata>
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</m>
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<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
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<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="LongLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Micronucleoli - Number of
Objects</s></vdata>
</m>
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vdata>
</m>
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base64">
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</vdata>
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<m n="@CV@20@25_ON" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
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<m n="Sum_ON" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<m n="Max_ON" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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```
<m n="Min_ON" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<m n="ObjectCount_ON" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
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<m n="OutputName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Micronucleoli - Number of
Objects</s></vdata>
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<m n="StatisticOverObjects" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PopulationOriginRef" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>SelectPopulation_4</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PopulationCreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>SelectPopulation_5</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PopulationItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Micronucleoli3</s></
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</m>
<m n="PopulationInternalIDNumber" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>5</s></
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</vdata>
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</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder4.Variable4A</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Micronucleoli - Number of Objects</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="103"><vdata k="103" t="string"><s>Nuclei
Selected - Number of Objects</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Nucleus Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>Nuclei Selected -
Nucleus Roundness</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Nuclei Selected -
Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</
s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Nucleus Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Ring
Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Nucleoplasm Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected -
Formula</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Formula (2)</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Total Spot Area</s><s>Nuclei
Selected - Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Number of Spots</s><s>Nuclei
Selected - Intensity Nucleus Region Exp3Cam2 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Total Spot Area (2)</
s><s>Nuclei Selected - Relative Spot to Background Intensity (2)</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Number of
Spots (2)</s><s>Nuclei Selected - many spots cells</s><s>Nuclei - Number of Objects</s><s>Nuclei -
Nucleus Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>Nuclei - Nucleus Roundness</s><s>Nuclei - Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</
s><s>Nuclei - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</s><s>Nuclei - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</
s><s>Nuclei - Nuclei Selected</s><s>Spots - Number of Objects</s><s>Spots - Relative Spot to
Background Intensity</s><s>Spots - Corrected Spot Intensity</s><s>Spots - Uncorrected Spot Peak
Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot Contrast</s><s>Spots - Spot Background Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot Area
```



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<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
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<m n="LongLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei Selected - Number of
Objects</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PopulationLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei Selected</s></
vdata>
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<m n="Mean_ON" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<m n="Sum_ON" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<m n="OutputName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei Selected - Number of
Objects</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticOverObjects" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PopulationOriginRef" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>SelectPopulation</
s></vdata>
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<m n="PopulationCreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>SelectPopulation_5</s></vdata>
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<m n="PopulationInternalIDNumber" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>1</s></
```

```
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</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder4.Variable4B</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nuclei Selected - Number of Objects</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="103"><vdata k="103" t="string"><s>Nuclei
Selected - Number of Objects</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Nucleus Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>Nuclei Selected -
Nucleus Roundness</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Nuclei Selected -
Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</
s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Nucleus Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Ring
Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Nucleoplasm Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected -
Formula</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Formula (2)</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Total Spot Area</s><s>Nuclei
Selected - Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Number of Spots</s><s>Nuclei
Selected - Intensity Nucleus Region Exp3Cam2 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Total Spot Area (2)</
s><s>Nuclei Selected - Relative Spot to Background Intensity (2)</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Number of
Spots (2)</s><s>Nuclei Selected - many spots cells</s><s>Nuclei - Number of Objects</s><s>Nuclei -
Nucleus Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>Nuclei - Nucleus Roundness</s><s>Nuclei - Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</
s><s>Nuclei - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</s><s>Nuclei - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</
s><s>Nuclei - Nuclei Selected</s><s>Spots - Number of Objects</s><s>Spots - Relative Spot to
Background Intensity</s><s>Spots - Corrected Spot Intensity</s><s>Spots - Uncorrected Spot Peak
Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot Contrast</s><s>Spots - Spot Background Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot Area
[ $\text{px}^2$ ]</s><s>Spots - Region Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot to Region Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot Area
[ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>Spots - Spot Roundness</s><s>Spots - Spot Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Spots - Spots
Selected</s><s>Spots Selected - Number of Objects</s><s>Spots Selected - Relative Spot to Background
Intensity</s><s>Spots Selected - Corrected Spot Intensity</s><s>Spots Selected - Uncorrected Spot
Peak Intensity</s><s>Spots Selected - Spot Contrast</s><s>Spots Selected - Spot Background
Intensity</s><s>Spots Selected - Spot Area [ $\text{px}^2$ ]</s><s>Spots Selected - Region Intensity</s><s>Spots
Selected - Spot to Region Intensity</s><s>Spots Selected - Spot Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>Spots Selected -
Spot Roundness</s><s>Spots Selected - Spot Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Spots Selected -
Micronucleoli</s><s>Spots Selected - Intensity Spot Exp3Cam2 Mean</s><s>Micronucleoli - Number of
Objects</s><s>Micronucleoli - Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Micronucleoli - Corrected
Spot Intensity</s><s>Micronucleoli - Uncorrected Spot Peak Intensity</s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot
Contrast</s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot Background Intensity</s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot Area [ $\text{px}^2$ ]/
s><s>Micronucleoli - Region Intensity</s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot to Region Intensity</
s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot Roundness</s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot
Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Micronucleoli - Intensity Spot Exp3Cam2 Mean</s><s>Spots (2) - Number of
Objects</s><s>Spots (2) - Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) - Corrected Spot
Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) - Uncorrected Spot Peak Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) - Spot Contrast</
s><s>Spots (2) - Spot Background Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) - Spot Area [ $\text{px}^2$ ]</s><s>Spots (2) - Region
Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) - Spot to Region Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) - Spots (2) Selected</s><s>Spots
(2) Selected - Number of Objects</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Relative Spot to Background Intensity</
s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Corrected Spot Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Uncorrected Spot Peak
Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Spot Contrast</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Spot Background
Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Spot Area [ $\text{px}^2$ ]</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Region Intensity</
s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Spot to Region Intensity</s><s>many spots cells - Number of Objects</
s><s>many spots cells - Nucleus Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>many spots cells - Nucleus Roundness</s><s>many
spots cells - Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</s><s>many spots cells - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1
Mean</s><s>many spots cells - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</s><s>many spots cells - Intensity
Nucleus Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>many spots cells - Intensity Ring Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>many
spots cells - Intensity Nucleoplasm Mean</s><s>many spots cells - Formula</s><s>many spots cells -
Formula (2)</s><s>many spots cells - Total Spot Area</s><s>many spots cells - Relative Spot to
Background Intensity</s><s>many spots cells - Number of Spots</s><s>many spots cells - Intensity
Nucleus Region Exp3Cam2 Mean</s><s>many spots cells - Total Spot Area (2)</s><s>many spots cells -
Relative Spot to Background Intensity (2)</s><s>many spots cells - Number of Spots (2)</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Nuclei
Selected - Number of Objects</s></vdata>
</m>
```

```

</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="OutputNameFormula4" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Formula
Output 4</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Name of output parameter</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">OutputNameFormula4</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Output Name</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultNamingIsUsed" t="i">0</a>
<a n="DefaultString" t="s">Formula Output 4</a>
<a n="OriginalDefault" t="s">Formula Output</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="UsedListCounter" t="i">1</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder4.OutputNameFormula4</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Formula Output 4</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Method5" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Standard Output</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select a method for defining output parameters. For deleting the current
method section select the last empty item.</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Method5</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Method</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock"
c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuningLabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder5.title</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Formula Output</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard
Output</s><s>Formula Output</s><s></s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Formula
Output</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Formula5" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">a/b</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Define a formula in style 100*(A-B)/C and thereupon specify below the
corresponding variables A, B, C etc. Please use only single characters (A, B,...,Y).</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Formula5</a>

```

```

<a n="Label" t="s">Formula</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="FolderCounter" t="i">5</a>
<a n="FoundLetters" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>A</s><s>B</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder5.Formula5</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">a/b</a>
<a n="wizardstep" t="s"></a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="sPopulationTypeForFormulaOutput5" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Standard and Kinetic</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select population type</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">1</a>
<a n="display" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>0Objects</s><s>Tracks</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">sPopulationTypeForFormulaOutput5</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Population Type</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder5.sPopulationTypeForFormulaOutput5</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Standard and Kinetic</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="2"><vdata k="2" t="string"><s>Standard and Kinetic</s><s>Tracks</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
<a n="v_values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Standard and Kinetic</s></vdata>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="Variable5A" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultValue" t="s">Nuclei Selected - Number of Objects</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select population - property pair to which the variable A in the formula should correspond to</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Variable5A</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Variable A</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefineResultsTableRow" t="m"><m n="memblock"

```

```
c="Table"><m n="Label" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Intensity Spot Exp3Cam2
Mean</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Scalar</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>_Scalar15</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>CalculateIntensityProperties_6</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>22</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Intensity Spot Exp3Cam2
Mean</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean intensity of Spot by
channel Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot;Nucleus
Region</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean Intensity</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Counts/Pixel</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean Intensity</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean intensity of Spot by channel
Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="LongLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Micronucleoli - Intensity
Spot Exp3Cam2 Mean</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PopulationLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Micronucleoli</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="Mean_ON" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<m n="StdDev_ON" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjAAAAAQAB
</vdata>
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eJxjAAAAAQAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="Sum_ON" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</vdata>
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</vdata>
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```

```
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</vdata>
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base64">
eJxjAAAAAQAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<m n="FormulaOutput_ON" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-
Encoding="zlib base64">
eJxjAAAAAQAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<m n="OutputName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Micronucleoli - Intensity
Spot Exp3Cam2 Mean</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticOverObjects" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
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t="string"><s>SelectPopulation_4</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PopulationCreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>SelectPopulation_5</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PopulationItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Micronucleoli3</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="PopulationInternalIDNumber" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>5</s></
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</m>
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</m>
<m n="RowNumberTemp" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="double" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjYAACHwAHAAGoANE=
</vdata>
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</a>
<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
</a>
<a n="tuninglabel" t="s">Tuning of parameter</a>
<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
</m>
</a>
<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder5.Variable5A</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Micronucleoli - Intensity Spot Exp3Cam2 Mean</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="103"><vdata k="103" t="string"><s>Nuclei
Selected - Number of Objects</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Nucleus Area [µm<sup>2</sup>]</s><s>Nuclei Selected -
Nucleus Roundness</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Nuclei Selected -
Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</
s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Nucleus Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Ring
Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Nucleoplasm Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected -
Formula</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Formula (2)</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Total Spot Area</s><s>Nuclei
Selected - Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Number of Spots</s><s>Nuclei
Selected - Intensity Nucleus Region Exp3Cam2 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Total Spot Area (2)</
s><s>Nuclei Selected - Relative Spot to Background Intensity (2)</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Number of
Spots (2)</s><s>Nuclei Selected - many spots cells</s><s>Nuclei - Number of Objects</s><s>Nuclei -
Nucleus Area [µm<sup>2</sup>]</s><s>Nuclei - Nucleus Roundness</s><s>Nuclei - Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</
s><s>Nuclei - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</s><s>Nuclei - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</
s><s>Nuclei - Nuclei Selected</s><s>Spots - Number of Objects</s><s>Spots - Relative Spot to
Background Intensity</s><s>Spots - Corrected Spot Intensity</s><s>Spots - Uncorrected Spot Peak
Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot Contrast</s><s>Spots - Spot Background Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot Area
[px<sup>2</sup>]</s><s>Spots - Region Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot to Region Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot Area
[µm<sup>2</sup>]</s><s>Spots - Spot Roundness</s><s>Spots - Spot Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Spots - Spots
Selected</s><s>Spots Selected - Number of Objects</s><s>Spots Selected - Relative Spot to Background
Intensity</s><s>Spots Selected - Corrected Spot Intensity</s><s>Spots Selected - Uncorrected Spot
```



```
<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefineResultsTableRow" t="m"><m n="memblock"
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Mean</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="AttrType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Scalar</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="ItemName" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>_Scalar15</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="OriginRegion" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="CreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>CalculateIntensityProperties_5</s></vdata>
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<m n="CreatedAtNo" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>21</s></vdata>
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<m n="RegionType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PreviousLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Intensity Spot Exp3Cam2
Mean</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Commentary" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean intensity of Spot by
channel Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="RegionTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spot;Nucleus
Region</s></vdata>
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<m n="Statistic" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean Intensity</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Channel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
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<m n="HiddenStatus" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>0</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="Unit" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Counts/Pixel</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="StatisticDetailed1" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean Intensity</s></
vdata>
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<m n="ID" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Mean intensity of Spot by channel
Exp3Cam2</s></vdata>
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<m n="ParType" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>d</s></vdata>
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<m n="ParTypeDetailed" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s></s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="LongLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spots Selected - Intensity
Spot Exp3Cam2 Mean</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PopulationLabel" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1" t="string"><s>Spots Selected</s></
vdata>
</m>
<m n="Mean_ON" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
eJxjAAAAQAB
</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
</m>
<m n="StdDev_ON" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
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</vdata>
<a n="factor" t="f">1</a>
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<m n="@CV@20@25_ON" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib
base64">
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<m n="Sum_ON" c="vector"><vdata k="1" t="byte" rank="1" dimsize0="1" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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```
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Spot Exp3Cam2 Mean</s></vdata>
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<m n="PopulationOriginRef" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>SelectPopulation_2</s></vdata>
</m>
<m n="PopulationCreatedAt" c="vector" t="string" k="1"><vdata k="1"
t="string"><s>SelectPopulation_5</s></vdata>
</m>
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s></vdata>
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<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Spots Selected - Intensity Spot Exp3Cam2 Mean</a>
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Selected - Number of Objects</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Nucleus Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>Nuclei Selected -
Nucleus Roundness</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Nuclei Selected -
Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</
s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Nucleus Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Ring
Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Nucleoplasm Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected -
Formula</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Formula (2)</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Total Spot Area</s><s>Nuclei
Selected - Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Number of Spots</s><s>Nuclei
Selected - Intensity Nucleus Region Exp3Cam2 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Total Spot Area (2)</
s><s>Nuclei Selected - Relative Spot to Background Intensity (2)</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Number of
Spots (2)</s><s>Nuclei Selected - many spots cells</s><s>Nuclei - Number of Objects</s><s>Nuclei -
Nucleus Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>Nuclei - Nucleus Roundness</s><s>Nuclei - Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</
s><s>Nuclei - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</s><s>Nuclei - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</
s><s>Nuclei - Nuclei Selected</s><s>Spots - Number of Objects</s><s>Spots - Relative Spot to
Background Intensity</s><s>Spots - Corrected Spot Intensity</s><s>Spots - Uncorrected Spot Peak
Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot Contrast</s><s>Spots - Spot Background Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot Area
[ $\text{px}^2$ ]</s><s>Spots - Region Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot to Region Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot Area
[ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>Spots - Spot Roundness</s><s>Spots - Spot Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Spots - Spots
Selected</s><s>Spots Selected - Number of Objects</s><s>Spots Selected - Relative Spot to Background
```



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<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
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<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
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method section select the last empty item.</a>
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c="container"></m>
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<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="ProcedureIDName" t="s">ReturnResults</a>
<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Formula Output</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="3"><vdata k="3" t="string"><s>Standard
Output</s><s>Formula Output</s><s></s></vdata>
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Output</s></vdata>
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<a n="Description" t="s">Define a formula in style  $100*(A-B)/C$  and thereupon specify below the
corresponding variables A, B, C etc. Please use only single characters (A, B,..,Y).</a>
<a n="disabled" t="i">0</a>
<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Formula6</a>
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<a n="max" t="s"></a>
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<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Numeric</a>
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<a n="qualifier" t="s"></a>
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<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
<a n="UIInsert" t="s">UI.InputParameters.ReturnResults.MethodFolder6.Formula6</a>
<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="UISlider" t="s">0</a>
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<a n="value" t="s">a/b</a>
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<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
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and Kinetic</s></s></vdata>
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Number of Objects</a>
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should correspond to</a>
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<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">Variable6A</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Variable A</a>
<a n="ParameterType" t="s">Discrete</a>
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```

```
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<a n="WizardRulerOff" t="i">0</a>
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<a n="skip" t="i">0</a>
<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
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<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">many spots cells - Number of Objects</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="103"><vdata k="103" t="string"><s>Nuclei
Selected - Number of Objects</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Nucleus Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>Nuclei Selected -
Nucleus Roundness</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Nuclei Selected -
Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</
s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Nucleus Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Ring
Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Nucleoplasm Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected -
Formula</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Formula (2)</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Total Spot Area</s><s>Nuclei
Selected - Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Number of Spots</s><s>Nuclei
Selected - Intensity Nucleus Region Exp3Cam2 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Total Spot Area (2)</
s><s>Nuclei Selected - Relative Spot to Background Intensity (2)</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Number of
Spots (2)</s><s>Nuclei Selected - many spots cells</s><s>Nuclei - Number of Objects</s><s>Nuclei -
Nucleus Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>Nuclei - Nucleus Roundness</s><s>Nuclei - Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</
s><s>Nuclei - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</s><s>Nuclei - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</
s><s>Nuclei - Nuclei Selected</s><s>Spots - Number of Objects</s><s>Spots - Relative Spot to
Background Intensity</s><s>Spots - Corrected Spot Intensity</s><s>Spots - Uncorrected Spot Peak
Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot Contrast</s><s>Spots - Spot Background Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot Area
[ $\text{px}^2$ ]</s><s>Spots - Region Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot to Region Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot Area
[ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>Spots - Spot Roundness</s><s>Spots - Spot Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Spots - Spots
Selected</s><s>Spots Selected - Number of Objects</s><s>Spots Selected - Relative Spot to Background
Intensity</s><s>Spots Selected - Corrected Spot Intensity</s><s>Spots Selected - Uncorrected Spot
Peak Intensity</s><s>Spots Selected - Spot Contrast</s><s>Spots Selected - Spot Background
Intensity</s><s>Spots Selected - Spot Area [ $\text{px}^2$ ]</s><s>Spots Selected - Region Intensity</s><s>Spots
Selected - Spot to Region Intensity</s><s>Spots Selected - Spot Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>Spots Selected -
Spot Roundness</s><s>Spots Selected - Spot Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Spots Selected -
Micronucleoli</s><s>Spots Selected - Intensity Spot Exp3Cam2 Mean</s><s>Micronucleoli - Number of
Objects</s><s>Micronucleoli - Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Micronucleoli - Corrected
Spot Intensity</s><s>Micronucleoli - Uncorrected Spot Peak Intensity</s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot
Contrast</s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot Background Intensity</s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot Area [ $\text{px}^2$ ]</
s><s>Micronucleoli - Region Intensity</s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot to Region Intensity</
s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot Roundness</s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot
Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Micronucleoli - Intensity Spot Exp3Cam2 Mean</s><s>Spots (2) - Number of
Objects</s><s>Spots (2) - Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) - Corrected Spot
Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) - Uncorrected Spot Peak Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) - Spot Contrast</
s><s>Spots (2) - Spot Background Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) - Spot Area [ $\text{px}^2$ ]</s><s>Spots (2) - Region
Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) - Spot to Region Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) - Spots (2) Selected</s><s>Spots
(2) Selected - Number of Objects</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Relative Spot to Background Intensity</
s></m>
</a>
```

```

s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Corrected Spot Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Uncorrected Spot Peak
Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Spot Contrast</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Spot Background
Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Spot Area [px<math>\leq</math>]</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Region Intensity</
s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Spot to Region Intensity</s><s>many spots cells - Number of Objects</
s><s>many spots cells - Nucleus Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2</math>]</s><s>many spots cells - Nucleus Roundness</s><s>many
spots cells - Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</s><s>many spots cells - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1
Mean</s><s>many spots cells - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</s><s>many spots cells - Intensity
Nucleus Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>many spots cells - Intensity Ring Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>many
spots cells - Intensity Nucleoplasm Mean</s><s>many spots cells - Formula</s><s>many spots cells -
Formula (2)</s><s>many spots cells - Total Spot Area</s><s>many spots cells - Relative Spot to
Background Intensity</s><s>many spots cells - Number of Spots</s><s>many spots cells - Intensity
Nucleus Region Exp3Cam2 Mean</s><s>many spots cells - Total Spot Area (2)</s><s>many spots cells -
Relative Spot to Background Intensity (2)</s><s>many spots cells - Number of Spots (2)</s></vdata>
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spots cells - Number of Objects</s></vdata>
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Number of Objects</a>
<a n="Description" t="s">Select population - property pair to which the variable B in the formula
should correspond to</a>
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<a n="InputComplexity" t="s">Complex</a>
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<a n="Item" t="s">Variable6B</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Variable B</a>
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<a n="UIPresent" t="i">1</a>
<a n="unit" t="s"></a>
<a n="value" t="s">Nuclei Selected - Number of Objects</a>
<a n="values" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector" t="string" k="103"><vdata k="103" t="string"><s>Nuclei Selected - Number of Objects</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Nucleus Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Nucleus Roundness</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Nucleus Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Ring Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Nucleoplasm Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Formula</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Formula (2)</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Total Spot Area</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Number of Spots</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Nucleus Region Exp3Cam2 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Total Spot Area (2)</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Relative Spot to Background Intensity (2)</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Number of Spots (2)</s><s>Nuclei Selected - many spots cells</s><s>Nuclei - Number of Objects</s><s>Nuclei - Nucleus Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>Nuclei - Nucleus Roundness</s><s>Nuclei - Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Nuclei - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</s><s>Nuclei - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</s><s>Nuclei - Nuclei Selected</s><s>Spots - Number of Objects</s><s>Spots - Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Spots - Corrected Spot Intensity</s><s>Spots - Uncorrected Spot Peak Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot Contrast</s><s>Spots - Spot Background Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot Area [ $\text{px}^2$ ]</s><s>Spots - Region Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot to Region Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>Spots - Spot Roundness</s><s>Spots - Spot Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Spots - Spots Selected</s><s>Spots Selected - Number of Objects</s><s>Spots Selected - Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Spots Selected - Corrected Spot Intensity</s><s>Spots Selected - Uncorrected Spot Peak Intensity</s><s>Spots Selected - Spot Contrast</s><s>Spots Selected - Spot Background Intensity</s><s>Spots Selected - Spot Area [ $\text{px}^2$ ]</s><s>Spots Selected - Region Intensity</s><s>Spots Selected - Spot to Region Intensity</s><s>Spots Selected - Spot Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>Spots Selected - Spot Roundness</s><s>Spots Selected - Spot Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Spots Selected - Micronucleoli</s><s>Spots Selected - Intensity Spot Exp3Cam2 Mean</s><s>Micronucleoli - Number of Objects</s><s>Micronucleoli - Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Micronucleoli - Corrected Spot Intensity</s><s>Micronucleoli - Uncorrected Spot Peak Intensity</s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot Contrast</s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot Background Intensity</s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot Area [ $\text{px}^2$ ]</s><s>Micronucleoli - Region Intensity</s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot to Region Intensity</s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot Roundness</s><s>Micronucleoli - Spot Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Micronucleoli - Intensity Spot Exp3Cam2 Mean</s><s>Spots (2) - Number of Objects</s><s>Spots (2) - Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) - Corrected Spot Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) - Uncorrected Spot Peak Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) - Spot Contrast</s><s>Spots (2) - Spot Background Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) - Spot Area [ $\text{px}^2$ ]</s><s>Spots (2) - Region Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) - Spot to Region Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) - Spots (2) Selected</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Number of Objects</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Corrected Spot Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Uncorrected Spot Peak Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Spot Contrast</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Spot Background Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Spot Area [ $\text{px}^2$ ]</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Region Intensity</s><s>Spots (2) Selected - Spot to Region Intensity</s><s>many spots cells - Number of Objects</s><s>many spots cells - Nucleus Area [ $\mu\text{m}^2$ ]</s><s>many spots cells - Nucleus Roundness</s><s>many spots cells - Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</s><s>many spots cells - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</s><s>many spots cells - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</s><s>many spots cells - Intensity Nucleus Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>many spots cells - Intensity Ring Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>many spots cells - Intensity Nucleoplasm Mean</s><s>many spots cells - Formula</s><s>many spots cells - Formula (2)</s><s>many spots cells - Total Spot Area</s><s>many spots cells - Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>many spots cells - Number of Spots</s><s>many spots cells - Intensity Nucleus Region Exp3Cam2 Mean</s><s>many spots cells - Total Spot Area (2)</s><s>many spots cells - Relative Spot to Background Intensity (2)</s><s>many spots cells - Number of Spots (2)</s></vdata></m>
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<a n="Description" t="s">Name of output parameter</a>
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<a n="InputType" t="s">s</a>
<a n="Item" t="s">OutputNameFormula6</a>
<a n="Label" t="s">Output Name</a>
<a n="max" t="s"></a>
<a n="min" t="s"></a>
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<a n="private" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"><a n="DefaultNamingIsUsed" t="i">0</a>
<a n="DefaultString" t="s">Formula Output 6</a>
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<a n="PreviousValues" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
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<a n="SimpleLastValue" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="container"></m>
```

```

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<a n="SkipWizard" t="i">1</a>
<a n="step" t="s"></a>
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c="container"></m>
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c="container"></m>
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of Objects</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Nucleus Area [µm<sup>2</sup>]</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Nucleus Roundness</
s><s>Nuclei Selected - Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Nucleus
Exp1Cam1 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</s><s>Nuclei Selected -
Intensity Nucleus Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Ring Region Exp2Cam2 Mean</
s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity Nucleoplasm Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Formula</s><s>Nuclei
Selected - Formula (2)</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Total Spot Area</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Relative Spot
to Background Intensity</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Number of Spots</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Intensity
Nucleus Region Exp3Cam2 Mean</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Total Spot Area (2)</s><s>Nuclei Selected -
Relative Spot to Background Intensity (2)</s><s>Nuclei Selected - Number of Spots (2)</s><s>Nuclei
Selected - many spots cells</s><s>Nuclei - Number of Objects</s><s>Nuclei - Nucleus Area [µm<sup>2</sup>]</
s><s>Nuclei - Nucleus Roundness</s><s>Nuclei - Nucleus Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Nuclei - Intensity
Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Mean</s><s>Nuclei - Intensity Nucleus Exp1Cam1 Maximum</s><s>Nuclei - Nuclei
Selected</s><s>Spots - Number of Objects</s><s>Spots - Relative Spot to Background Intensity</
s><s>Spots - Corrected Spot Intensity</s><s>Spots - Uncorrected Spot Peak Intensity</s><s>Spots -
Spot Contrast</s><s>Spots - Spot Background Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot Area [px<sup>2</sup>]</s><s>Spots -
Region Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot to Region Intensity</s><s>Spots - Spot Area [µm<sup>2</sup>]</s><s>Spots -
Spot Roundness</s><s>Spots - Spot Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Spots - Spots Selected</s><s>Spots
Selected - Number of Objects</s><s>Spots Selected - Relative Spot to Background Intensity</s><s>Spots
Selected - Corrected Spot Intensity</s><s>Spots Selected - Uncorrected Spot Peak Intensity</
s><s>Spots Selected - Spot Contrast</s><s>Spots Selected - Spot Background Intensity</s><s>Spots
Selected - Spot Area [px<sup>2</sup>]</s><s>Spots Selected - Region Intensity</s><s>Spots Selected - Spot to
Region Intensity</s><s>Spots Selected - Spot Area [µm<sup>2</sup>]</s><s>Spots Selected - Spot Roundness</
s><s>Spots Selected - Spot Ratio Width to Length</s><s>Spots Selected - Micronucleoli</s><s>Spots
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```



```
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Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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<a n="ReturnResults" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="2" t="signed int" rank="1"
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<a n="SelectPopulation" t="m"><m n="memblock" c="vector"><vdata k="6" t="signed int" rank="1"
dimsize0="6" Transfer-Encoding="zlib base64">
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</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</a>
</m>
</eventdata></EventXml>
```

#end:attachment